

D1.1 Pilots Planning Documentation

WP1 Pilots Planning and Execution

FDEUSTO

Report

Public

Version	Date	Description of main changes	Author
1.0	2017/05/30	First draft	ALL
2.0	2017/11/17	Included Appendixes and PO's comments regarding Legal section, Target Groups and Architecture,	FDEUSTO
2.1	2017/11/23	Format improvements suggested by ENG included	FDEUSTO
2.2	2017/11/23	Wording improvements suggested by VW included	FDEUSTO
2.3	2017/11/24	Improvements suggested by SOFTLINE included	FDEUSTO
2.4	2017/11/28	Included legislation about Green Procurement, page numbering	FDEUSTO
2.5	17/12/2018	This new version includes the changes requested by the reviewers	FDEUSTO

Table of content

1.	Introduction	5
2.	Legislative framework	9
2.1	Methodology	10
2.1.	Results	11
2.2.	Conclusions	15
3.	Scope of the Project	16
3.1.	Target Groups.....	16
3.1.1	Methodology	16
3.1.2	Results	19
3.2.	User Requirement analysis and use case definition	25
3.2.1	Requirement analysis	25
3.2.2	Use case analysis	27
3.2.3	Results	28
4.	Technical requirements.....	32
5.	Overview of the architecture	32
5.1.	CO CREATION ACTIVITY TO DEFINE THE PILOTS ARCHITECTURE.....	32
5.2.	PILOTS ARCHITECTURE results	37
5.2.1	Pilots with already deployed solutions: Cascais and Seveso	40
5.2.2	Pilots without deployed solutions: HALANDRI and ZAMUDIO	41
5.3.	Definition of the APIs	43
6.	Pilots deployment schedule	46
7.	Annexes of Deliverable D1.1	47

Figures

FIGURE 1 WASTE4THINK PILOTS SITES.....	6
FIGURE 2 CONTENT OF THE DELIVERABLE 1.1	7
FIGURE 3 LEGISLATIVE FRAMEWORK FOR THE WASTE4THINK PROJECT	9
FIGURE 4 TYPES OF EU LEGAL ACTS.....	10
FIGURE 5 MAIN RESULT OF THE SOCIAL WORKING GROUP.....	17
FIGURE 6 HIGH-LEVEL TARGET GROUPS DIAGRAM.....	21
FIGURE 7 RELATION BETWEEN REQUIREMENTS AND USE CASES.....	25
FIGURE 8 ARCHITECTURE MADE FOR CASCAIS.....	34
FIGURE 9 ARCHITECTURE MADE FOR HALANDRI	35
FIGURE 10 ARCHITECTURE MADE FOR SEVESO.....	35
FIGURE 11 ARCHITECTURE MADE FOR ZAMUDIO	36
FIGURE 12 GENERIC IOT COMMUNICATION ARCHITECTURE.....	39
FIGURE 13 CONCEPTUAL ARCHITECTURE OF CASCAIS	41
FIGURE 14 CONCEPTUAL ARCHITECTURE OF SEVESO	41
FIGURE 15 CONCEPTUAL ARCHITECTURE OF HALANDRI	42
FIGURE 16 CONCEPTUAL ARCHITECTURE OF ZAMUDIO	43
FIGURE 17 LOGICAL ARCHITECTURE OF THE PROJECT	45

Tables

TABLE 1. EXPECTED RESULTS OF WASTE4THINK.	5
TABLE 2 EUROPEAN UNION LEGISLATIVE FRAMEWORK	11
TABLE 3 ZAMUDIO'S PILOT LEGISLATIVE FRAMEWORK	13
TABLE 4 CASCAIS'S PILOT SINGULAR LEGISLATIVE FRAMEWORK	14
TABLE 5 SEVESO'S PILOT SINGULAR LEGISLATIVE FRAMEWORK	14
TABLE 6 HALANDRI'S PILOT SINGULAR LEGISLATIVE FRAMEWORK	15
TABLE 7 RESULTS FROM THE SOCIAL DISCUSSION	17
TABLE 8 RESULTS FROM THE TECHNICAL DISCUSSION	18
TABLE 9 HIGH AND LOW LEVEL TARGET GROUPS	19
TABLE 10 TARGET GROUP DESCRIPTION	21
TABLE 11 REQUIREMENT GATHERING TEMPLATE	26
TABLE 12 TEMPLATE FOR THE USE CASE DEFINITION	27
TABLE 13 LIST OF THE USE CASES IDENTIFIED FOR WASTE4THINK	29

Glossary

PAYT: [Pay as you throw](#)

ICT: [Information and communications technology](#)

Volere methodology: Requirements Specification Template and other requirements and business analysis resources.

FIWARE: Platform to help in the development and deployment of the Future Internet.

Mawis: Software platform to manage the waste collection and for monitoring and optimizing PAYT by MOBA.

Wintarif: Software for the waste collection and tariff management by SOFTLINE.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable defines all the cross-cutting aspects of the Waste4Think Project that should be taken into consideration for the subsequent developments. In particular, the document will be divided into 4 Sections:

- **Legislative Framework** (Section 2): An assessment of the legal framework has been carried out in order to ensure the full compliance of the pilots execution. The first scale analyzed is the EU legislation that provides the basis and the frame of reference for the body of laws and policies of all EU Member States. The second level is applied to all pilots. They have been identified all the laws and reference documents at the national, regional and local levels.
- **Scope of the project** (Section 3): It involves the following actions:
 - Identification of the **target groups** involved in the project (direct users, policy makers and municipalities, waste managers, stakeholders, scientific community and civil associations) has been made through a participatory activity among Waste4Think partners.
 - **User requirement analysis** for the identification of the needs of the 20 Waste4Think Eco-solutions has been carried out using the **Volere methodology**.
 - **Use Case Analysis**: A set of use cases for the 20 Waste4Think Eco-solutions has been defined. Use Case Analysis aims at organizing how external entities (actors) interact with the system, emphasizing on gathering the functional requirements of the system.
- **Technical requirements** (Section 4): This section introduces the methodology followed to specify the technical requirements. To this purpose a deep description of the 4 collection systems subjected to study has been made including all the solutions (hardware and software) that are already running and in which the W4T eco-solutions should be integrated
- **Overview of the architecture** (Section 5): This section describes the methodology used to define the overall architecture. Four architectures have been defined, one per pilot site, using a co-creation activity based on **Card sorting methodology**. This technique, based on the user experience field to build dendrograms, has been adapted to this purpose.
- **Pilots deployment status** (Section 6): This section shows the foreseen status of the eco-solutions deployment which will allow the monitoring of the system in each pilot site.

1. Introduction

One of the main perspectives in the Europe 2020 Strategy is to further advance progress towards the achievement of a **Circular Economy (CE)**. The Waste4Think project promotes a major transformation of the current model of waste management so as to convert this model into the foundation of the principles of this new economy paradigm in 4 municipalities in Europe.

The main objective of Waste4Think is to move forward the current waste management practices into a Circular Economy motto demonstrating the value of integrating and validating the following 20 eco-innovative solutions that cover all the waste value chain (Table 1). The particular objectives are:

- Reduction of waste generation thanks to prevention campaigns and cooperative activities to promote reuse and eco-design solutions.
- Promotion of behavioral changes in the waste generators by awareness campaigns and new educational tools in order to foster more sustainable consumption and production habits and to increase the rate of waste sorting.
- To improve the integral waste management services reducing their management costs and the GHG (greenhouse gas) emissions.
- To reduce the amount of primary waste deposited in landfill to zero and to the maximum in case of secondary waste.
- To identify the waste products with a low potential for recycling and to propose eco-innovative valorization and production solutions.
- To assess the transferability to the market of the new proposed eco-innovative solutions.

Table 1. Expected results of Waste4Think.

	<p>R1 - Operation & Management Module</p> <p>R2 – Collection Module</p> <p>R3 – Planning Module</p> <p>R4 – Circular Economy Module</p>
	<p>R5 - Food App: Promotion of food waste prevention</p> <p>R6 - Local Trade App: Promotion of local trade, eco- tourism and cooperative actions</p> <p>R7 - Citizen App: Promotion of transparency and citizen empowerment, communication with waste managers.</p>
	<p>R8 – Innovative Teaching Units: Educational materials about waste management.</p> <p>R9 – Sorting Game: Game that teaches on the importance of waste sorting</p> <p>R10 - Eco-design Game: Introduction to the eco-design.</p> <p>R11 – Planning Game: Game to raise awareness and to train on the integral waste management system.</p> <p>R12 – Virtual City Game: Game that provides training on the Circular Economy principles</p> <p>R13 – Eco-Design solutions: Co-creation of eco-products and services.</p> <p>R14 – Planning solutions for the co-creation of integral waste management</p>

	<p>strategies.</p> <p>R15 – Circular Economy solutions for the co-creation of Circular Economy strategies</p>
	<p>R16– Economic instruments: Legislation about PAYT and incentive schemes.</p> <p>R17 – Innovative awareness actions: web tools and awareness campaigns.</p> <p>R18 – Best Practices Book</p>
	<p>R19 – Pre-dried and shredded bio-waste (FORBI): Valorisation of kitchen/food waste in a circular economy concept</p> <p>R20 - Bio-fuel: Valorisation ant treatment of nappies for bio-fuel production.</p>

The benefits of these solutions will be enhanced by their integration using ICT tools built over the components of the FIWARE community which will enable to cross-check information from the technological features and from the social response of citizens in order to extract knowledge of the management systems. This will allow us to monitor the efficiency of the system and to apply necessary improvements (such as ad-hoc prevention campaigns or changes in the infrastructures). The eco-solutions will be demonstrated in 4 complementary urban areas in Europe. The most relevant expected impacts are: a 20% increase in waste sorting, 10% saving of management costs, and 10% reduction of GHG emissions. Figure 1 summarizes the main characteristics of each pilot site and their particular challenges in Waste4Think.

<p>Halandri (Greece, 70.000 inhab)</p> <p>Suburban city of Athens Basic waste collection system: 2 bins (recyclables and rest)</p> <p>Urban waste sorted: 11% Goal: Increase sorted waste >30% by defining advacned waste collection system and exploitation of biowaste</p>	<p>Seveso (Italy, 22.000 inhab)</p> <p>Door to door waste collection system. User identification system by tags in waste bags</p> <p>Urban waste sorted: 70% Goal: increase sorted waste by the implemetation of economic instruments and social actions, sustainable events</p>
<p>Zamudio (Spain, 3.200 inhab)</p> <p>Collection system by waste bins for: paper and cardboard, biowaste, lighweigth packaging, glass, bulky waste, batteries, reusable items, cooking oil</p> <p>Urban waste sorted: 18% Goal: Increase sorted waste > 30% by economic instruments and social actions</p>	<p>Cascais (Portugal, 206.479 inhab)</p> <p>Separate collection system by collection bins for:rest, recyclables, gardening and bulky. Advanced waste collection software.</p> <p>Urban waste sorted: 30% Goal: optimization of the waste collection to reduce environmental impacts due to collection works</p>

Figure 1. Waste4Think pilots sites.

This document gathers all the cross-cutting aspects of the Project that should be taken into consideration for the subsequent developments. In particular, it will include a comprehensive legislation framework analysis in each pilot site, the definition of the scope of the project identifying the user groups and all involved stakeholders, specifying the use cases and the functional and non-functional requirements of all the eco-solution as well as the definition of the technical specification of the envisaged technical solutions. Figure 2. depicts the content of this deliverable.

Figure 2. Content of the Deliverable 1.1

Each section will have a brief description of the objective, the methodology used and the main results. When necessary an appendix will be used to include all the supplementary or confidential information.

This deliverable is complemented with the following deliverables, describing the overall framework of project:

D1.3 Sustainability assessment models with detailed information about the waste management systems of the pilot sites, their baseline status and the definition of the set of ESTE KPIs (Environment-Social-Technological-Economical Key Performance Indicators) to monitor the impact of the project.

D.4.1 Implementation of R17: non ICT Innovative Social Actions and *D.4.2 Implementation of R17: ICT based Innovative Social Actions* with the detailed environmental programmes of the pilot sites and their scheduling.

Deliverables from D1.4 Preparatory Actions Report to D1.7 Full Test report with all the results achieved for each Milestone of the project.

Finally all the public data of the project can be consulted in Waste4Think Zenodo Community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/waste4think/?page=1&size=20>).

2. Legislative framework

Section 2 includes an assessment of the legal framework that affects and influences the activities that will be developed during the project implementation.

The first level analysed is the EU legislation that provides the basis and frame for the state members' policies and laws. For each pilot and country has been identified all the laws and reference documents in the following three levels: National, Regional and Local. Additionally, a final section about innovative legal documents from other countries has been included. The scheme of the legal framework assessment is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Legislative framework for the Waste4Think project

As the EU legal Framework is very wide and includes several types of legal acts, here below Figure 4 summarises the main consequences and obligations derived from the different EU regulations.

Regulations	•A "regulation" is a binding legislative act. It must be applied in its entirety across the EU.
Directives	•A "directive" is a legislative act that sets out a goal that all EU countries must achieve. However, it is up to the individual countries to devise their own laws on how to reach these goals.
Decisions	•A "decision" is binding on those to whom it is addressed (e.g. an EU country or an individual company) and is directly applicable.
Recommendations	•A "recommendation" is not binding. A recommendation allows the institutions to make their views known and to suggest a line of action without imposing any legal obligation on those to whom it is addressed.
Opinions	•An "opinion" is an instrument that allows the institutions to make a statement in a non-binding fashion, in other words without imposing any legal obligation on those to whom it is addressed. While laws are being made, the committees give opinions from their specific regional or economic and social viewpoint.

Figure 4. Types of EU legal acts

2.1 Methodology

For each one of the identified and selected laws and reference documents related to the following main topics that are treated within the project:

- Waste general legislation/programmes
- Municipal waste management and treatment
- Prevention and reutilisation
- Food waste management and treatment (compost)
- Food wastage (food production and safety)
- Packaging
- Taxes and PAYT
- Collection systems and ICT
- Green Procurement

It has been created a form that includes the following details and description of the main contents of the rule:

1. **Name of the law:** official title of the law or reference document.
2. **Type of waste regulated:** identification of the specific waste flows regulated and considered in the document.
3. **Quantitative objectives:** specific quantitative objectives set by the document that establish the numeric goals to be achieved and the available time frame.

4. **Other strategies included:** description of other strategies and measures introduced by the document that are relevant for the topics and activities of the project, specially focusing on the issues mentioned above such as food waste, food wastage, taxes and PAYT, prevention, etc.
5. **Management competences:** identification of the distribution and attribution of prevention and management competencies in order to deploy and follow the measures and the objectives to be reached.
6. **Link to the document:** online address where all the contents of the document are accessible to be reviewed.

2.1. Results

In Table 2. to Table 6. the summary of the main laws and complementary reference documents analysed for each one of the levels considered are presented. In the Appendix A, all the forms with the details and description of the main contents of the laws and other documents are included. Each one of the rules studied is identified with a code that relates it with the corresponding level/country of application as well as with the corresponding form exposed in the Annex A.

Table 2. European Union legislative framework

European Union	
Group	Name of the law
General	<p>EU.G.1. COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS Closing the loop - An EU action plan for the Circular Economy</p> <p>EU.G.2. Proposal for a DIRECTIVE OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL amending Directive 2008/98/EC on waste /DRAFT REPORT on the proposal for a directive of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Directive 2008/98/EC on waste (COM(2015)0595 – C8-0382/2015 – 2015/0275(COD))</p> <p>EU.G.3. Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 November 2008 on waste</p>
Treatment	<p>EU.T.1. Directive 1999/31/EC of European Council of 26 April 1999 on the landfill of waste</p> <p>EU.T.2. Directive 2000/76/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 December 2000 on the incineration of waste</p>
Fractions	<p>EU.F.1. Directive 94/62/EC of European Parliament and Council of 20 December 1994 on packaging and packaging waste</p> <p>EU.F.2. Directive (EU) 2015/720 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2015 amending Directive 94/62/EC as regards reducing the consumption of lightweight plastic carrier bags</p>

Other	<p><u>COMPOST APPLICATION</u></p> <p>EU.O.1. End-of-waste criteria for biodegradable waste subjected to biological treatment (compost & digestate): Technical proposals</p> <p><u>FOOD WASTAGE</u></p> <p>EU.O.2. European Parliament resolution of 19 January 2012 on how to avoid food wastage: strategies for a more efficient food chain in the EU (2011/2175(INI))</p> <p><u>FOOD SAFETY/FOOD SUPPLY</u></p> <p>EU.O.3. Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 January 2002 laying down the general principles and requirements of food law, establishing the European Food Safety Authority and laying down procedures in matters of food safety</p> <p>EU.O.4. Regulation (EC) N° 852/2004 of the European Parliament and the Council of 29 April 2004 on the hygiene of foodstuffs</p> <p>EU.O.5. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, The European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions “A better functioning food supply chain in Europe”</p> <p>GREEN PUBLIC PROCUREMENT</p> <p>EU.O.6. Directive 2014/24/EU of the European Parliament and the Council of February 2014 on public procurement</p> <p>EU.O.7 Directive 2014/24/EU of the European Parliament and the Council of 26 February 2014 on procurement by institutions operating in the water, energy, transport and postal services</p>
COMPLEMENTARY ISSUES	<p>EU.C.1. Directive 2003/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 November 2003 on the re-use of public sector information</p> <p>EU.C.2. DIRECTIVE 2013/37/EU OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 26 June 2013 amending Directive 2003/98/EC on the re-use of public sector information</p> <p>EU.C.3. Directive (EU) 2016/680 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Council Framework Decision 2008/977/JHA</p>

Table 3. Zamudio's pilot legislative framework

Zamudio Pilot-SPAIN	
Group	Name of the law
National	<p><u>General</u></p> <p>ES.N.1. Framework State Plan on waste management(PEMAR) 2016-2022</p> <p>ES.N.2. Law 22/2011, of 28 July 2011, on waste and contaminated soils</p> <p><u>Treatment</u></p> <p>ES.N.3. Royal Decree 1481/2001, of 27 December 2001, on waste elimination via landfilling. Last update, published on 23/04/2013</p> <p><u>Fractions</u></p> <p>ES.N.4. Law 11/1997, of 24 April 1997, on Packaging and Packaging waste. Royal Decree 252/2006, of 3 March 2006, on the revision of the recycling and valorisation objectives established by the Law 11/1997.</p>
Regional	<p>ES.R.1. Comprehensive plan for urban waste management in Bizkaia 2005-2016</p> <p>ES.R.2 Plan for the prevention and management of waste in the Basque Autonomous Community</p>
Local	<p>ES.L.1. Ordinance regulating the management of urban solid waste</p> <p>ES.L.2. Ordinance regulating the management of waste in industrial estates, business and technology parks</p> <p>ES.L.3. Fiscal Ordinance. Rate for provision of waste collection service.</p>
Other	<p><u>TAXS</u></p> <p>ES.O.1. Royal Legislative Decree 2/2004 of 5 March, approving the revised text of the Law Regulating Local Tax Authorities. Law 8/1989 of 13 April on Public taxes and Prices (LTPP). Law 58/2003 of 17 December on General Tax (LGT)</p> <p><u>FOOD WASTAGE</u></p> <p>ES.O.2. Spanish Strategy "More Food Less Waste". Program to reduce food loss and waste and maximise the value of discarded food. Regulation on the Use of the Spanish Strategy "More Food Less Waste" logo</p> <p><u>GREEN PUBLIC PROCUREMENT</u></p> <p>ES.O.3. Order Pre/116/2008 the Agreement of the Council is published, approving the Green Public Procurement Plan of the General State Administration, its Government Agencies and the Managing Body of Social Security.</p> <p>ES.O.4. Enviromental Framework Program 2020</p>

COMPLEMENTARY ISSUES	<p>ES.C.1. Organic Law 15/1999, of December 13h, on the Protection of Personal Data</p> <p>ES.C.2. Law 19/2013, of December 9h, on Transparency, Access to Public Information and Good Governance</p>

Table 4. Cascais's pilot singular legislative framework

Cascais Pilot-PORTUGAL	
Group	Name of the law
National	<p>P.N.1. Law Decree nº 178/2006 of September 5th – Approves the general regime for waste management by internal juridical order for the Directive nº 2006/12/CE of the European Parliament and Council of April 5th and the Directive nº 91/689/CEE of December 12th of the EU Council</p> <p>P.N.2. Law Decree nº 194/2009 of August 20th – Establishes the juridical regime of municipal services for water, sewage water and waste services</p>
Regional	-
Local	P.L.1. Urban Waste Service Regulation
Other	--

Table 5. Seveso's pilot singular legislative framework

Seveso Pilot-ITALY	
Group	Name of the law
National	IT.N.1. Testo unico ambientale (Environmental Framework regulation) – D.Lgs. 152/2006 and subsequent modifications
Regional	IT.R.1. Programma Regionale di Gestione dei Rifiuti (PRGR, Regional Waste Management Plan) 2014-2020
Local	IT.L.1. Regolamento di igiene urbana (Municipal Waste Management Regulation). Regolamento TARES (waste tax regulation)
Other	<p>IT.O.1. Food wastage</p> <p>IT.O.2. PAYT/Taxs</p> <p>IT.O.3. Plastic bags</p> <p>IT.O.4. ITC</p>

Table 6. Halandri's pilot singular legislative framework

Halandri Pilot-GREECE	
Group	Name of the law
National	GR.N.1. National Waste Management Plan – NWMP (2015). Law No4042/2012 (harmonization with EC directives 2008/99, 2008/98)
Regional	GR.R.1. Solid Waste Management Plan for the Attica Region (The Plan has been voted in 2006, the current version is the Second Revision which has been active since August 2015)
Local	GR.L.1. Local Waste Management Plan, Municipality of Chalandri (2015)
Other	-

2.2. Conclusions

The Project W4T has its main reference on the new EU waste rules (Circular Economy package [presented](#) in December 2015 and approved in May 2018) that have the objectives to prevent waste and, where this is not possible, significantly step up recycling of municipal and packaging waste. According to the new legislation W4T tries to strengthen the "waste hierarchy", taken specific measures to prioritize prevention, re-use and recycling (finding the achieving of the recycling targets for 2025, 2030, 2035) above landfilling (objective to reduce the amount of waste sent to landfill) and incineration, thus making the circular economy a reality. Additionally, as it is requested by the EU rules, the project promotes the use of effective economic instruments, such as PAYT schemes in some of the pilots (that nowadays are not specifically regulated in the pilot countries except for Italy, so here there is an interesting legal framework to be developed by the Member States) and more clear and automatic methods to measure and track the management data and results. Finally, the Project W4T is placing a particular focus on waste prevention and introduces measures for food waste reduction in line with the EU new strategies.

3. Scope of the Project

Section 3 includes an assessment of the scope of the project. The definition of the scope of the projects involves identifying the target groups, specify the use cases while concurrently defining the functional and non-functional requirements. Subsequently the definition of the technical specifications and the reference architecture are listed.

3.1. Target Groups

A crucial step in the analysis of the user requirements is to clearly define the different groups of users to which Waste4Think would like to take into account, as they are the primary stakeholders interested in the eco-solutions developed.

3.1.1 Methodology

The role of the target groups could be defined according to two point of view: social and technical. It is important to highlight the singularities of each target group as not to forget their necessities. Two different working group were organized involving experts in the field. Two were the questions made:

- What is the role of the target group?
- Has any relation with other target groups?

Figure 5 shows the main results from the social working group on target groups (Months 6 Progress Meeting, Cascais, Dec 2017). In Table 7. and Table 8. the results from social and technical focus groups are presented. It is shown that for social working groups it was important to highlight the slight differences inside the same target group such as the level of awareness or the kind of waste produced. Conversely, the technical working groups highlight just the specifications in face of the system making more general groups.

Figure 5. Main result of the social working group

The results of both focus groups were again assessed in a smaller group to arrange an agreement about the final list of the target groups.

Table 7. Results from the social discussion

Social discussion
General citizen
Primary Students
Secondary Students
University Students
Vocational Students
Researchers
High aware Associations
Low aware Associations
SME
Educational centres employees and managers
Tourist

Immigrants
Domestic generator
Commercial generator
Industrial generator
Cooked food waste generators (restaurants, catering,...)
Up to expired food waste generators (supermarkets)
Nappies generators (old age homes, nurseries)
Potential parents (0-3 years)
Nursery employees and managers
Cleaning services at public administration
Waste collectors
Truck drivers
Waste Collection Companies
Technician
Food waste recyclers
Food waste reusers (social kitchen)
Association in general
Policy makers
Waste management technicians

Table 8. Results from the technical discussion

Technical discussion
Citizen
Students
Researchers
Associations
SME
Educational centres
Non-residential generators
Domestic generator
Commercial generator

Industrial generator
Food Waste Generator
Nappies Generator
Waste Collection Operators
Waste collection company
Treatment Plants Operators
Food Waste Manager
Zero waste ecosystem
Waste Manager Public Bodies

3.1.2 Results

In this section, the final agreement with the description of each of the target groups will be given. In Table 9. the agreement on the target groups is presented. Figure 66 depicts the high-level target groups identified in the Waste4Think project. In Table 10. the description of each target group can be seen.

Table 9. High and low level target groups

High level target group	Low level target group
Citizen	Age Gender Level of awareness Social group
Students	Primary Secondary University Vocational students
Researchers	
Associations	Level of awareness
SME	
Education centres	
Non-residential generators	Tourist Immigrants
Domestic generator	

Commercial generator	
Industrial generator	
Food Waste Generator	Cooked food waste generators Up to expired food waste generators
Nappies Generator	Old age homes Nurseries Potential parents
Waste Collection Operators	Cleaning services at public administration Waste Collectors Truck drivers
Waste collection company	
Technician	
Food Waste Manager	Food waste recyclers Food waste reusers
Zero waste ecosystem	
Waste Manager Public Bodies	Policy Makers Waste Management technicians

Figure 6. High-level Target groups diagram

Table 10. Target group description

	Target group	Acronym	Description
Generator	Domestic generator	DG	The domestic generator are all those groups of residential and non-residential household waste generators that generate waste due to their daily consume and living habits and to their level of awareness inside their home. Household waste are: biowaste, paper and cardboard (packaging and non-packaging), wood, plastics (packaging and non-packaging), glass (packaging and non-packaging), metals (packaging and non-packaging), textiles, household hazardous waste, complex products, inert waste fines, and miscellaneous.
	Commercial generator	CG	The commercial generators are the economic activities inside the municipality that generate household waste inside their economy activity
	Industrial generator	IG	The industrial generators are those economic activities that indirectly generate waste similar to household apart from their direct waste generation
	Nappies generator	NG	The nappies generators are all those groups of residential or non-residential waste generators characterized by a daily use of nappies. Nappies are used mainly by babies not yet toilet-trained or by ill people (mainly elderly but also younger people). The nappies generators addressed by the actions of W4T are: families with newborns and nurseries in Seveso, and hospices in Zamudio and Seveso.

			In the case of families, the main target of the sensitization actions of W4T will be the parents. About the nursery and the hospice, the actions must be aimed to employees but also to the managers in order to foster a strong commitment at the management level.
	Food waste generator	FWG	Expired food generators may be Supermarkets or local shops that sell food products (vegetables etc) and have in a weekly or monthly basis expired products that would end up in the municipal bins.
	Non-residential generator	NRG	Non-registered as resident people has to be also taken into account. People renting a house, an apartment, a room (or internal domestic work staff may be some examples. Despite having a similar waste production as other residents (domestic) they are in a completely different group of users as they are unable to get the information on waste production and, most of the times, they do not pay the water bill where waste cost is explained (as in the case of Cascais and Zamudio). There is a need to develop a specific communication campaign to both landlords and tourists to ensure the understanding of the project's goals and bin access. In the specific case of Cascais, the pilot area is located near one of the most popular beaches in Lisbon region and, as it has a striving tourism economy, there is a strong demand on accommodation. As the target area is residential, mostly apartments, it is common to have a short term renting offer dedicated to tourists the usually come during summer time.
Operator	Waste collection operator	WCO	The waste collection process is comprised of a bunch of daily tasks that include personnel from both the waste collection companies and the public administration. On the one hand, truck drivers and operators will fulfill the service thanks to hardware and the tools they are provided with on the trucks. On the other hand, the service performance can be checked and improved (if needed) from the administration departments on both public and private (waste company) sides. Such improvements, together with the environmental harm decrease, can be carried on by means of hardware and software tools.
	Treatment plant operator	TPO	A technician is someone who is a nursery employee with technical skills or an employee of a technical company (such as Greentech) and is responsible for the appropriate operation of the Waste Treatment Unit (WTU). He has the responsibility to check if the equipment works properly, check and update the recording files of the WTU and inform the head of the

			nursery in any case. In addition, he has to empty the bag filters of the WTU, load and empty the composter frequently to ensure its proper operation.
Manager	Food waste manager	FWM	Food waste manager is a person responsible in the management of certain kind of food waste such as food waste recyclers or NGOs collaborating with the municipality
	Waste collection company	WCC	Waste management includes all the activities and actions required to manage waste from its generation to its final treatment (collection, transportation, disposal or recycling and monitoring). The waste (gaseous, liquid, solid, etc.) is managed to avoid its adverse effect over human health and environment and, most of the time, to get resources from it. The management of municipal waste is general responsibility of the local government that typically entrust to a company all the waste management activities. This company in some cases deals with many more issues such as PAYT invoicing, waste and fleet monitoring including its optimization; hence will be a target group involved in the actions and the decision processes of W4T.
	Waste manager public body	WMPB	The Waste Managers, typically part of Public Bodies, are responsible for waste management at the local, regional or national level. Strategies and decisions about how to manage waste are taken by policy makers both at the municipal and the regional/national level, by means of political or administrative guidelines or regulations. These decisions are also based on advices of waste management technicians such as external consultants etc., that are aware and expert on all the technical issues regarding the waste management. The policy makers can be different among EU countries, basically according to the national regulation and the transposition of EU Directives.
Social groups of interest	Citizen	C	Citizen is a person who is entitled to enjoy all the political, civil and social rights and privileges granted by a state to the people comprising its constituency, and is obligated to obey its laws and to fulfil his or duties as called upon. A citizen is characterized by age and gender. From a social point of view, in order to finalize sensitization and awareness actions, a citizen could be also characterized by his/her level of awareness with regard to a specific argument and his/her membership in a social group.
	Educational centre	EC	Refers to the physical space where people gather or congregate for education, receives, assimilates and learned knowledge and to acquire, in addition, cultural

			and behavioural sensitization by previous generations. It is usually differentiated by age groups in compulsory education or by specific thematic.
	Students	S	Student is a person who learns, usually someone who attends an educational institution. The Student could be enrolled or attends classes at a school, college or university. We usually refer to formal education.
	SME	SME	Small and medium sized enterprise
	Researcher	R	Researcher is a person interesting in the data recorded by all It and non-IT tools in order to make assessments and go beyond the reason of the behaviour of the systems and the usability of the actions deployed.
	Zero Waste Ecosystem	ZWE	W4T depicts some Zero Waste Ecosystems where some technical and social actions will be implemented. In these Ecosystems, we identified as target groups all that associations or organizations committed to reduce the amount of waste aiming at the zero waste. Generally speaking, in this category a wide range of targets and environments could be included such as schools and their related associations, events-organizers (e.g. Eco-events), environmental or social associations but also, in some cases, private companies, the Town Hall and its internal waste organization etc.
	Association	A	Associations are groups of people, either of general citizens or specific activities, interested in collaborate in the action deployed in the municipalities.

In Annex B1 a detailed list of the different target groups involved in each pilot site has been included. The specific actions and the way of interaction with each target group will be described in the corresponding deliverable (D4.1 and D4.2 regarding the Social Action Plan and D7.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan and their corresponding reports D1.4, D1.5, D1.6, D1.7 and D7.2).

3.2. User Requirement analysis and use case definition

The purpose of this section is to perform the requirement elicitation, which comprises a set of activities concerned with the identification and communication of the purpose of the system. These processes are part of the Requirement Engineering procedure. Requirements Engineering (RE) is a set of activities concerned with identifying and communicating the purpose of a system, and the contexts in which it will be used, among different stakeholders. RE refers to the process of defining, documenting and maintaining requirements of a system. Hence, it is necessary to construct a bridge between user or real world requirements and the capabilities and opportunities afforded by technologies (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Relation between requirements and use cases

This section begins by outlining the requirement specification methodology used. The goal of this method is to suggest a formal framework to describe the system requirement. Subsequently, the functional and non-functional requirements are listed. The detailed information is reported in confidential appendixes. Due to the early stage of the project these requirements and the corresponding use cases may suffer from changes that will be updated in the corresponding appendixes.

3.2.1 Requirement analysis

Requirements analysis encompasses those tasks related to determining the needs or conditions to meet for a new or altered product or project, considering the possibly conflicting requirements of the various stakeholders, analysing, documenting, validating and managing software/system requirements. The aim of the requirement analysis is to facilitate the design of the system architecture and the development of the envisaged system.

The Waste4Think requirement analysis mostly relies on **Volere methodology**. The Volere methodology comprises a general template for presenting the layout and structure of the requirements specification document, as a result of the requirements elicitation and analysis processes. The first edition of the Volere Requirements Specification Template was released in 1995. Since then, several updates have been released that resulted in refinements of the previous ones, based on feedback from an affiliated network of organisations from all over the world that have used the Volere template to discover, organise, and communicate their requirements. The subsequent updates reflect more specific needs

imposed by those organisations. The template is distributed under a commercial license and it is copyrighted by The Atlantic Systems Guild Limited. Some older versions are available on the Web.

According to the Volere template of Requirements Specification, the following types of requirements are supported:

- *Functional requirements* which describe which are the functions of the product.
- *Non-functional requirements* which describe the properties that the functions must have, such as performance and usability.

In addition to the requirements types, Volere introduces the following constraints:

- *Project constraints*, which are restrictions on the product e.g. due to the budget or the time available to build the product.
- *Design constraints* impose restrictions on how the product must be designed.

The Volere template also refers to:

- *Project drivers* (in the beginning), which reflect the business-related forces. For example, the purpose of the project is a project driver, as are all of the stakeholders each for different reasons.
- *Project issues* (at the end) including the conditions under which the project will be done. The purpose of this section is to present a coherent picture of all factors that contribute to the success or failure of the project and to illustrate how managers can use requirements as input when managing a project.

Waste4Think has made use of the template purpose by the eCOMPASS project. Not all elements of the Volere template were considered to be suitable for Waste4Think project. Therefore, a number of Sections from the Volere template about the description of functional and non-functional specifications were chosen. Table 11. sums up the section used to describe the functional and non-functional requirements.

Table 11. Requirement gathering template

ID	A unique identifier
Name	<i>Title of the requirement.</i>
Requirement type	<i>Whether it is a functional or non-functional requirement and in case of non-functional requirements the specific type of requirement according to the Volere notation.</i>
Description	<i>A requirement must say exactly what is required.</i>
Rationale	<i>A justification of the requirement</i>
Fit criterion (measurable)	<i>By measurable we mean is it possible, once the system has been constructed, to verify that this requirement has been met. In other words, this means the tests which must be performed in order to satisfy the requirement.</i>
Customer satisfaction	<i>Degree of stakeholder happiness if this requirement is successfully implemented (Scale from 1=uninterested to 5=extremely pleased).</i>
Customer dissatisfaction	<i>Degree of stakeholder unhappiness if this requirement is not</i>

	<i>implemented (Scale from 1=hardly matters to 5=extremely displeased).</i>
Priority	<i>The requirement is ranked according to the customer value. (Scale from 1=low priority to 5=highest priority).</i>
Conflicts	<i>Any requirements whose implementation is blocked by this one.</i>
Constraints (attainable)	<i>An attainable requirement will usually answer the question: How can the requirement be accomplished? Hence, here we provide any constraints / conditions for the requirement to be executed.</i>
Difficulty	<i>Level of difficulty for requirement implementation (estimation). (Scale from 1=low difficulty to 5=extreme difficulty).</i>
Actors	<i>An actor is someone or something outside the system that interacts with it or with one of its components (primary actor). If the actor is interacted by the system or one of its components is a secondary actor.</i>
Author	<i>The owner of each requirement that was recorded.</i>
Version and date	<i>This field shows the version and date that the requirement was created.</i>

3.2.2 Use case analysis

Use Case Analysis aims at organizing how external entities interact with the system, emphasizing on gathering the functional requirements of a system. Use cases are an effective technique for capturing, organizing and communicating the functional requirements of a system. A use case typically represents a subset of functionalities of the system towards the achievement of a specific goal, with the key characteristic that these are considered from the user's point of view.

A use case lists a number of possible sequences of interactions between the system and external actors to accomplish a goal, describing a flow of events where the system fulfils one or more user's requirements. An actor represents an external role that interacts with the system (not necessarily a person, it can be any element outside the system, such as an organization, device or even a software package). A primary actor makes use of the system to achieve a specific goal, while a secondary actor provides assistance to the system in order to achieve the primary actor's goal. Table 12. sums up the description of the use cases.

Table 12. Template for the Use Case definition

Use Case ID	<unique identifier in the form UCx.y>
Use Case Name	<brief title that expresses the goal of this Use Case>
Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Purpose and goal: <intention of the Use Case> • Scenario of use: <detailed statement describing the context, user's profile, why he/she uses the platform, interaction with the system, interaction with actors involved, benefits obtained, etc.>
Primary target group	<the target group who will be initiating this Use Case>
Secondary target group	<other target group who interact with the system/participate in completing the Use Case>
Priority level	<available options: <i>Essential, Secondary, Supportive</i> >

Reason assigning priority for this	<importance of classifying this Use Case into the specific priority level>
Preconditions	<description of the conditions (if any) that must be fulfilled before the Use Case can be executed>
Trigger	<events that trigger the actions to be executed>
Main flow	<detailed description of the user actions and system responses (in the form of step-by-step action/event list) that will take place during execution of the Use Case under normal, expected conditions> Example: 1. The user sends a request for... ... n. The system displays a set of ...
System output	<detailed system's functionality as a response to the user's actions>
Alternative flow	<situations that can prevent proper execution of the Use Case, referring to the corresponding step number, the condition that must hold true and the alternative actions to be taken> Example: k.a. The system cannot identify the user. k.a.1. The system displays an error message. k.a.2. The flow continues with step m.
Services involved	<Waste4Think services involved in the implementation of this Use Case>
Devices	<on which device this Use Case will operate properly>
Critical success parameters	<identification of key factors for successful execution of the Use Case>
Constraints	<all constraints to be taken into account, e.g. environmental>
Relevant functional requirements	<IDs of the functional requirements that are used to derive this Use Case>
Legal issues	<comments about Law reference involve in this Use Case (if applicable)>
Ethical issues	< comments about ethical issues involve in this Use Case (if applicable)>
Notes and issues	<additional comments about this Use Case or remaining open issues that must be resolved (if applicable)>
Author	<name of the author of this Use Case>
Version	<Use Case version>
Date	<date of last change>
Pilot	<name of the pilot>

3.2.3 Results

The functional and non-functional requirements have been defined for each of the eco-solutions that will be developed in the Waste4Think project. The ID is made of two fields:

- Eco-solution number Rx, $x = \{1, 2, \dots, 20\}$
- Functional (or non-functional) requirement ID: [N]FRy where y is a multi-index of up to 5 level of depth.

In Annex B2 the requirement for the operation and planning IT tools for the mobile apps for citizens , for the educational materials and tools for citizen science, for the mechanisms to boost behavioural changes, and for the decentralised new treatments are presented. The colours just represent the level of concretion of the FR. Please note that in order to emphasize the non-functional requirements, they are highlighted in red.

Appendix B (confidential) shows the full list of the FR and NFR until the most detailed level (Level 5). Moreover the description of those of Level 2 is also included. Please note that Level 1 requirements are just the title to categorize them and the lower levels have been added to provide a more detailed description of the Level 2 ones.

In Annex C contains the list of Use Cases identified in Waste4Think. Each use case is identified by a letter and a number Xy, where X is the identifier of the pilot where the use case applied (A for all pilot sites, C for Cascais pilot, H for Halandri, S for Seveso and Z for Zamudio) and y is the identifier of the use case. Annex C (confidential) contains a full description of all the Use Cases identified.

Finally, Annex C summarizes the relation between the use cases, the target groups and requirements tested. To this end, this appendix shows for every functional requirement (in rows) what target group will use this functionality (in columns) and in the corresponding cell it can be found the use case that described the action. Please note that the pilot where it is going to be tested is also identified by the first letter of the use case code.

Table 13. List of the use cases identified for Waste4Think

	Use Case	Use case description
ALL	A1	Use of the long term planning module
	A2	Use of the Food app by the producers of food waste
	A3	Use of the food app by the reusers of food
	A4	Use by citizen of the local trade app
	A5	Provide information of local business
	A6	Use of the citizen APP to search for information
	A7	Provide information of the social actions
	A8	Use of innovative teaching units and results of learning analytics
	A9	Use of the serious games by citizens
	A10	Monitor participation in social actions
	A11	Provide information and knowledge to the target groups on the social action in order to change habits and behaviours
	A12	Creation of social campaigns to prevent the waste generation and to promote recycling among different sectors of the population
	A13	Use of the citizen APP to create an issue
	A14	Use of the Circular Economy planner
	A15	Consult the next bill
	A16	Use of the Green Procurement tool
CASCAIS	C1	Chamber System – Chamber generation in the website
	C2	Chamber System – White list generation in the website
	C3	Chamber System – User access and identification management
	C4	Filling Level Sensors
	C5	Waste Collection Module – Plan a collection tour model

	C6	Waste Collection Module – Plan a service tour
	C7	Waste Collection Module – Perform real tours (Tours finished by the trucks)
	C8	Waste Collection Module – Check the fulfilment of the tours
	C9	Data reporting
	C10	Invoicing Module – Generate Invoices
	C11	Monitoring waste collection
	C12	Monitoring driver behaviour for fuel saving, real time driver info
	C13	Data collection for bin management and complain management bin/property related information, Photo function with built in camera, GPS Trace and event data collection, Signature as job confirmation
HALANDRI	H1	Public awareness Campaign and selection of participating citizens in the Municipality of Halandri
	H2	Collection of food/kitchen waste
	H3	Collection of open-air market waste
	H4	Biomass product generation
	H5	Pellet production from biomass product
	H6	Gaseous biofuel and truck fuelling demonstration
	H7	Lab and small pilot scale experimentation for biomass product valorisation
	H8	Lab and small pilot scale experimentation for biofuel production
	H9	Lab and small pilot scale experimentation for bioethanol production
	H10	Lab and small pilot scale experimentation for electricity production
	H11	Lab and small pilot scale experimentation for activated carbon production
	H12	Lab and small pilot scale experimentation for animal feed production
	H13	Full-scale assessment of biomass product as alternative fuel for cement industry
	H14	Full-scale assessment of biomass product as an alternative resource for composting industry
	H15	Educational Programme
	H16	Consumer Programme
	H17	Separate collection of disposable nappies
	H18	Transportation of Expired Food Products to the Waste Treatment Unit
	H19	Separate storage of Expired Food Products (EFP)
	H20	Treatment of waste streams
	H21	Composting
SEVESO	S1	Delivery of the RFID bag to the domestic generator
	S2	RFID Bags collection with vehicles equipped with on board device
	S3	Delivery of the waste at the Municipal recycling centre
	S4	Anomalies in unsorted waste bag
	S5	Anomalies in recyclable waste fractions
	S6	Calculation of the duration by trip and collection vehicle
	S7	Estimation of the weight of the RFID iBags
	S8	Invoicing with unit pricing waste rate
	S9	Acquisition of the invoicing data (personal identification and waste)
	S10	Display statistics on the bags collected trips
	S11	Check the efficiency of the waste management service
	S12	Set up of an OPEN DATA on the waste production and services tariffing
ZA	Z1	Deposit waste (domestic)
	Z2	Deposit waste in clean point

Z3	Deposit waste (industrial)
Z4	Waste collection
Z5	Community composting plant
Z6	Participation in a Zero Waste Ecosystem
Z7	Participation in a Zero Waste Ecosystem: Zero waste Events
Z8	Use of the waste observatory web site / app
Z9	Consult the waste management monitoring system
Z10	Use of the fleet management tool
Z11	Use of the invoicing module

4. Technical requirements

This section introduces the methodology followed to specify the technical requirements. Given that the 20 eco-solutions have a completely different nature, it is impossible to use a template or similar approach. To overcome this problem the following methodology has been used:

- Provide a wide description of the pilot sites including:
 - ✓ a map of the pilot
 - ✓ collection system characteristics
 - ✓ collection points characteristics
 - ✓ collection trucks description
 - ✓ photos of all the previous items
- Provide a technical description of all the solutions (hardware and software) that are already running and in which the W4T eco-solutions should be integrated (such as the bin locks or the invoicing module). Provide information related to: providers, models, standard and protocols used by the devices.
- Any other relevant information about the pilots.

Annex D includes a description of the four pilots.

5. Overview of the architecture

5.1. CO CREATION ACTIVITY TO DEFINE THE PILOTS ARCHITECTURE

In this section a description of the methodology used to define the overall architecture is provided. As every pilot has their own particularities, it is not possible to define an overall architecture, so 4 architectures have been defined (Figures 7-10). A card sorting session was held at Cascais meeting to discuss this topic. Card sorting is a technique defined in user experience field to build dendrograms but that have also been adapted to define user interfaces. In this session we have adapted the methodology to develop architectures.

A card sorting session has the following steps:

1. **Define the objective of the session:** It is important that the objective of the session is clear. This is needed to both the researchers and the users. While the researchers would need to select the cards that are most appropriated to the task at hand, the users should be able to clearly understand the objective without provide much textual information.
2. **Select the cards:** The image used in every card of the deck should be easy to understand as it could lead to problems in the interpretation of the results.
3. **Perform the activity:** The actions should typically consist on providing to a set of subjects a deck of cards that should be “sorted” in some way. Typically making clusters of concepts that are near.
4. **Analysis:** Record the results and perform a qualitative analysis of the results.

In this particular case, the actions carried on have been the following:

1. **Define the objective of the session:** in this case, the objective is to “sort” a deck of cards to build a diagram of the architecture.

2. **Select the cards:** two decks of cards have been built. While one deck (Deck S) will have a list of sensors and transmission protocols the other one (Deck C) will contain a list of components of waste management systems. Annex E has the list of cards that have been used.
3. **Perform the activity:** four groups have been made, one for every pilot. The first task of every group is to sort Deck C accordingly to the path that the waste follows in the waste collection system used in the pilots. When more than one path could be follow, the cards should be put in parallel. Please note that we have considered that waste in several points of the path is transformed also in “information” that also follows some path that have to be modelled. After this task is made, the subject should use Deck S to select the places where the sensors will be and how this information is going to be transmitted. There is an important card in Deck C: the FIWARE card. The subjects should put that card in the place where the information is going to reach the software platform to be shared. Finally, the subjects could add any comment with posits (including new cards to the decks if they thing they are necessary).
4. **Analysis:** photos of the different architectures have been taken. As expected, the four pilots have built a completely different architecture for them. Only the architecture of Zamudio and Halandri are similar, as in both cases they have the less amount of technology already deployed so they have less constrictions. In the case of Seveso and Cascais, they have to fit the solutions that they have already deployed, and this make the architecture quite different.

All the architectures can be seen in Figure 8 (Cascais), Figure 9 (Halandri), Figure 10 (Seveso) and Figure 11 (Zamudio), respectively.

Figure 8. Architecture made for Cascais

Figure 9. Architecture made for Halandri

Figure 10. Architecture made for Seveso

Figure 11. Architecture made for Zamudio

5.2. PILOTS ARCHITECTURE results

From a generic point of view, an Internet of Thing (IoT) architecture is composed of the following four layers:

1. **Sensor / perception layer.** This layer is composed of the series of sensors that collect data from either an object under measurement in the environment or from the environment itself, and turn it into useful data.
2. **Transport layer.** The transport layer transfers the sensor data from the perception layer to the processing layer and vice versa through networks such as wireless, 3G, LAN, Bluetooth, RFID, and NFC. Ideally, each observed object would have an intelligent sensor attached, capable of retrieving the necessary data and then connecting over the Internet to send it to the middleware.
3. **Middleware / processing layer.** The processing layer is also known as the middleware layer. It stores, analyses, and processes huge amounts of data that come from both the transport layer and the business/services layer.
4. **Business/services layer.** This layer is responsible for delivering application specific services to the user. It defines various applications in which the IoT can be deployed.

Figure 12 shows the translation of this generic architecture to the components we have identified in Waste4Think, where:

1. **Sensor Layer (green).** This layer concentrates all the sensors/devices that act as input to define the waste management system. In particular:
 - *Sensors deployed at the bins and clean points:* Waste4Think will deploy identification tags, electronic locks and filling levels sensors in different containers, but there are other sensors available in the market, such as those to measure temperature, humidity, and position of the bins. Additionally, the Waste4Think clean points will have the same sensors as the bins, but in other cases, weighing systems may also be deployed.
 - *Sensors deployed at the truck:* several sensors are traditionally installed in the trucks, such as the bin identification system, the weighing sensor and the GPS system. Moreover, Waste4Think will also deploy a system to retrieve the information from the electronic locks and from a high speed camera to estimate the amount of improper waste in the bins.
 - *Sensors deployed at the treatment plants:* Waste4Think will monitor different treatment plants. On the one hand, composting plants will have temperature and humidity sensors while, on the other hand, the Biowaste Treatment Unit and the Waste Treatment Unit will monitor the amount of the input material, the amount and quality of the different outputs and different control parameters of the treatment plant.
 - *Other sources of information:* These sources comprise a series of different input mechanisms such as surveys, focus groups, APPs, the serious games and learning materials (Learning Analytics) and other monitoring actions that feed information to the system.

More information about these sensors will be covered in detail in the Deliverable 2.1 “Technical Documentation of R1: Operation Module”.

2. **Transport Layer (red).** In nearly all the cases, the sensors will use a wireless transport layer, in some cases the connection with upper layers will be direct, and in other cases there will be

a device acting as a gateway. Nevertheless, in the case of the surveys and other monitoring actions, the transport layer will be wired based.

3. **Middleware (blue).** The selected middleware revolves around the use of the components of the FIWARE ecosystem. These layers will be thoroughly detailed in Deliverable D2.1.
4. **Business/services layer (purple).** The middleware layer will feed the data to several applications (verticals) built upon it. These applications can be grouped into several categories:
 - *Persistence.* This category will group all the services responsible for storing the information for long term archiving (it will be covered in detail in Deliverable 2.1). We can identify two components of this module:
 - Databases that are responsible for storing the relevant information fed from the sensor layer for internal reuse.
 - Open Data module that filters and consolidates the information to publish to the relevant repositories for external reuse.
 - *Operation and management services.* This category gathers all services in charge of the management of the waste collection system under six main groups.
 - Dashboard that graphically represents the information from the sensor layer as well as what is typically called Business Intelligence (alerts, forecasting, knowledge extraction, etc.). This service will be covered in detail in Deliverable D2.1.
 - Collection Management that will help in the management of the daily collection routes. This service will be covered in detail in Deliverable D2.5.
 - Long Term Planning that will perform long term simulations to help plan investments, the waste collection system and eco-events. This service will be covered in detail in Deliverables D2.7 and D2.9.
 - Zero Waste ecosystems / events that will allow the planification and monitorization of the events and ecosystems. This service will be covered in detail in Deliverable D1.3 and Deliverable D2.1
 - Invoice Module that analyses the information stored in the persistence layer and produces invoices accordingly to the PAYT rules. This service will be covered in detail in Deliverable D5.1.
 - Public Observatory that will allow the citizens and entrepreneurs to access and exploit open data information. This service will be covered in detail in Deliverable D2.1.
 - Citizen Behaviour Tracking that will help managers and teachers perceive the problems of the society concerning the understanding of the waste management system. This particular service will be covered in several deliverables as it is spread among several components and services.
 - Green Procurement that will help managers introducing green procurement into their workflows. This service will be covered in detail in Deliverable D1.3 and D2.7.
 - Circular Economy that will help assessing the impact of implementing different best practices in an area. This service will be covered in detail in Deliverable D2.9.
 - *Serious Games and Learning Materials.* This category groups the services that will be used to teach lessons about the waste collection system in different contexts. These services will be developed in Deliverables D4.3 to D4.5.
 - *APPs layer.* This category groups three apps.
 - Citizen app that will help citizens retrieving useful information about the waste collection system.
 - Food waste app that will give food producers the opportunity to avoid generating food waste by looking for potentials re-users of the food.
 - Local trade app that will help citizens to retrieve useful information about the actions that local business are taking to reduce their waste generation.

Figure 12. Generic IoT communication architecture

Being an idealist representation of the IoT architecture, this approach does not consider that some of the services or layers may already be deployed. Please note that, we must avoid substituting components that are already deployed in the pilot sites and are working correctly. Due to the fact that the four pilot sites have different boundary conditions that limit the use of the reference architecture, the next sections will present how we have adapted the aforementioned reference architecture to the characteristics and needs of each of the four pilots.

5.2.1 Pilots with already deployed solutions: Cascais and Seveso

Figure 13 and Figure 14 show the conceptual architecture of the Cascais and Seveso pilots. As seen, both architectures are similar, but present a main difference with respect to the reference architecture: the presence of an already existing software that manage the waste collection system: In the case of Cascais, the Mawis solution from MOBA, and in the case of Seveso, the Wintarif solution.

Mawis features its own middleware (MIP) that connects the sensor layer with a Dashboard, an Invoicing module, a Persistence module and, most importantly, a Collection Management module. All these existing services will be improved during the project (it will be covered in detail in Deliverable D2.5). The rest of new services defined in the Waste4Think project will be deployed through the configuration of a connector between MIP and FIWARE middleware in order to retrieve all the necessary data. This pilot is also unique in regards of the transport layer, since all sensors use a wireless connection to send real time information to the MIP.

Wintarif on its part, being basically a persistence layer itself, provides a Dashboard, a Long Term Planner and an Invoice module. Following the aforementioned approach, all these existing services will be upgraded during the project (it will be covered in detail in Deliverable D2.7), while the creation of new services will be achieved by configuring a connector between Wintarif and FIWARE middleware in order to retrieve the relevant data. Another particularity of this pilot is the use of bags to measure the amount of waste produced and to identify the user of the system.

Figure 13. Conceptual architecture of Cascais

Figure 14. Conceptual architecture of Seveso

5.2.2 Pilots without deployed solutions: HALANDRI and ZAMUDIO

Figure 15 and Figure 16 present the conceptual architectures of the Halandri and Zamudio pilots. As seen, both architectures are quite similar to the reference architecture since the pilots do not present many boundary conditions. However, they do feature some particularities worth noting:

- In both cases containers will use the waste collection trucks as a transport layer of the information retrieved there. More details will be provided in Deliverable D2.1.
- Halandri does not plan to implement a PAYT scheme, therefore, its architecture does not feature this module.
- Halandri is going to implement several new generation treatment plants that will be monitored almost in real time. More details will be provided in Deliverable 2.1.

Figure 15. Conceptual architecture of Halandri

Figure 16. Conceptual architecture of Zamudio

5.3. Definition of the APIs

In order to gather the needs and contributions from all the solutions, a template to retrieve information from all the partners were build. All partners have been asked to fill in the template with the description of the technical functionalities for each of their results in terms of data needs, data processing, and expected outputs. The information requested in the template is explained below:

- **Functionality:** Descriptive name that allows to immediately identify a specific functionality among others.
- **Input:**
 - Input Data: Description of the data needed by the functionality.
 - Real-Time or Historic: Description about whether the data should be provided as soon as it is recorded or will be collected in batches.
 - Communication protocol: Description about whether the specific functionality needs to be connected to the network in order to retrieve or receive the input data, and if so define whether it can use the HTTP protocol.
 - API provider(s): Component of the solution providing the API.
 - Data model entity(es): List of entities of the Waste4Think data model or other standard format used by the Input Data.
- **Output:**
 - Output Data: Description of the data that a specific functionality provides.
 - Real-Time or Batch: Description about whether the data should be provided as soon as it is produced or it will be sent in batches.

- Communication protocol: Description about whether the specific functionality needs to be connected to the network in order to send the output data, and if so define whether it can use the HTTP protocol.
- API user(s): Component of Waste4Think platform consuming the API.
- Data model entity(es): List of entities of the Waste4Think data model or other standard format used by the Output Data.

Annex F (confidential) contains the information completed by the relevant partners of the project. As it contains confidential information, only a summary of it can be consulted in this deliverable. Using this information, Figure 17 was build. As can be seen, almost all the APIs are provided by the back-end of R1 and consumed by the rest of components. Some notable exceptions are:

- **The interactions between the Collection Management Module and the Back-End:** These entries of the API are basically the connector between FIWARE and both the MIP and Wintarif. Please note that these calls will be used to share the information between these tools and the rest of solutions provided in Waste4Think.
- **The feedback loop between the back-end and both the Learning Analytics Module and the Apps:** The Serious Games and the Learning Materials will retrieve information from the back-end to personalize the different stages and materials but they will also retrieve information about the use of these games and learning materials (Citizen Behaviour Tracking Module) that have to come back to the back-end as inputs.
- **The use of the Serious Games by the Citizen Science Actions:** to perform some of the Citizen Science Actions it is needed to configure a Serious Game to get realistic scenarios. To this end, some APIs should have to be defined.
- **The use of the Long Term Planner and Circular Economy by the Serious Games:** The Planning Game will use the results from Long Term Planner Module and the Best Practices Database in some games.

Figure 17. Logical architecture of the project

6. Pilots deployment schedule

In order to facilitate the follow up of the status of the eco-solutions deployment as well as the monitoring system (sensors deployed) in each pilot site a Gantt Chart has been created and it is available in Annex G. This Gantt Chart is divided into 6 tables, one for each group of the eco-solutions:

- IoT
- Operational and Planning tools
- Apps
- Educational Materials
- Social Actions
- Treatment Plants

The rows on the top present the planned status of the implementation of the functional requirements according to the Grant Agreement. On the other hand, the bottom of the table provides information about the planned status of the integration in each pilot site.

This Gantt Chart will be used as the basis to monitor the status of the project and it will be reported in the corresponding monitoring deliverables from D1.4 Preparatory Actions Report to D1.7 Full Test Report from milestone MS2 to MS5, respectively.

7. Annexes of Deliverable D1.1

- A. Legislative framework.
- B. Functional requirements (this appendix contains a confidential part not included in this deliverable).
 - B1 Target group identification per pilot site.
 - B2. Functional Requirements.
- C. Use Cases (this appendix contains a confidential part not included in this deliverable).
- D. Technical requirements.
 - D1. Pilot: Seveso
 - D2. Pilot: Halandri
 - D3. Pilot: Zamudio
 - D4. Pilot: Cascais
- E. System architecture
 - E1. System architecture: List of cards with the components of waste management systems in Waste4Think
 - E2. System architecture: List of cards with the components of waste management systems in Waste4Think
- F. APIS (this appendix contains a confidential part not included in this deliverable).
- G. Pilots deployment schedule
- H. Comments from External Reviewers

A.LEGISLATIVE FRAMEWORK

a. EU legislation

i. General

<p>Name of the law</p>	<p>EU.G.1. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and The Committee of the Regions Closing the Loop - An EU action plan for the Circular Economy</p>
<p>Type of waste regulated</p>	<p>All</p>
<p>Quantitative objectives</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A common EU target for recycling 65% of municipal waste by 2030; • A common EU target for recycling 75% of packaging waste by 2030; • Material-specific targets for different packaging materials; • A binding landfill target to reduce landfill to maximum of 10% of municipal waste by 2030; • A ban on landfilling of separately collected waste;
<p>Other strategies included</p>	<p>Measurements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • simplification and harmonisation of definitions and calculation methods to ensure comparable, high quality statistics across the EU (specially recycling rates); • special rules for Member States facing the biggest implementation challenges; • simplification of reporting obligations and alleviating obligations faced by SMEs; • introduction of an Early Warning System for monitoring compliance with targets; • steering Member States towards greater use of economic instruments (such as a landfill tax) to incentivise the application of waste hierarchy Promotion of economic instruments to discourage landfilling <p>Incentives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • concrete measures to boost reuse activities, including a clearer definition and rules that expand the scope of reuse activities rewarded under the EU targets; • general requirements for the operation of Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) schemes – meaning a producer’s responsibility for a product is extended to the post-consumer stage of a product’s life cycle, aimed at improving their performance and transparency, including direct financial incentives for greener product design; • Economic incentives for producers to put greener products on the market and support recovery and recycling schemes (eg for packaging, batteries, electric and electronic equipments, vehicles). • clearer rules on by-products and end-of-waste criteria to stimulate the sharing of by-product resources among industries and markets for recycled materials; • new measures to promote prevention, including for food waste and marine litter, and reuse; provisions to improve the traceability of hazardous waste.

FOOD WASTE

- develop a common EU methodology to measure food waste and define relevant indicators;
- create a platform, bringing together Member States and all actors of the food chain, to help define the measures needed to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals on food waste and share best practice and results achieved;
- take measures to clarify EU legislation relating to waste, food and feed, and facilitate food donation as well as the safe use of former foodstuffs and by-products in feed production.
- examine ways to improve the use of date marking by actors of the food chain and its understanding by consumers, in particular the "best before" label.

BIO-WASTE

- the revised legislative proposal on waste contains a target for recycling wood packaging and a provision to ensure the separate collection of bio-waste

CIRCULAR ECONOMY

1) End of waste criteria

According to Article 6 (1) and (2) of the Waste Framework Directive 2008/98/EC, certain specified waste shall cease to be waste when it has undergone a recovery (including recycling) operation and complies with specific criteria to be developed in line with certain legal conditions,

Such criteria should be set for specific materials by the Commission using the procedure described in Article 39(2) of the Waste Framework Directive. the Commission is now preparing a set of end-of-waste criteria for priority waste streams.

End-of-waste Criteria technical proposals (European Commission - Joint Research Centre)	Specific regulation
Waste plastic for conversion	
Paper	
Compost & digestate	
Glass	Commission Regulation on EoW for glass cullet (1179/2012)
Copper and Copper Alloy Scrap (bulky, WEEE,..)	Commission Regulation on EoW for copper scrap (715/2013)
aluminium scrap (packaging, weee).	Council Regulation (333/2011)
Iron Steel scrap (municipal & bulky waste)	iron, steel and aluminium scrap
Study on methodological aspects regarding limit values for pollutants in aggregates in the context of the possible development of end-of-	

[waste criteria under the EU Waste Framework Directive](#)

Waste no longer holding waste status under end-of-waste, is to be regarded as a substance and therefore falls under the scope of the REACH Regulation. Waste, as defined in the EU's waste legislation, is exempt from REACH, but a product recovered from waste is not. REACH applies for any substance, mixture or article you recover from waste that meets the end of waste criteria.

Exemption for a recovered substance that has already been registered by someone else. [Registration is not required](#) for substances: Already registered and recovered through a waste recovery process

Substances included in Annex V are exempted from registration for all their possible uses (currently or in the future). It should be noted that the companies benefiting from an exemption must provide the authorities (on request) with appropriate information to show that their substances qualify for the exemption.

2) Distinction between waste and by-products

By-product: substance or object, resulting from a production process (industrial kitchens..), the primary aim of which is not the production of that item

[Communication from the Commission to the Council and the European Parliament on the Interpretative Communication on waste and by-products /* COM/2007/0059 final */](#)

[Procedimiento evaluación subproducto](#) ministerio medio ambiente en relación al artículo 4 de la [Ley 22/2011](#)

Figure 4. 1. Sub product diagram

	<pre> graph TD Q1[Is the intended use of the material legal?] -- No --> A1[The material is waste] Q1 -- Yes --> Q2[Was the material deliberately produced? (Did the production process change to produce the material?)] Q2 -- Yes --> A2[The material is a product, not a production] Q2 -- No --> A3[The material is a production waste - 'infra' criteria applies] A3 --> Q3[Is the material going to be used for sure?] Q3 -- No --> A4[The material is waste] Q3 -- Yes --> Q4[Is the material prepared for use without previous transformation (different from the normal process, as an integral part of the production process)?] Q4 -- No --> A5[The material is waste] Q4 -- Yes --> Q5[Is the material produced as an integral part of the] Q5 -- No --> A6[The material is waste] Q5 -- Yes --> A7[The material is then a Sub product, not waste] </pre>
	<p>Waste no longer holding waste status under end-of-waste, is to be regarded as a substance and therefore falls under the scope of the REACH Regulation. Waste, as defined in the EU's waste legislation, is exempt from REACH, but a product recovered from waste is not. REACH applies for any substance, mixture or article you recover from waste that meets the end of waste criteria.</p> <p>Exemption for a recovered substance that has already been registered by someone else. Registration is not required for substances: Already registered and recovered through a waste recovery process</p> <p>Substances included in Annex V are exempted from registration for all their possible uses (currently or in the future). It should be noted that the companies benefiting from an exemption must provide the authorities (on request) with appropriate information to show that their substances qualify for the exemption.</p>
Management Competences	-
Link to the document	http://ec.europa.eu/environment/circular-economy/index_en.htm http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52015DC0614

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Name of the law	EU.G.2. Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Directive 2008/98/EC on waste /Draft report on the proposal for a directive of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Directive 2008/98/EC on waste (COM(2015)0595 – C8-0382/2015 – 2015/0275(COD))
Type of waste regulated	All
Quantitative objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The targets for preparation for re-use and recycling of municipal waste should be increased at least to 60 % by 2025 and at least to 70 % by 2030 • Target of reducing food waste by 50 % by 2030 • Target of reducing marine litter by 50 % by 2030. • By 31 December 2018, the Commission shall examine the possibility of setting up Union-wide waste prevention targets to be met by 2025 and 2030.
Other strategies included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Member States shall take measures, as appropriate, to promote preparing for re-use activities, notably by encouraging the establishment of and support for re-use and repair networks and by facilitating the access of such networks to waste collection points, and by promoting the use of economic instruments, procurement criteria, quantitative objectives or other measures. • Member States should put in place adequate incentives for the application of the waste hierarchy, in particular, by means of financial, fiscal and regulatory incentives aimed at achieving the waste prevention and recycling objectives of this Directive, such as landfill and incineration charges, pay as you throw schemes, extended producer responsibility schemes and incentives for local authorities.. • Member States should ensure the establishment of extended producer responsibility schemes for at least packaging, electrical and electronic equipment and batteries and accumulators. Moreover, Member States should encourage the establishment of extended producer responsibility schemes for all other relevant waste streams. • It is important that Member States set up national prevention reduction targets taking appropriate measures to prevent waste generation and littering, including the use of adequate economic instruments and awareness campaigns for citizens. • Compliance with the obligation to set up separate collection systems for paper, metal, plastic, glass, wood and textile is essential in order to increase preparing for re-use and recycling rates in Member States. In addition bio-waste should be collected separately to contribute to an increase in preparing for re-use and recycling rates and the prevention of contamination of dry recyclable materials. In addition, separate collection of bio-waste from municipal waste should be made obligatory and a recycling target should be laid down for bio-waste from municipal waste to attract infrastructure investments towards recycling facilities for bio-waste and to boost markets for compost and digestate.
Management Competences	-

Link to the document	http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52015PC0595 http://www.europarl.europa.eu/sides/getDoc.do?pubRef=-%2F%2FEP%2F%2FNONGML%2BCOMPARL%2BPE-580.497%2B01%2BDOC%2BPDF%2BV0%2F%2FEN
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Name of the law	EU.G.3. Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 November 2008 on waste and repealing certain directives (OJ L 312, 22.11.2008, pp. 3–30)
Type of waste regulated	All
Quantitative objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It introduces recycling and recovery targets to be achieved by 2020 for household waste (50 %) and construction and demolition waste (70 %). Specifically: by 2020, the preparing for re-use and the recycling of waste materials such as at least paper, metal, plastic and glass from households and possibly from other origins as far as these waste streams are similar to waste from households, shall be increased to a minimum of overall 50 % by weight; by the end of 2014, the setting of waste prevention and decoupling objectives for 2020, based on best available practices including, if necessary, a revision of the indicators referred to in Article 29(4).
Other strategies included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The legislation establishes a waste hierarchy: prevention, re-use, recycling, recovery for other purposes such as energy and disposal. It confirms the ‘polluter pays principle’ whereby the original waste producer must pay for the costs of waste management. It introduces the concept of ‘extended producer responsibility’. This may include an onus on manufacturers to accept and dispose of products returned after use.
Management Competences	Competent national authorities must establish waste management plans and waste prevention programmes
Link to the document	http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:32008L0098

ii. Treatment

Name of the law	EU.T.1. Directive 1999/31/EC of European Council of 26 April 1999 on the landfill of waste
Type of waste regulated	Disposed waste
Quantitative objectives	By no later than 2016, biodegradable municipal waste going to landfills must be reduced to 35 % of the total amount (by weight) of biodegradable municipal waste produced in 1995 or the latest year before 1995 for which standardised Eurostat data is available.

Other strategies included	Only waste that has been treated may be landfilled.
Management Competences	Member States shall set up a national strategy for the implementation of the reduction of biodegradable waste going to landfills. At intervals of three years Member States shall send to the Commission a report on the implementation of this Directive.
Link to the document	http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:31999L0031

Name of the law	EU.T.2. Directive 2000/76/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 December 2000 on the incineration of waste
Type of waste regulated	Incinerated waste. Incineration of both hazardous and harmless wastes may cause emissions of substances which pollute the air, water and soil and have harmful effects on human health.
Quantitative objectives	R1 Formula for incineration facilities (Annex II of the Waste Directive), to consider the activity as a recovery operation: This includes incineration facilities dedicated to the processing of municipal solid waste only where their energy efficiency is equal to or above: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> — 0,60 for installations in operation and permitted in accordance with applicable Community legislation before 1 January 2009, — 0,65 for installations permitted after 31 December 2008, using the following formula: Energy efficiency = $(E_p - (E_f + E_i)) / (0,97 \times (E_w + E_f))$
Other strategies included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All incineration or co-incineration plants must have a permit to carry out their activities. In order to guarantee complete waste combustion, the Directive requires all plants to keep the incineration or co-incineration gases at a temperature of at least 850°C for at least two seconds. • The limit values for incineration plant emissions to air are set out in Annex V to the Directive. They concern heavy metals, dioxins and furans, carbon monoxide (CO), dust, total organic carbon (TOC), hydrogen chloride (HCl), hydrogen fluoride (HF), sulphur dioxide (SO₂) and the nitrogen oxides (NO and NO₂). • The Directive requires the installation of measurement systems to monitor the parameters of an installation and relevant emissions. Emissions to air and to water must be measured continuously or periodically in accordance with Article 11 and Annex III of the Directive.
Management Competences	
Link to the document	http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:32000L0076 More info on R1 Formula http://ec.europa.eu/environment/waste/framework/pdf/guidance.pdf

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iii. Fraction

Name of the law	EU.F.1. Directive 94/62/EC of European Parliament and Council of 20 December 1994 on packaging and packaging waste
Type of waste regulated	Packaging
Quantitative objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • by no later than 30 June 2001, between 50 and 65 % by weight of packaging waste to be recovered or incinerated at waste incineration plants with energy recovery; • by no later than 31 December 2008, at least 60 % by weight of packaging waste to be recovered or incinerated at waste incineration plants with energy recovery; • by no later than 30 June 2001, between 25 and 45 % by weight of the totality of packaging materials contained in packaging waste to be recycled (with a minimum of 15 % by weight for each packaging material); • by no later than 31 December 2008, between 55 and 80 % by weight of packaging waste to be recycled; • no later than 31 December 2008 the following targets for materials contained in packaging waste must be attained: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 60 % for glass, paper and board; • 50 % for metals; • 22.5 % for plastics and; • 15 % for wood.
Other strategies included	<p>Member States must ensure that packaging placed on the market complies with the essential requirements of Annex II:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • to limit the weight and volume of packaging to a minimum in order meet the required level of safety, hygiene and acceptability for consumers; • to reduce the content of hazardous substances and materials in the packaging material and its components; • to design reusable or recoverable packaging.
Management Competences	Member States should develop information systems (databases) on packaging and packaging waste so that realisation of the targets of this Directive can be monitored.
Link to the document	http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=URISERV:l21207&from=EN

Name of the law	EU.F.2. Directive (EU) 2015/720 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2015 amending Directive 94/62/EC as regards reducing the consumption of lightweight plastic carrier bags It amends Directive 94/62/EC on packaging and packaging waste
Type of waste regulated	Lightweight plastic carrier bags
Quantitative objectives	<p>EU countries must take measures to reduce the consumption of lightweight (wall thickness below 50 microns to 15)* plastic carrier bags. These may include national reduction targets, restrictions on their use or financial measures such as charging for them.</p> <p>The measures must include either one or both of the following:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. defining a maximum annual consumption level of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 90 lightweight plastic carrier bags per person by the end of 2019 (a 50 % reduction compared to 2010) and • 40 lightweight plastic carrier bags per person by the end of 2025 (an 80 % reduction compared to 2010) 2. ensuring that, by the end of 2018, lightweight plastic carrier bags are not provided free of charge at the point of sale of goods or products.
Other strategies included	-
Management Competences	From 27 May 2018, EU countries must report the annual consumption of lightweight plastic carrier bags to the EC
Link to the document	http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32015L0720

Compost application

Name of the law	EU.O.1.End-of-waste criteria for biodegradable waste subjected to biological treatment (compost & digestate): Technical proposals																																																				
Type of waste regulated	Biowaste-Compost																																																				
Quantitative objectives		<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="727 580 930 636">Quality / Standard</th> <th data-bbox="930 580 1198 636"></th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="727 636 930 680">As</td> <td data-bbox="930 636 1198 680">-</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="727 680 930 725">Cd</td> <td data-bbox="930 680 1198 725">1,5</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="727 725 930 770">Cr (tot)</td> <td data-bbox="930 725 1198 770">100</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="727 770 930 815">Cr VI</td> <td data-bbox="930 770 1198 815">-</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="727 815 930 860">Cu</td> <td data-bbox="930 815 1198 860">200</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="727 860 930 904">Hg</td> <td data-bbox="930 860 1198 904">1</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="727 904 930 949">Ni</td> <td data-bbox="930 904 1198 949">50</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="727 949 930 994">Pb</td> <td data-bbox="930 949 1198 994">120</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="727 994 930 1039">Zn</td> <td data-bbox="930 994 1198 1039">600</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="727 1039 930 1084">PERSISTENS ORGANIC POLLUTANTS CONCENTRATIONS (mg·kg⁻¹ d. m.)</td> <td data-bbox="930 1039 1198 1084">Total PAH</td> <td data-bbox="930 1039 1198 1084">< 6</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="727 1084 930 1184"></td> <td data-bbox="727 1084 930 1184">Total PCB</td> <td data-bbox="930 1084 1198 1184"></td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="727 1184 930 1252">IMPURITIES</td> <td data-bbox="727 1184 930 1252">Total (> 2 mm fraction)</td> <td data-bbox="930 1184 1198 1252">< 0,5%</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="727 1252 930 1319"></td> <td data-bbox="727 1252 930 1319">Total (> 5 mm fraction)</td> <td data-bbox="930 1252 1198 1319"></td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="727 1319 930 1386">QUALITY REQUIREMENTS</td> <td data-bbox="727 1319 930 1386">Organic matter</td> <td data-bbox="930 1319 1198 1386">> 15%</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="727 1386 930 1509">SANITISATION MICROBIAL INDICATORS</td> <td data-bbox="727 1386 930 1431"><i>Salmonella sp.</i></td> <td data-bbox="930 1386 1198 1431">absents in 25 g</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="727 1431 930 1476"></td> <td data-bbox="727 1431 930 1476"><i>Escherichia coli</i></td> <td data-bbox="930 1431 1198 1476">< 1000 CFU/g</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="727 1476 930 1509"></td> <td data-bbox="727 1476 930 1509"><i>Others</i></td> <td data-bbox="930 1476 1198 1509"></td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="727 1509 930 1626">OTHER ASPECTS</td> <td data-bbox="727 1509 930 1554">Weeds (plants·L⁻¹)</td> <td data-bbox="930 1509 1198 1554">≤ 2</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="727 1554 930 1626"></td> <td data-bbox="727 1554 930 1626">Stability Maturity</td> <td data-bbox="930 1554 1198 1626">Rottegrade III / OUR < 25 mmol O₂·kg⁻¹ VS·h⁻¹</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Quality / Standard		As	-	Cd	1,5	Cr (tot)	100	Cr VI	-	Cu	200	Hg	1	Ni	50	Pb	120	Zn	600	PERSISTENS ORGANIC POLLUTANTS CONCENTRATIONS (mg·kg ⁻¹ d. m.)	Total PAH	< 6		Total PCB		IMPURITIES	Total (> 2 mm fraction)	< 0,5%		Total (> 5 mm fraction)		QUALITY REQUIREMENTS	Organic matter	> 15%	SANITISATION MICROBIAL INDICATORS	<i>Salmonella sp.</i>	absents in 25 g		<i>Escherichia coli</i>	< 1000 CFU/g		<i>Others</i>		OTHER ASPECTS	Weeds (plants·L ⁻¹)	≤ 2		Stability Maturity	Rottegrade III / OUR < 25 mmol O ₂ ·kg ⁻¹ VS·h ⁻¹	
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	Stability Maturity	Rottegrade III / OUR < 25 mmol O ₂ ·kg ⁻¹ VS·h ⁻¹																																																			
Other strategies included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The scope includes non-contaminated input materials from the separate collection of bio-waste, as well as from biodegradable residues from agriculture (including manure), forestry, fishery and horticulture, or any such previously composted or digested material • The producer must demonstrate for each compost/digestate batch that a suitable time-temperature profile was followed during the composting/digestion process for all material contained in the batch • Producers need to declare a number of parameters and information about the product and the way in which it should be used. This includes its: v Usefulness concerning soil improving function v Fertilising properties (macro and micro nutrient content) v Biological properties v General material 																																																				

	<p>properties The name and address of the producer, batch code and external quality assurance organisation also need to be declared.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compost/digestate producers are required to operate a quality management system in compliance with quality assurance standards that are recognised as suitable for compost/digestate production by Member States or the Community. • Compost/digestate ceases to be waste, provided all other end-of-waste criteria are fulfilled, when used by the producer or upon its transfer from the producer to the next holder. Use and transfer may include a period of temporary storage of stable materials for a maximum of 18 month, under proper conditions.
Management Competences	
Link to the document	<p>http://ftp.jrc.es/EURdoc/JRC87124.pdf http://www.compostnetwork.info/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2011/08/140122_ECN_Info-paper_01_2014_EoW.pdf</p>

Food wastage

Name of the law	EU.O.2. European Parliament resolution of 19 January 2012 on how to avoid food wastage: strategies for a more efficient food chain in the EU (2011/2175(INI))
Type of waste regulated	Food waste
Quantitative objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To take practical measures towards halving food waste by 2025 and at the same time preventing the generation of bio-waste
Other key strategies included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To involve all participants in the food supply chain and to target the various causes of waste sector by sector; therefore, to make an analysis of the whole food chain in order to identify in which food sectors food waste is occurring most, and which solutions can be used to prevent food waste. • Create specific food waste prevention targets for Member States, as part of the waste prevention targets to be reached by Member States by 2014, as recommended by the 2008 Waste Framework Directive. • Quality requirements regarding appearance, whether imposed by European or national legislation or by internal company rules, which stipulate the size and shape of fresh fruit and vegetables in particular, are at the basis of many unnecessary discards, which increase the amount of food wasted; asks stakeholders to recognise and explain the nutritional value of agricultural products of imperfect size/shape in order to reduce discards.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encourage the exchange of best practice and promote awareness-raising campaigns to inform the public of the value of food and agricultural produce, the causes and effects of food waste and ways of reducing it, thereby fostering a scientific and civic culture guided by the principles of sustainability and solidarity; calls Member States to encourage the introduction of food education courses, at all levels of education, including colleges, explaining for example how to store, cook and dispose the food, thereby encouraging better behaviours; stresses the important role played by local authorities and municipal enterprises, in addition to retailers and the media, in providing information and support to citizens on preventing and reducing food waste. • Welcome the initiatives already taken in various Member States aimed at recovering, locally, unsold and discarded products throughout the food supply chain in order to redistribute them to groups of citizens below the minimum income threshold who lack purchasing power; stresses the importance of the exchange of best practices in this connection between Member States, as also of initiatives at local level. • Calls on the Member States to encourage and support initiatives geared to stimulating sustainable small- and medium-scale production that is linked to local and regional markets and consumption; acknowledges that local markets are environmentally sustainable and contribute to the stability of the primary sector.
Management Competences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Calls on the Commission, in cooperation with the Member States, to issue recommendations regarding refrigeration temperatures, based on evidence that non-optimal and improper temperature leads to food becoming prematurely inedible and causes unnecessary waste; underlines the fact that harmonised levels of temperature throughout the supply chain would improve product conservation and reduce food waste for products transported and sold cross-border;
Link to the document/web	goo.gl/zKTjYa

Food safety/food supply

Name of the law	EU.O.3.Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 January 2002 laying down the general principles and requirements of food law, establishing the European Food Safety Authority and laying down procedures in matters of food safety
Type of waste regulated	Food Safety
Quantitative objectives	-

Other key strategies included

- Food law shall pursue one or more of the general objectives of a high level of protection of human life and health and the protection of consumers' interests, including fair practices in food trade, taking account of, where appropriate, the protection of animal health and welfare, plant health and the environment.
- Food law shall aim at the protection of the interests of consumers and shall provide a basis for consumers to make informed choices in relation to the foods they consume.
- Food safety requirements:
 - Food shall not be placed on the market if it is unsafe.
 - Food shall be deemed to be unsafe if it is considered to be:
 - (a) injurious to health;
 - (b) unfit for human consumption.
 - In determining whether any food is unsafe, regard shall be had:
 - (a) to the normal conditions of use of the food by the consumer and at each stage of production, processing and distribution, and
 - (b) to the information provided to the consumer, including information on the label, or other information generally available to the consumer concerning the avoidance of specific adverse health effects from a particular food or category of foods.
- The traceability of food, feed, food-producing animals, and any other substance intended to be, or expected to be, incorporated into a food or feed shall be established at all stages of production, processing and distribution.
- Where it is evident that food or feed originating in the Community or imported from a third country is likely to constitute a serious risk to human health, animal health or the environment, and that such risk cannot be contained satisfactorily by means of measures taken by the Member State(s) concerned, the Commission, acting in accordance with the procedure provided for in Article 58(2) on its own initiative or at the request of a Member State, shall immediately adopt one or more of the following measures, depending on the gravity of the situation:
 - in the case of food or feed of Community origin:
 - suspension of the placing on the market or use of the food in question;
 - suspension of the placing on the market or use of the feed in question;
 - laying down special conditions for the food or feed in question;
 - any other appropriate interim measure;
 - in the case of food or feed imported from a third country:
 - suspension of imports of the food or feed in question from all or part of the third country concerned and, where applicable, from the third country of transit;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ laying down special conditions for the food or feed in question from all or part of the third country concerned; ▪ any other appropriate interim measure.
<p>Management Competences</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Food Safety Authority, hereinafter referred to as the ‘Authority’, is hereby established. The tasks of the Authority shall be the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ to provide the Community institutions and the Member States with the best possible scientific opinions in all cases provided by Community legislation and on any question within its mission; ○ to promote and coordinate the development of uniform risk assessment methodologies in the fields falling within its mission; ○ to provide scientific and technical support to the Commission in the areas within its mission and, when so requested, in the interpretation and consideration of risk assessment opinions; ○ to commission scientific studies necessary for the accomplishment of its mission; ○ to search for, collect, collate, analyse and summarise scientific and technical data in the fields within its mission; ○ to undertake action to identify and characterise emerging risks, in the fields within its mission; ○ to establish a system of networks of organisations operating in the fields within its mission and be responsible for their operation; ○ to provide scientific and technical assistance, when requested to do so by the Commission, in the crisis management procedures implemented by the Commission with regard to the safety of food and feed; ○ to provide scientific and technical assistance, when requested to do so by the Commission, with a view to improving cooperation between the Community, applicant countries, international organisations and third countries, in the fields within its mission; ○ to ensure that the public and interested parties receive rapid, reliable, objective and comprehensible information in the fields within its mission; ○ to express independently its own conclusions and orientations on matters within its mission; ○ to undertake any other task assigned to it by the Commission within its mission. • A rapid alert system for the notification of a direct or indirect risk to human health deriving from food or feed is hereby established as a network. It shall involve the Member States, the Commission and the Authority. The Member States, the Commission and the Authority shall each designate a contact point, which shall be a member of the network. The Commission shall be responsible for managing the network. • The Commission shall be assisted by a Standing Committee on the Food Chain and Animal Health, hereinafter referred to as the ‘Committee’, composed of

	representatives of the Member States and chaired by the representative of the Commission. The Committee shall be organised in sections to deal with all relevant matters.
Link to the document/web	goo.gl/44t8Te

Name of the law	EU.O.4.Regulation (EC) N° 852/2004 of the European Parliament and the Council of 29 April 2004 on the hygiene of foodstuffs
Type of waste regulated	Food Waste / Food Safety
Quantitative objectives	-
Other key strategies included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lay down general rules for food business operators on the hygiene of foodstuffs, taking particular account of the following principles: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Primary responsibility for food safety rests with the food business operator. ○ To ensure food safety throughout the food chain, starting with primary production; ○ For food that cannot be stored safely at ambient temperatures, particularly frozen food, to maintain the cold chain; ○ General implementation of procedures based on the HACCP principles, together with the application of good hygiene practice, should reinforce food business operators' responsibility; ○ Guides to good practice are a valuable instrument to aid food business operators at all levels of the food chain with compliance with food hygiene rules and with the application of the HACCP principles. ○ To establish microbiological criteria and temperature control requirements based on a scientific risk assessment. ○ To ensure that imported foods are of at least the same hygiene standard as food produced in the Community, or are of an equivalent standard.
Management Competences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Member States shall encourage the development of national guides to good practice for hygiene and for the application of HACCP principles. The dissemination and use of both national and Community guides shall be encouraged. Nevertheless, food business operators may use these guides on a voluntary basis.
Link to the document/web	goo.gl/V4swKM

Name of the law	EU.O.5. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, The European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions “A better functioning food supply chain in Europe”
Type of waste regulated	Food Waste
Quantitative objectives	-
Other key strategies included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote sustainable and market-based relationships between stakeholders in the food supply chain. • Increase transparency along the food supply chain to encourage competition and improve its resilience to price volatility. • Foster the integration and competitiveness of the European food supply chain across Member States.
Management Competences	-
Link to the document/web	https://goo.gl/uKMdA7

Green Public Procurement

Name of the law	EU.O.6. Directive 2014/24/EU of the European Parliament and the Council of February 2014 on public procurement and repealing 2004/18/EC
Type of waste regulated	Public Procurement
Quantitative objectives	These reforms of the Public Procurement Directives made in 2014 reinforce the role of public procurement as an instrument of political strategy. The new Directives promote SMEs’ access to public procurement and facilitate the implementation of environmental policies, social integration and innovation.
Other key strategies included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consider the costs of the entire life cycle, both internal costs (use, maintenance and management of products in disuse), as well as external costs associated with environmental impacts generated (costs associated with greenhouse gas emissions). • Include sustainability criteria linked to the production process of products and services, although they are not part of the material substance of the same. • Require specific labels that certificate environmental, social or other characteristics of goods, works or services.

Management Competences	-
Link to the document/web	http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/es/TXT/?uri=celex:32014L0024

Name of the law	EU.O.7. Directive 2014/25/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 February 2014 on procurement by institutions operating in the water, energy, transport and postal services and repealing the Directive 2004/17/EC.
Type of waste regulated	Public Procurement
Quantitative objectives	These reforms of the Public Procurement Directives made in 2014 reinforce the role of public procurement as an instrument of political strategy. The new Directives promote SMEs' access to public procurement and facilitate the implementation of environmental policies, social integration and innovation.
Other key strategies included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consider the costs of the entire life cycle, both internal costs (use, maintenance and management of products in disuse), as well as external costs associated with environmental impacts generated (costs associated with greenhouse gas emissions). • Include sustainability criteria linked to the production process of products and services, although they are not part of the material substance of the same. • Require specific labels that certify environmental, social or other characteristics of goods, works or services.
Management Competences	-
Link to the document/web	http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:32014L0025

b. Zamudio

i. National legislation

General

Name of the law	ES.N.1. Framework State Plan on waste management (PEMAR) 2016-2022 Plan Estatal Marco de Gestión de Residuos (PEMAR) 2016-2022
Type of waste regulated	All
Quantitative objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Objectives of preparation for reuse and recycling: (minimum) 50% of preparation for reuse and recycling by 2020, of which 2% will be the preparation for reuse mainly of textile waste, WEEE, furniture and other waste susceptible of being prepared for reuse. Objectives of elimination: in 2016, achieve the objective of reducing landfilling of biodegradable waste (reduce by 12 percentage points the dumping of this waste since 2012). Prohibition of landfilling untreated municipal waste. By 2020, limiting the landfilling of all municipal waste generated by 35%.
Other strategies included	<p>Implement progressively and gradually separate bio-waste collection for its biological treatment (anaerobic and aerobic):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strengthen the promotion of self-composting in those places where it is easily practicable (home composting in horizontal housing in urban and rural environments, community composting, self-composting in clean points). Introduce changes in existing separate collection systems to reduce the presence of impurities. Construction of new biological treatment facilities and / or adaptation of existing facilities to increase the capacity of treatment of separate collected bio-waste.
Management Competences	<p>In order to ensure compliance with national objectives, the CCAA must meet at least that goals with the waste generated in their territory, unless sectoral regulations set specific performance criteria.</p> <p>When targets affect municipal waste, local authorities have to put all means to fulfill those objectives. In any case, the CCAA in their regional waste management plans will establish the contribution of local authorities, independently or collectively, to fulfill the objectives applicable to municipal waste competition.</p>
Link to the document	http://www.magrama.gob.es/es/calidad-y-evaluacion-ambiental/planes-y-estrategias/pemaraprobado6noviembrecondae_tcm7-401704.pdf

Name of the law	ES.N.2.Law 22/2011, of 28 July 2011, on waste and contaminated soils Ley 22/2011, de 28 de julio, de residuos y suelos contaminados
Type of waste regulated	All
Quantitative objectives	<p>By 2020, the quantity of domestic and commercial waste for preparation for reuse and recycling of paper, metals, glass, plastics, bio-waste or other recyclable fractions shall reach together, at least 50 % in weigh.</p> <p>Before 2020, the amount of non-hazardous waste from construction and demolition for the preparation for reuse, recycling and other material recovery, excluding the materials in their natural state in Category 17 05 04 of waste List, must achieve at least 70% by weight of the produced.</p> <p>Replacement calendar for commercial single-use bags of non-biodegradable plastic (reference to the estimated quantities put on the market in 2007):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Before 2013, replacing 60% of the bags; b) by 2015, replacing 70% of bags; c) by 2016, replacing 80% of bags; d) in 2018, replacing all of these bags, except for those used to contain fish, meat and other perishables.
Other strategies included	<p>Application of the waste hierarchy in the following order of priority:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Prevention; b) Preparation for reuse; c) Recycling; d) Other recovery, including energy recovery; e) Elimination. <p>Before 2015 a separate collection scheme should be in force for at least: paper, metals, plastics and glass. The separate collection schemes that exist can be adapted to the separate material collection referred to in the last paragraph. More than one material of the same fraction can be collected when a further proper separation is guaranteed as long as it does not suppose a reduction of quality of the obtained materials nor an increase in cost</p> <p>BIO-WASTE</p> <p>Environmental authorities will promote:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) The bio-waste separate collection to be allocated to composting or anaerobic digestion in particular of the vegetal fraction, the biowaste from large generators and the bio-wastes generated in households. b) Domestic and community composting. c) The treatment of separate collected bio-waste without mixing with mixed waste during the process. Where appropriate, authorization of such installations must include the technical requirements for the proper treatment of bio-waste and the quality of the materials obtained. d) The use of compost produced from bio-waste and environmentally safe in agriculture, gardening or regeneration of degraded areas, replacing other organic and mineral fertilizers amendments.

	<p>COST AND TAXES</p> <p>'Polluter pays' principle, the costs have to be borne by the original waste producer, the current holder or the previous holder of waste.</p> <p>For the determination of domestic and commercial waste costs in local authorities, it should be included the actual cost of the operations of collection, transport and treatment of waste, including the supervision of such operations and the after-care of landfills.</p> <p>FOOD/FOOD WASTAGE</p> <p>Including measures to prevent food wastage and encourage responsible consumption, such as agreements with businesses to minimize expired food, establish guidelines for consumers, restoration and activities with dining area to take advantage of leftover food, create pathways for using of surpluses in good condition through popular social initiatives –popular dining rooms, food banks, etc.</p>
Management Competences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop waste prevention and management plans within its jurisdiction. • Municipal manage non-hazardous commercial waste and domestic waste generated by industries in the terms established in respective local ordinances, notwithstanding that the producers of this waste can manage it by themselves in the terms provided in Article 17.3. • Public administrations, in their respective areas of competence, will adopt before 12 December 2013, waste prevention programs in which the objectives of prevention, reducing the amount of waste generated and reducing the amount of dangerous or polluting substances shall be established. • The competent authorities may establish economic, fiscal and financial measures to promote the prevention of waste generation, implementing the separate collection and improving waste management. For these purposes landfilling and incineration taxes for household waste may be established.
Link to the document	https://www.boe.es/diario_boe/txt.php?id=BOE-A-2011-13046

Treatment

Name of the law	<p>ES.N.3. Royal Decree 1481/2001, of 27 December 2001, on waste elimination via landfilling. Last update, published on 23/04/2013</p> <p>Real Decreto 1481/2001, de 27 de diciembre, por el que se regula la eliminación de residuos mediante depósito en vertedero. Última actualización, publicada el 23/04/2013.</p>
Type of waste regulated	Disposed waste
Quantitative objectives	By no later than 16 July 2016, biodegradable municipal waste going to landfills must be reduced to 35 % of the total amount (by weight) of biodegradable municipal waste produced in 1995.
Other strategies included	<p>Only waste that has been treated previously may be landfilled.</p> <p>The price that the operator charges for the waste disposal in the landfill must cover at least the costs involved in its establishment and operation, the costs of</p>

	the guarantees referred in paragraphs c) and d) of Article 9.1, as well as the estimated costs of the closure and subsequent maintenance of the facility and the site during the period set by the authority, which in no case will be less than thirty years.
Management Competences	<p>Member States shall set up a national strategy for the implementation of the reduction of biodegradable waste going to landfills.</p> <p>At intervals of three years Member States shall send to the Commission a report on the implementation of this Directive.</p> <p>Before 16 July 2003, the General State Administration and the Administrations of the Autonomous Communities shall develop a joint program of actions to reduce biodegradable waste going to landfill. This program will include measures to achieve the objectives set out by the Decree, in particular through recycling, composting and other forms of valorisation, such as biogas production by anaerobic digestion.</p>
Link to the document	https://www.boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-2002-1697

Fractions

Name of the law	<p>ES.N.4. Law 11/1997, of 24 April 1997, on Packaging and Packaging waste. Royal Decree 252/2006, of 3 March 2006, on the revision of the recycling and valorisation objectives established by the Law 11/1997.</p> <p>Ley 11/1997, de 24 de abril, de Envases y Residuos de Envases. Real Decreto 252/2006, de 3 de marzo, por el que se revisan los objetivos de reciclado y valorización establecidos en la Ley 11/1997, de 24 de abril, de Envases y Residuos de Envases, y por el que se modifica el Reglamento para su ejecución, aprobado por el Real Decreto 782/1998, de 30 de abril.</p>
Type of waste regulated	Packaging
Quantitative objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Since the entry into force of this royal decree, it shall be recycled from a minimum of 25% and a maximum of 45% by weight of the totality of packaging materials contained in packaging waste, with a minimum of 15% by weight for each packaging material; • Before 31 December 2008, and in subsequent years, it will be recycled from a minimum of 55% and a maximum of 80% by weight of packaging waste; • Before 31 December 2008, and in subsequent years, it will be achieved the following minimum recycling targets for materials contained in packaging waste: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 60 % by weight for glass, • 60% by weight paper and cardboard; • 50 % by weight for metals; • 22.5 % by weight for plastics, exclusively considering the material that will be again transformed into plastics;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 15 % by weight for wood. • Before 31 December 2008, and in subsequent years, it will be valorised or incinerated at waste incineration facilities with energy recovery at least 60% by weight of packaging waste.
Other strategies included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Within their respective areas of competence, the General State Administration and the Autonomous Communities, after a consultation with the operators, will adopt appropriate measures, especially concerning the design and manufacturing process of packaging, in order to minimize and prevent at source the production of packaging waste. The adopted measures may include research and development activities, designed to promote prevention. • The public administrations, within their competence, will encourage the use of materials obtained from recycled packaging waste. To that end, the measures envisaged in the national waste plans aimed at increasing such use and to create or improve secondary markets for recycled materials from packaging waste will be promoted.
Management Competences	<p>Within a maximum period of one year from the entry into force of this Act, the Government will approve a National Program on Waste Packaging and used packaging, integrating the programs developed by the Autonomous Communities. The National Program will be included in the National Plan of Urban Waste Management and shall be valid for the entire national territory.</p>
Link to the document	<p>http://www.boe.es/diario_boe/txt.php?id=BOE-A-1997-8875 https://www.boe.es/buscar/doc.php?id=BOE-A-2006-3874</p>

ii. Regional legislation

Name of the law	ES.R.1. Comprehensive plan for urban waste management in Bizkaia 2005-2016																			
Type of waste regulated	All urban waste.																			
Quantitative objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Treatment objectives, no collection objectives. <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>Recycling</th> <th>Composting</th> <th>Other treatments (Energy recovery,...)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Domestic waste</td> <td>26%</td> <td>5%</td> <td>69%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Industrial, commercial and institutional waste assimilated to domestic</td> <td>67%</td> <td>3%</td> <td>30%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Total waste</td> <td>40%</td> <td>4%</td> <td>56%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>					Recycling	Composting	Other treatments (Energy recovery,...)	Domestic waste	26%	5%	69%	Industrial, commercial and institutional waste assimilated to domestic	67%	3%	30%	Total waste	40%	4%	56%
	Recycling	Composting	Other treatments (Energy recovery,...)																	
Domestic waste	26%	5%	69%																	
Industrial, commercial and institutional waste assimilated to domestic	67%	3%	30%																	
Total waste	40%	4%	56%																	

Other strategies included

COLLECTION

HOW?

- In containers (except bulky waste)
- Lorry type for Rest-fraction and paper/cardboard:
 - In urban area: Side-loading
 - In industrial or business area: Back-loading.

WHO?

- Reusable waste and packaging:
 - By provincial council public company
- Commingled waste, organic waste, paper and cardboard, batteries, bulky waste:
 - Contracting of an external company
- Glass:
 - By non-profit making association

TREATMENT

- ✓ By provincial council public company:
 - Commingled waste or rest-fraction: Incineration plant. Materials and energy valorisation (90%) and controlled dumping (10%)
 - Organic waste: Compost
 - Reusable waste: Reuse and recycling (selling of products)
 - Packaging: Reuse
- ✓ By private company:
 - Paper and cardboard: Recycling
 - Oil: Recycling (biodiesel)
 - Batteries: Recycling
- ✓ By non-profit making association:
 - Glass: Recycling

	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Destination of the UW generated in Bizkaia 2016</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Type and Dimensioning of infrastructures</i></p> <p>*TMB: Mechanical Biological Treatment Plant. *Zabalgardi: Energy Recovery Plant</p>
Management Competences	Provincial Council of Bizkaia
Link to the document/web	http://bizkaia.eus/home2/Archivos/DPT09/Temas/Pdf/PIGRUB%2020%20revision%20(2012).pdf

Name of the law	ES.R.2. PLAN FOR THE PREVENTION AND MANAGEMENT OF WASTE IN THE BASQUE AUTONOMOUS COMMUNITY Plan de prevención y gestión de residuos 2020 de la CAPV
Type of waste regulated	All
Quantitative objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce the total amount of waste generated by 10% for 2020 compared to the amount produced in 2010, • Increase the selective collection and separation of waste to at least 75% for 2020, and set up collection systems for problematic waste streams • Increase the proportion of waste which is prepared for reuse, recycled and recovered to 60% by 2020, resolving the main issues in the Basque Autonomous Community. • Optimise waste disposal by preventing primary waste from being sent to landfill, developing instruments to minimise waste, requiring the principles of proximity and self-sufficiency to be applied when recovering and disposing of waste whenever these actions can be carried out under equivalent conditions, and minimising the impact of existing landfills. • Improve information and transparency concerning waste; simplify and streamline administrative procedures as far as waste regulations allow, and boost the green market and the creation of jobs by developing and implementing this Plan

Other strategies included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • this Plan for the Prevention and Management of Waste in the Basque Autonomous Community 2020 outlines 5 action programmes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Programme for Prevention — Programme for Selective Collection and Separation — Programme for Preparation for reuse, Recycling and Recovery — Programme for Optimising Disposal — Programme for Exemplary Behaviour of Authorities and Good Governance <p>Each action programme outlines various measures which are designed to improve the situation of specific waste streams</p>
Management Competences	<p>With regards to municipal waste, the Environmental Agency of the Basque Autonomous Community (the Basque Government’s Department of Environment and Regional Policy) shall be responsible for the following, in accordance with Law 3/1998 of 27 February on General Environmental Protection:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> — creating a planning framework for municipal waste management, — authorising, inspecting and sanctioning the Integrated Management Systems outlined in Law 11/1997 of 24 April concerning Packaging and Packaging Waste. <p>Meanwhile, the powers invested in the regional authorities of the Basque Provinces (the Provincial Councils) with regards to municipal waste are as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Planning municipal waste management in each Basque province through the relevant Provincial Council plans. — Coordinating municipal activities in each Basque province in order to guarantee the comprehensive provision of services related to waste. — Boosting supra-municipal infrastructures for waste management. <p>The Waste Coordination Body of the Basque Autonomous Community (OCRU), which comprises representatives from the Basque Government’s Department of Environment and the three Provincial Councils, has been set up to coordinate this jurisdiction. <u>Unless stated otherwise, all the measures advocated in this Plan with regards to domestic and commercial waste shall therefore be promoted from the perspective of the OCRU framework, and their inclusion in the respective Provincial Council waste plans shall also be encouraged when these are up for review.</u></p>
Link to the document	http://www.ingurumena.ejgv.euskadi.eus/contenidos/plan/plan_residuos_2020/es_plan/adjuntos/DocuCompletoCAS_%20Plan_RESIDUOS_2020+Anexos.pdf

iii. Local legislation

Name of the law	ES.L.1.Ordinance regulating the management of urban solid waste
Type of waste regulated	Domestic waste Waste of household-type activities Waste from cleaning public spaces

	Miscellaneous household waste Construction and home repair waste Kitchen and restaurants waste that do not come directly from health care.
Quantitative objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There's no quantitative objective.
Other strategies included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The deposit of the selectable collection materials in a non-separative manner is prohibited.
Management Competences	The waste management competence is of the commonwealth of Txorierra
Link to the document/web	http://www.e-txorierra.com/es-ES/Servicios/Residuos/Ordenanzas%20Residuos/02_Ordenanza_RSU.pdf

Name of the law	ES.L.2.Ordinance regulating the management of waste in industrial estates, business and technology parks
Type of waste regulated	Industrial waste assimilated to domestic waste
Quantitative objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There's no quantitative objective.
Other strategies included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The deposit of the selectable collection materials in a non-separative manner is prohibited.
Management Competences	The waste management competence is of the commonwealth of Txorierra
Link to the document/web	http://www.e-txorierra.com/es-ES/Servicios/Residuos/Ordenanzas%20Residuos/01_Ordenanza_industrial.pdf

Name of the law	ES.L.3.Fiscal Ordinance. Rate for provision of waste collection service.
Type of waste regulated	Domestic waste, commercial and industrial waste assimilated to domestic waste
Quantitative objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There is no quantitative objective.

Other strategies included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No PAYT, no incentives. 																																																																																									
	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Section</th> <th>Type</th> <th>First</th> <th>Second</th> <th>Third and rest</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>House</td> <td>24,40 €</td> <td>22,40 €</td> <td>20,30 €</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Shops, food, catering, drinks</td> <td>92,20 €</td> <td>84,40 €</td> <td>76,80 €</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Trade and commerce in general and offices, clinics and the like professionals</td> <td>57,00 €</td> <td>52,20 €</td> <td>47,60 €</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Banking Entities</td> <td>57,00 €</td> <td>52,20 €</td> <td>47,60 €</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="5"><i>The rate of sections 2, 3 and 4 will increase depending on the surface of the establishment</i></td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Industries, workshops and factories of all kinds workers:</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Occupying up to 6 workers</td> <td>68,39 €</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>From 7 to 20 workers</td> <td>181,54 €</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>From 21 to 50 workers</td> <td>362,96 €</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>From 51 to 100 workers</td> <td>562,13 €</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>From 101 to 200 workers</td> <td>1.009,83 €</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>From 201 to 400 workers</td> <td>1.193,87 €</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="5"><i>For every 200 workers or fraction exceeding the first 400, satisfy the increased rate above 25% non-cumulative.</i></td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Communities of garages:</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Up to 500 m2</td> <td>30,00 €</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>More than 500 m2</td> <td>50,00 €</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="5"><i>For every 500 m2 or fraction exceeding the first 1,000 m2, plus the rate of the first 1,000 m2, 25€ non-cumulative</i></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Section	Type	First	Second	Third and rest	1	House	24,40 €	22,40 €	20,30 €	2	Shops, food, catering, drinks	92,20 €	84,40 €	76,80 €	3	Trade and commerce in general and offices, clinics and the like professionals	57,00 €	52,20 €	47,60 €	4	Banking Entities	57,00 €	52,20 €	47,60 €	<i>The rate of sections 2, 3 and 4 will increase depending on the surface of the establishment</i>					5	Industries, workshops and factories of all kinds workers:					Occupying up to 6 workers	68,39 €				From 7 to 20 workers	181,54 €				From 21 to 50 workers	362,96 €				From 51 to 100 workers	562,13 €				From 101 to 200 workers	1.009,83 €				From 201 to 400 workers	1.193,87 €			<i>For every 200 workers or fraction exceeding the first 400, satisfy the increased rate above 25% non-cumulative.</i>					6	Communities of garages:					Up to 500 m2	30,00 €				More than 500 m2	50,00 €			<i>For every 500 m2 or fraction exceeding the first 1,000 m2, plus the rate of the first 1,000 m2, 25€ non-cumulative</i>			
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Link to the document/web	http://www.zamudiokoudala.net/es-ES/Ayuntamiento/Ordenanzas-Reglamentos/Ordenanzas%20fiscales/ord_fiscal_07_anexo_1_2014.pdf																																																																																									

iv. Other

Taxes

Name of the law	<p>ES.O.1. Royal Legislative Decree 2/2004 of 5 March, approving the revised text of the Law Regulating Local Tax Authorities</p> <p>Law 8/1989 of 13 April on Public taxes and Prices (LTPP)</p> <p>Law 58/2003 of 17 December on General Tax (LGT)</p> <p>Real Decreto Legislativo 2/2004, de 5 de marzo, por el que se aprueba el texto refundido de la Ley Reguladora de las Haciendas Locales</p> <p>Ley 8/1989, de 13 de abril, de Tasas y Precios Públicos (LTPP)</p> <p>Ley 58/2003, de 17 de diciembre, General Tributaria (LGT)</p>
Type of waste regulated	All
Quantitative objectives	-

<p>Other strategies included</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LTPP Local authorities can establish taxes for the provision of public services of local competences which particularly benefit taxpayers. Among these services is identified the collection, treatment and disposal of urban solid waste. • LGT Tributes, besides being means to obtain the resources necessary to sustain public expenditure, may serve as instruments of general economic policy and address the consecution of the principles and purposes contained in the Constitution. • LRHL States that the amount of the taxes for the provision of a service may not exceed its cost. • LRHL recognizes these types of taxes as valid: "The tax quota will consist on: a) the resulting amount of applying a tariff, b) a fixed amount designated for that purpose, c) the amount resulting from the joint application of both procedures. • Neither LTPP nor LRHL say anything about the determination of the tax base. • LGT establishing the following options regarding the tax base: direct estimation, singular objective estimation and indirect estimation, the last one only should be considered if it is impossible to determine the taxable base by either of the other two procedures.
<p>Management Competences</p>	<p>Law 7/1985, of 2 April, Regulating Local Rules, provides in Article 25.2 that the collection service and treatment of urban waste is a non waived function of the City Council. Therefore, it is one of the cases where the City Council can set taxes, as it is a mandatory reception service that only the council can provide.</p>
<p>Link to the document</p>	<p>https://www.boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-2004-4214 https://www.boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-1989-8508 https://www.boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-2003-23186</p>

Food wastage

<p>Name of the law</p>	<p>ES.O.2. Spanish Strategy “More Food Less Waste”. Program to reduce food loss and waste and maximise the value of discarded food Regulation on the Use of the Spanish Strategy “More Food Less Waste” logo</p>
<p>Type of waste regulated</p>	<p>Food waste</p>
<p>Quantitative objectives</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • -

<p>Other key strategies included</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Studies to understand the what, how, where and why of food loss and waste. Knowing at what stage and processes waste occurs in the value chain, its quantification and value, its economic, social, nutritional and environmental impact, and how food waste is currently recycled or re-used. • Measuring the attitudes, perception, practices and behaviour of companies and citizens in terms of prevention, re-use and recycling of food waste and assessing the real impact of measures taken by the authority, both by sector and region. • Drawing up and distributing best practice guides between farmers, companies and operators in the chain, that improve knowledge of existing problems and promote the adoption of corrective measures. • Identifying, in partnership with agents on the food chain, the regulatory hurdles that can limit the reduction, re-use or recycling of food waste. • Encouraging and cooperating in the definition of the commitments that companies, organisations and associations from different links of the food chain voluntarily comply with making progress by reducing food waste. Contributing to the development and compliance of said agreements. • Contributing to maximising the redistribution of food waste, promoting partnerships with food banks and other bodies. • Boosting direct relations between producers and consumers, shortening the food supply chains, as a means of contributing to the reduction of food waste and loss. • Encouraging the development and application of audits within companies, aimed at assessing the efficient management of food waste and loss, and identifying areas for improvement. <p>USE OF THE LOGO</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To cede use of the Spanish Strategy “More Food Less Waste” Logo, in particular those stakeholders related with the food waste and follow the acceptance of the commitments detailed in this regulation.
<p>Management Competences</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Within the framework of innovation policies for the food industry, projects will be promoted to improve the efficient use of product
<p>Link to the document/web</p>	<p>goo.gl/HCJT7f Use of the Logo goo.gl/jATH3h</p>

Green Public Procurement

<p>Name of the law</p>	<p>ES.O.3. Order PRE/116/2008 the Agreement of the Council of Ministers is published, approving the Green Public Procurement Plan of the General State Administration, its Government Agencies and the Managing Body of Social Security.</p>
<p>Type of waste regulated</p>	<p>Public Procurement</p>

Quantitative objectives	Implementation of good practices that respect the environment in Public Procurement. It is, ultimately, a Plan that aims to respond to community objectives in accordance with recommendations of the European Commission; be a complement and serve as support for the implementation of state policies for the defense of the environment and climate, as well as savings and energy efficiency.
Other strategies included	This Plan also establishes the conditions under which the procurement authorities might introduce environmental and social requirements in the different stages of public procurement, establishing objectives aimed at incorporating environmental considerations in order to acquire and contact a series of specific products, services and works, which are considered priorities by the European Commission
Management Competences	
Link to the document	https://www.boe.es/buscar/doc.php?id=BOE-A-2008-1631

Name of the law	ES.O.4. Environmental Framework Program 2020
Type of waste regulated	Public Procurement
Quantitative objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -
Other key strategies included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Proposes a qualitative jump in environmental policy, associating the environment with economic and social prosperity through the development of a competitive, green and innovative economy that incorporates principles of efficiency in the consumption of resources and low carbon emissions.
Management Competences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Department of Environment and Territorial Policy, through the Public Society IHOBÉ, offers tools and support to the Basque Country Administrations in the introduction of the environmental perspective in hiring to respond to their political obligations.
Link to the document/web	http://www.ihobe.eus/Publicaciones/Ficha.aspx?IdMenu=750e07f4-11a4-40da-840c-0590b91bc032&Cod=b34b0641-45b2-4b5a-9870-469079626014&Idioma=es-ES

c. Cascais

i. National legislation

Name of the law	P.N.1. Law Decree nº 178/2006 of September 5th – Approves the general regime for waste management by internal juridical order for the Directive nº 2006/12/CE of the European Parliament and Council of April 5th and the Directive nº 91/689/CEE of December 12th of the EU Council
Type of waste regulated	Establishes the general regime of LER classified waste of the European Waste List
Quantitative objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> According to the waste management and prevention are defined the following goals for 2020: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - An increase of at least 50% in selective waste production including paper, plastic, glass and metal, wood and urban biodegradable waste. - An increase of at least 70% of waste weight for reuse, recycling and other valorisation form, including filling operation that use waste as substitute for other materials, construction and non dangerous waste, excluding natural materials in the 17 05 04 category of the LER classified waste of the European Waste List.
Other key strategies included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establishes the general regime applicable to waste prevention, production and management, namely the principles of responsibility for the management attributed to the municipality up to the maximum of 1100 daily litters per producer. Defines the waste management priorities: prevention and reduction, preparation for reusing, recycling and other types of valorisation. Introduces the mandatory separation of waste at the source for producers as a way to increase valorisation per flux Establishes the responsibility principle to reach the principles and objectives in the adoption of preventive behaviours in waste production and recycling or valorisation Define annual waste tax regarding its quantity and final destination to compensate administrative costs, incentivise reduction of waste production and overall sector improvements.
Management Competences	It is the competence of the National Waste Authority (ANR) to insure the goals and target reach according to calculation methods defined by the EU
Link to the document/web	https://dre.pt/application/file/539951

Name of the law	P.N.2. Law Decree nº 194/2009 of August 20th – Establishes the juridic regime of municipal services for water, sewage water and waste services
Type of waste regulated	

Quantitative objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No, generic mention for the reduction mentioned as environmental contribution
Other key strategies included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Allows municipalities to manage urban waste Establishes different management models, namely service delegation for local private sector (municipality owned) Establishes the norms for service accessibility Defines rights and obligations for users and service providers Introduces a mandatory service regulation for services providers Defines general criteria for tariff calculation Defines the regulatory entity and its role of competences
Management Competences	Establishes a general method to define competences of management entities, service owners and regulatory entity.
Link to the document/web	https://dre.pt/application/file/488182

ii. Regional legislation

No legislation identified

iii. Local legislation

Name of the law	P.L.1.Urban Waste Service Regulation
Type of waste regulated	Urban Waste
Quantitative objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Undefined, overall reduction mentioned as environmental contribution
Other strategies included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establishes the urban waste management principles for Cascais by the Municipality (Town Hall) and the management entity (EMAC). Defines the rights and duties of the management entity and users in service within the deposit, collection and transportation of selective and undifferentiated waste. Defines the deposit system by establishing different types of bins for selective and undifferentiated collection Establishes the tariff and service invoice for fixed and variable tariff for domestic and non domestic users Defines the methodology to apply variable tariff regarding water consumption index as an indicator for waste production
Management Competences	Provides competences to the Municipality of Cascais as service owner and EMAC as management entity to manage waste in the municipality
Link to the document/web	http://www.cascaisambiente.pt/sites/cascaisambiente/files/anexos/regulamento_de_servico_de_gestao_de_residuos_urbanos.pdf

d. Seveso

i. National legislation

Name of the law	IT.N.1. Testo unico ambientale (Environmental Framework regulation) – D.Lgs. 152/2006 and subsequent modifications
Type of waste regulated	Municipal waste, industrial waste, Remediation
Quantitative objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 65% separate collection to be achieved by every single municipality by 31st December 2012. This deadline has not been postponed so far so it is still valid. • European target of 50% recycling of at least paper, metals, plastic and glass.
Other key strategies included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specific sections on waste packaging and particular categories of waste streams. • Changes the previous regulation on <u>waste tax</u> clarifying that it has to be variable and related to the quantity of waste generated (PAYT principle). • <u>Biowaste</u> is addressed as a key waste stream but without a specific target or obligation of the introduction of its collection. • Mandates the Environmental Ministry to prepare a national Waste Prevention Plan (approved on 7th Oct 2013, link : targets 5% waste reduction 2010/2010 considering also GDP and family expenditure indicators) and to report every two years on its implementation
Management Competences	Competences are indicated in art. 195 (State) general guidelines and strategies, 196 (Regions): regional waste management plans, 197 (Provinces): controls, 198 (Municipalities): management of MSW
Link to the document/web	Actualized version: http://www.ambientediritto.it/home/legislazione/decreto-legislativo-3-aprile-2006-n-152-parte-4 Art.177-266.

ii. Regional legislation

Name of the law	IT.R.1. Programma Regionale di Gestione dei Rifiuti (PRGR, Regional Waste Management Plan) 2014-2020
Type of waste regulated	Municipal and Industrial
Quantitative objectives	<p>Main quantitative targets by 2020:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipal waste production: innovative decoupling target. 8% decrease with respect to the variation of household spending in 2020 compared to 2011 • Average separate collection rate of 67% in the whole Region, and 65% to be achieved by each Municipality • Adoption of a "standard model" for separate collection (at least for the main waste fractions), based on door to door, in 80% of municipalities

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Achievement of 60 kg / (capita * year) of OFMSW (Organic Fraction of Municipal Solid Waste) collection • 65% material recovery (final recycling including street sweeping) • Reuse and recycling of waste (at least domestic paper, metal, plastic and glass) at least of 55% in terms of weight (EU target) • Total waste recovery, as material or energy: at least 80% • Bring to zero the residual municipal waste landfilled • 90% recycling of the total quantity of waste produced by incineration, and 30% of fly ashes • Spread of the PAYT systems for the urban waste management: 10% of municipalities by 2015; 20% of the municipalities by 2020
<p>Other strategies included</p>	<p>The priorities and objectives contained in the PRGR are in line with the hierarchy of the Directive 2008/98/EU.</p> <p>PRGR has a long list of strategic objectives regarding all the priorities from the EU hierarchy. Regarding the specific topics of food-waste, prevention and PAYT/TAX, the following can be highlighted.</p> <p><u>Prevention</u>: an Action Plan for Waste Reduction (ref. art. 199 comma 3 letter r, D. Lgs. 152/2006), is included in PRGR.</p> <p>Among them, the main flow of urban waste on which to focus is food waste. The main actions of the prevention plan focus on:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Bulk sale without packaging of food 2. Food donation in supermarkets with social destination 3. Home composting 4. Washable diapers 5. Bulky recovery ("reuse Days") 6. Farm delivery 7. Communications to users of products with less packaging at large retailers 8. Short chain (from producers to consumers) 9. Paper consumption reduction at work 10. Reduction of commercial advertisements distributed to private houses 11. Promotion of the use of tap water <p>The <u>PAYT system</u> is another important instrument to prevent the waste production. In fact the citizen tends, besides to better perform the separate collection, to produce less waste. The objective of the PRGR is to extend the use of PAYT system at least in 20% of Lombardy municipalities by 2020, spreading out the good practices already existing.</p> <p>Furthermore, Lombardy Region encourages the reuse of material, though the spread of "reuse centers", as places where citizens can put used goods and objects to be reused before becoming waste (ref. art. 180-bis, D.lgs 152/06)..</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Another important <u>financial instrument</u> that can contribute to the waste reduction is the "eco-tax", i.e. the tax linked to the amount of waste landfilled based on several parameters of efficiency.
<p>Management Competences</p>	<p>Lombardy Region has the management competences for the achievement of the PRGR objectives, with the aid of the Regional Agencies (e.g. ARPA, ASL,</p>

	etc.). Provinces and Municipalities must fulfil the targets, through local regulations and specific actions.
Link to the document/web	http://www.reti.regione.lombardia.it/cs/Satellite?c=Redazionale_P&childpage name=DG_Reti%2FDetail&cid=1213595689750&pagename=DG_RSSWrapper or https://www.cartografia.regione.lombardia.it/sivas/

iii. Local legislation

Name of the law	IT.L.1.Regolamento di igiene urbana (Municipal Waste Management Regulation). Regolamento TARES (waste tax regulation)
Type of waste regulated	Municipal solid waste and similar to municipal waste
Quantitative objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No target is included in the regulations. The municipality needs to comply with the national target (65% of separate collection) but it already reached 75%.
Other strategies included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The municipal waste management regulation defines the fundamentals and principles of the waste collection model: door to door, frequencies access to the municipal recycling centre etc. Every contractor, be it the same municipal company or others in case of a tender, shall comply to this. The TARES regulation, currently taxing waste producers on the basis of the surface of the household and the number of inhabitants, is going to be updated during W4T to allow the application of a direct PAYT system in Seveso, combined with the already existing iBag (blue bags with RFID transponder) system. Some reductions of the tax are applied to some categories, like home composting etc.
Management Competences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The municipality defines the waste collection model and signs a service contract , currently with the municipal company GELSIA. The choice of the final destination for recycling / disposal is done by the municipality with separate tenders. The municipality currently collects waste tax directly and manages all the related process. It also deliver blue RFID bags (iBags) for residual waste and constantly updates the database of households / waste producers.
Link to the document/web	<p><u>Municipal waste management regulation</u>: not available on line, old document to be revised soon.</p> <p><u>Waste tax regulation</u>: http://www.comune.seveso.mi.it/allegati/2191%5Edelibera%20Tares%20tariffa%20e%20regolamento%20.pdf</p>

iv. Other

Food wastage

IT.O.1. In Italy the most innovative legislation about food waste is the very recent update ([Legge 19 agosto 2016 n.166](#)) of the “Good Samaritan law”. It is an advanced law on food donation updating a previous one of 2003; it basically eases donation from retailers to charities and NGO, making more complicated the disposal of food waste and clarifying the expiry date issue.

PAYT/taxs

IT.O.2. About **PAYT**, art. 238 of D.Lgs. 152/06 states that waste tax is related to the quantity and quality of waste generated. It also clearly specifies that waste tax is composed of a fixed part covering the essential part of waste management costs, and a variable part to be linked to the generation. Currently it is still missing a specific bylaw specifying the technical criteria to calculate the fixed and variable part, so municipalities are acting individually having some older guidelines such as decree 158/99.

Incentives: National law 28 dicembre 2015, n. 221 ([link](#)) introduced a modulation scheme for the application of the landfill tax (a national tax to be applied by the Regions to the amount of waste landfilled). This new scheme introduces a surcharge of 20% for municipalities not reaching the separate collection target (65%), and a discount variable from 30% to 70% for those overpassing it with different levels.

Plastic bags

IT.O.3. Since 2008, with a specific modification to the Environmental Framework Law 152/06 (Art 182ter) in Italy food waste collection is possible only with certified compostable bags (or without bag).

About shoppers, ([link](#)) the first law prohibiting the use of non-biodegradable plastic bags for shopping was law 27th December 2006, n. 296, comma 1130, art. 1. After a standstill situation this law was enforced with some clarifications and the introduction of fines for reselling polyethylene bags under a certain thickness. Now shoppers can only compostable and compliant to the standard UNI 13432:2002.

ICT

IT.O.4. In Italy a long term legislation regulating the traceability and management of waste data have been in place. Every waste producer, or treatment plant, has to fill informatically some sheets of data (MUD, Modello Unico di Dichiarazione ambientale) that are stored and managed basically by the Enviromental Agencies at a national and Regional level allowing statistics and waste planning. Data of MUD and, more recently, of SISTRI, are mostly referring to industrial waste; however, there is also a section dedicated to municipal waste.

Besides MUD / SISTRI, Regions manage autonomously the collection and validation of municipal waste data (asking more information than the basic one related to MUD) from the Municipalities. Almost all of them now use ICT and webtools for gathering data, and some Regions (9 out of 20) are also participating to an interregional web platform (O.R.SO) that allows cross validation with advanced features.

e. Halandri

i. National legislation

Name of the law	GR.N.1. National Waste Management Plan – NWMP (2015) . Law No4042/2012 (harmonization with EC directives 2008/99, 2008/98)
Type of waste regulated	<p>Law No 4042:</p> <p>generic waste, hazardous waste, oil waste, biowaste. Characterization of specific waste types is made according to European Waste Catalogue (2000/532/EE directive).</p> <p>NWMP:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Urban waste <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.1 Solid municipal waste 1.2 Household electrical electronic waste 1.3 Small batteries 1.4 Municipal sludge 2. Industrial and other processes waste <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2.1 Industrial waste 2.2 Common goods utilities infrastructure waste 2.3 Oil waste 2.4 Vehicle and industrial type batteries 2.5 End-of-life vehicles 2.6 Used vehicle tyres 2.7 Industrial electric electronic waste 2.8 Health units waste 3. Construction and demolition waste <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3.1 Non hazardous CDW 3.2 Hazardous CDW (contain asbestos) 4. Agricultural and livestock waste
Quantitative objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Separation at the source of 40% of the total weight of biodegradable household waste by 2020 • Separation at the source of 65% of glass, metal and plastic by 2020 • Disposal to landfills is to be reduced to less than 30% of the total amount of Solid Municipal Waste by 2020 • Preparation of reuse, recycling and recovery of 70% of Construction and Demolition waste by 2020 • At least 10% of the total amount of biowaste will be collected separately by 2020 • Recovery of 60% of packaging waste and recycling between 55% and 80% • Reuse, recovery and recycling of 70% of CDW by 2020 • 35% reduction of Biodegradables and Paper/cardboard which are disposed at landfills by 2020 • The cost of waste management is attributed to the waste producer and/or the previous owners of waste.

Other key strategies included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A <u>special tax</u> is legislated for waste management. The tax is regulated by the municipalities. The amount is imposed on inhabitants of the municipality, and the amount to be paid is proportionate to the surface of the building. The multiplier is set by the Municipality each year and is the same for everyone. The tax is collected by the Public Power Corporation through the electricity bill and then it is transferred to the Municipality's account. • Energy recovery by solutions such as biogas recovery from landfills, biogas production by anaerobic digestion, biodiesel production by oil waste • The waste pyramid hierarchy is adopted (prevention > reuse > recycle > energy recovery > disposal)
Management Competences	<p>Is regulated by Ministry of Environment & Energy. The Ministry is to prepare countrywide Waste Management Plans for various recycling streams and specific waste streams. Regional authorities are to prepare Regional Waste Management Plans. The Ministry is to prepare Waste Prevention Programs.</p> <p>http://www.ypeka.gr/Default.aspx?tabid=238&language=en</p>
Link to the document/web	<p>http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=8rKEKVFO8G0%3d&tabid=238&language=el-GR</p>

ii. Regional legislation

Name of the law	GR.R.1.Solid Waste Management Plan for the Attica Region (The Plan has been voted in 2006, the current version is the Second Revision which has been active since August 2015)
Type of waste regulated	Urban solid waste, Non-hazardous industrial waste, other non-hazardous waste
Quantitative objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction of biodegradable municipal waste which ends up in landfills by 2020 to 35% of the amount produced at 1995. • Other quantitative objectives are outdated. A new revision is about to be voted in the following weeks.
Other strategies included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Landfill diversion, biowaste valorization for thermal energy • Other strategies are outdated. A new revision is about to be voted in the following weeks.
Management Competences	It is put together and voted by the regional council of Attica. Is to be implemented by Solid Waste Management Agency for the Attica Region. Municipalities in the Attica Region must prepare Local Waste Management Plans - www.edsna.gr
Link to the document/web	http://www.patt.gov.gr/site/attachments/3496_PESDA%20ATTIKHS_FINAL.pdf

iii. Local legislation

Name of the law	GR.L.1.Local Waste Management Plan, Municipality of Chalandri (2015)																																
Type of waste regulated	Σύμμεικτα, ανακυκλώσιμα (ενιαίο ρεύμα ανακύκλωσης), κίτρινος κάδος (χαρτί), καφέ κάδος (οργανικά)																																
Quantitative objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quantity (t/y), Preselection of materials: <table data-bbox="518 465 1295 763"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th></th> <th><u>household</u></th> <th><u>mechanical</u></th> </tr> <tr> <th>year</th> <th><u>mixed waste</u></th> <th><u>composting</u></th> <th><u>composting</u></th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td><u>2015</u></td> <td>33030</td> <td>500</td> <td>0</td> </tr> <tr> <td><u>2020</u></td> <td>16570</td> <td>1490</td> <td>1100</td> </tr> <tr> <th></th> <th><u>packaging</u></th> <th></th> <th></th> </tr> <tr> <th>year</th> <th><u>paper</u></th> <th><u>paper</u></th> <th><u>plastic</u></th> </tr> <tr> <td><u>2015</u></td> <td>1110</td> <td>890</td> <td>960</td> </tr> <tr> <td><u>2020</u></td> <td>3330</td> <td>2660</td> <td>2890</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> 50% reduction of green bins (mixed waste) by 2020, progressive replacement by a network of yellow (paper), brown (organic, mainly household kitchen waste) and blue (plastic, metal, glass). 			<u>household</u>	<u>mechanical</u>	year	<u>mixed waste</u>	<u>composting</u>	<u>composting</u>	<u>2015</u>	33030	500	0	<u>2020</u>	16570	1490	1100		<u>packaging</u>			year	<u>paper</u>	<u>paper</u>	<u>plastic</u>	<u>2015</u>	1110	890	960	<u>2020</u>	3330	2660	2890
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<u>2015</u>	1110	890	960																														
<u>2020</u>	3330	2660	2890																														
Other strategies included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A pilot program for <u>household composting</u> is being implemented as of November 2016. The Municipality has procured 340 compost bins (280 lt capacity) for kitchen biowaste and pruning. The quality and quantity of the product will be monitored. The municipality is to draw a public campaign addressed to citizens to inform and raise awareness regarding recycling and waste management. Waste4Think pilot will be used to evaluate the various possible solutions regarding biowaste valorization, as well as optimal ways of separation and collection at the source. 																																
Management Competences	Is to be implemented by Municipality of Chalandri - Environment and Waste Management Agency																																
Link to the document/web	http://www.halandri.gr/inst/halandri/gallery/2015/ΓΙΑ ΔΗΜΟΤΕΣ/ΠΕΡΙΒΑΛΛΟΝ ΚΑΘΑΡΙΟΤΗΤΑ/ΤοΔ (Διαχείριση αποβλήτων) 11.6.2015.pdf																																

f. Other innovative legislation (other countries)

i. Food waste/Food wastage

INN.1. Scottish Regulations on commercial food waste collection

The [Waste \(Scotland\) Regulations 2012](#) require that all waste producers (excluding householders) take reasonable steps to present key dry recyclables such as glass, metals, plastics, paper and card (including cardboard) for separate collection.

The regulations also require some food businesses to segregate food waste for separate collection:

- Food businesses (except in rural areas) which produce over 50 kg of food waste per week to present that food waste for separate collection from 1 January 2014.
- Food businesses (except in rural areas) which produce over 5 kg of food waste per week to present that food waste for separate collection from 1 January 2016

Fails without reasonable excuse to comply with the duties imposed above may be liable to:

- on summary conviction, to a fine of up to £10,000
- on conviction on indictment, to an unlimited fine

Other rules:

- A ban on any metal, plastic, glass, paper, card and food collected separately for recycling from going to incineration or landfill from 1 January 2014.
- A ban on biodegradable municipal waste going to landfill from 1 January 2021.

More info: <https://www.sepa.org.uk/regulations/waste/recycling-including-food-waste/>

INN.2. French regulation on supermarkets food wastage and donation

On January 13, 2016, France became the first country in the world to pass a law requiring supermarkets to donate food that is approaching its expiration date instead of throwing it away. The regulation that applies to supermarkets over 4,000 square feet requires stores to sign donation contracts with local food banks.

The law also makes it illegal for stores to pour bleach or water over nearly expired food, or store it inside locked warehouses until it is picked up by garbage trucks. These extreme measures are often undertaken by supermarkets to prevent the hungry from foraging through the trash bins.

Also, manufacturers producing perishable private label products like yogurt or milk for supermarkets, are now allowed to donate excess goods directly to the food banks. Though they have always been able to do that, the current process is long and complicated, making it difficult for manufacturers to give away the food in a timely manner.

The law also requires the charities receiving the donations to store the food in a hygienic manner and, more importantly, give it out with 'dignity.' This means that they should distribute it to people in need from a food bank or center where they can interact with them, instead of just handing it out on the streets.

The law will also introduce an education programme about food waste in schools and businesses. It follows a measure in February to remove the best-before dates on fresh foods.

The measures are part of wider drive to halve the amount of food waste in France by 2025

More info:

<https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/affichTexte.do?cidTexte=JORFTEXT000032036289&categorieLien=id>

ii. Plastic bags

INN.3. Ban on plastic bags in France

Plastic bags are banned in France from July 1 2016. This measure will concern supermarkets, pharmacies, bakeries, petrol stations, covered and open-air markets.

The law says that the ban covers bags with a capacity “smaller than 10 litres and with a thickness less than 50 microns” – otherwise known as the “common plastic bag”.

Bags thicker than 50 microns will still be allowed on the basis they are reusable.

The ban on plastic bags will come into effect in two stages: on July 1, 2016 for “lightweight” shopping bags and January 1, 2017 for packaging bags for fruit and vegetables.

The law also currently plans to authorise “domestically compostable bags made in full or in part from bio-sourced materials,” which should replace plastic fruit and vegetable packaging in January 2017.

Other rules:

France has become the first country in the world to ban plastic plates, cups and utensils, this will go into effect in 2020. Exceptions will be allowed for items made of compostable, biosourced materials.

More info: [Energy Transition for Green Growth Act](#)

B. FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS (THIS APPENDIX CONTAINS A CONFIDENTIAL PART NOT INCLUDED IN THIS DELIVERABLE)

B1 TARGET GROUP IDENTIFICATION PER PILOT SITE

Target groups	Direct users (DG, CG, IG, NG, FWG, NRG, C, EC, S, ZWE)	Policy makers and Municipalities (WMPB)	Waste managers (WCO, TPO, WCC)	Stakeholders (FWM, SME)	Scientific community (R)	Civil associations (A)
ZAMUDIO	Citizen, Bizi Zamudio Commerce Association and other commerces who want to take part and Technological Park, Pinagua, Ugaldeguren I, Ugaldeguren II, Ugaldeguren III, Torrelarragoiti Industrial Park Industries (Txorierrri Valley: last five). Schools: Zamudio Public School, Txorierrri Highschool, Vizcaya School and French School.	Diputación Foral Bizkaia, Basque Government and Spain Ministry. Other municipalities like Larrabetzu, Lezama, Derio Sondika, Loiu and Txorierrri Commonwealth.	Treatment plants: Zabalgarbi, Artigas, Beotibar Recycling Plant, Ecovidrio, Refinor, Orkonera treatment plants. Collection companies: Enviser Clean points managers: Garbiker Townhall/commonwealth technicians: Zamudio, Larrabetzu, Lezama, Derio, Sondika, Loiu and Txorierrri.	Technology providers: Contenur, Formato Verde, Plastic Onium, Dorlet, PDC ONGs: Mancommunity Social Services, AUNAR, Danontzat food bank Loiu)	Local universities and technological centers: Deusto University, FDeusto	Neighborhood: Associations: Eguraldi Ona Fest Commission, Lagatzu
CASCAIS	Citizen, Residents associations or condominium from Quinta dos Lombos Sul, services (Quinta dos lombos restaurants and other open to public services located in Quinta dos Lombos and Quinta de São Gonçalo); School of St. Julians, Secondary School of carcavelos, Basic School of Lombos, nº 1 Basic School of Carcavelos,	Cascais próxima (mobility) and Câmara Municipal de Cascais (town hall) ERSAR - national regulatory entity for water and waste services	Tratolixo (treatment)	Sotkon technology provider) Reefood (food kitchen for the needed)	National universities Technical and Sciences Faculty of the New University of Lisbon; Tecnical Institute of the University of Lisbon Faculty of Sciences of the University of Lisbon	Residents associations Residents associations or condominium from Quinta dos Lombos Sul, Services (Quinta dos lombos restaurants and other open to public services located in Quinta dos Lombos and Quinta de São

						Gonçalo); Schools School of St. Julians, Secondary School of carcavelos, Basic School of Lombos, nº 1 Basic School of Carcavelos Sport Association of Quinta dos Lombos
HALANDRI	<p>Municipality of Halandri citizens</p> <p>School community: 16 kindergarten schools 16 primary schools 8 secondary schools 5 high schools 3 technical high schools</p> <p>Commercial enterprises ~200 restaurants ~200 coffee shops</p>	<p>Region of Attica</p> <p>Neighboring Municipalities: Vrillisia, Amarousio, Filothei, Psychikou, Agias Paraskevis, Geraka</p>	<p>Attica Association for Waste Management</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Landfill- Ano Liosia - FYLIS Residual waste (Green bin)- FYLIS • Facility of Mechanical Recycling and Composting Waste (EMAK)- Ano Liosia - EMAK Pruning-Biowaste- (prunings) EMAK • Biogas of Sanitary Landfill - Biogas Energy Ano Liosia S.A. BEAL SA Residual Waste - BEAL SA • Medical Waste Incineration Plant of A.C.M.A.R. (Association of Communities and 	<p>NGOs</p> <p>Companies that can use the generated biomass product as raw material:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TITAN S.A • POLYECO • MEGAECO • MEGABIOGAS 	<p>Universities and research institutes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National Technical University of Athens NTUA, • University of Patras • Institute of Chemical Engineering Sciences (ICE-HT) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local associations • Neighborhood Associations • School associations

			<p>Municipalities in the Attica Region)</p> <p>Medical Waste- Apotefrotiras S.A</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hellenic Recovery Recycling Corporation (HERRCO) Recyclable waste –HERRCO S.A • Material Recovery Facility (MRF) in Koropi, Attica Recyclable waste – WATT S.A • Tires waste – Ecoelastica S.A Tires waste – Ecoelastica S.A • Batteries waste, WEEE – Afis S.A Batteries waste, WEEE – Afis S.A • End of life vehicles (ELV) – OIKANO S.A End of life vehicles (ELV) – OIKANO S.A 			
SEVESO	<p>Public nursery G. Rodari, B. Munari Seveso</p> <p>Private nurseries Scuola Dell'Infanzia Di C.So Marconi, Scuola Dell'Infanzia Parrocchia Beata V. Immacolata, Scuola Dell'Infanzia San Pietro Martire</p> <p>Public schools Primary schools: C. Collodi, E. Toti Comprehensive school (nursery,</p>	<p>Seveso Municipality, Region Lombardy, Other municipalities managed by GELSIA experimenting RFID Bags: Lissone, Cusano Milanino</p>	Gelsia Ambiente Srl	<p>Technology providers: Gelsia Ambiente and its subcontractors</p> <p>Associations organizing Eco-events: A.S.D. Associazione Sportiva, Dilettantistica,</p>	<p>Universities and research institutes: FLA (Lombardy Foundation for Environment)</p>	<p>Local associations: associations organizing eco-events (see stakeholder column), Mum in progress</p> <p>Neighborhood and citizens of neighboring</p>

	<p>primary and secondary): I.C. Via Adua Seveso, I.C. Via De Gasperi/Seveso</p> <p>Secondary schools: I.C. Via De Gasperi/Seveso, Don A. Giussani Seveso, Leonardo Da Vinci Seveso</p> <p>High schools: Istituto P. S. S. C. T. S. L. Milani (touristic and commercial institute)</p> <p>Private schools</p> <p>Primary schools: Scuola Elementare Parificata P.G.Frassati, Scuola Primaria Par. San Pietro Martire</p> <p>Secondary schools: Scuola Secondaria Di 1° Gr. Pier Giorgio Frassati</p> <p>High schools: Liceo Scientifico Pier Giorgio Frassati (scientific liceum)</p> <p>Parishes</p> <p>SS. Gervaso e Protaso, B.V. Immacolata Baruccana, S. Carlo Altopiano, Oratorio Paolo VI Seveso, S. Pietro Martire</p> <p>Retirement home: Casa Di Riposo Padre Giovanni Masciadri</p> <p>Private enterprises: municipal waste generators affected by PAYT</p>			<p>Associazione Comitato Genitori Istituto Comprensivo De Gasperi (Scholars' parents association), Comitato AmaLO, Croce Bianca, Rete Speranza, ASDC Base 96, Panico Carmela, Carabinieri Cesano</p> <p>Recycling consortia: dry recyclables national consortia (CONAI)</p>	<p>municipalities (Cesano Maderno, Barlassina, Meda, Seregno)</p>
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B2. FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

Requirements for operation and planning IT tools

R1_FR1	To monitor the waste generation
R1_FR1.1	Allow to identify the users to the collection system
R1_FR1.2	Monitor the delivery of waste (control access)
R1_FR1.3	Allow to characterize the waste deposited
R1_FR1.4	Get information about the state of the deposit point and composting plants
R1_FR1.5	Be a fallback solution to publish information in the context broker
R1_NFR1.1	The system must be auditable
R1_FR2	Get information of a collection route
R1_FR2.1	Get the total fuel consumption of a collection route
R1_FR2.2	Estimate the total environmental impact of a collection route
R1_FR2.3	Get the GPS Trace of a collection route
R1_FR2.4	Get the FMS information from the CAN BUS
R1_FR2.5	Get the total weight of waste collected
R1_FR2.6	Get the places where the bin have been collected
R1_FR2.7	Get the time when the bin have been collected
R1_FR2.8	Allow to emit a certification of the work done during the shift
R1_FR3	Allow to report issues
R1_FR3.1	Allow to report the overfill of a container
R1_FR3.2	Allow to report vandalizing of a container
R1_FR3.3	Allow to report incorrect use of a container or bag
R1_FR3.4	Allow to take evidences (photos or videos) of the incidences
R1_FR3.5	Allow to request of specific collections (bulky waste)
R1_FR4	To display the state of the waste collection system
R1_FR4.1	Allow to show the state of the waste collection system
R1_FR4.2	Detect anomalies in the waste generation patterns
R1_FR4.3	Allows to personalize the monitoring system

R1_FR4.4	Allows to create automatic reports in PDF, Excel and CSV
R1_FR4.5	The system must be able to crawl the web to get incidences
R1_FR5	Provide a system to persist the information
R1_FR5.1	Provide a communication channel to the persistence solution
R1_FR5.2	Provide a communication channel to CKAN storage systems
R1_NFR6.1	The communication channel should be secure (un-authorized person should not be able to read a message)
R1_NFR6.2	The communication channel should be reliable (no information can be lost)
R1_NFR6.3	Provide bidirectional communication system
R1_NFR6.3.1	Provide bidirectional communication system between the {back-end, MAWIS and Wintariff} and the sensors
R1_NFR6.3.2	Provide bidirectional communication system between the {back-end, MAWIS and Wintariff} and the truck
R1_NFR6.3.3	The communication system should use the FIWARE platform
R1_FR5.3	Data Transmission to the Server (for MOBA components)
R2_FR1	To manage the waste collection service
R2_FR1.1	To create the routes to follow every vehicle of the fleet
R2_FR1.2	Optimize the route of the fleet
R2_FR2	Provide feedback to drivers
R2_FR2.1	Provide turn-by-turn information to the driver
R2_FR2.2	Provide tips to promote more sustainable driving
R2_FR3	Calculate the taxes to be charge to the citizens (invoicing module)
R2_FR3.1	Be able to calculate taxes following different PAYT schemes
R2_NFR3.1	Fulfilment with the calculation method established by the Municipality Regulation
R2_NFR3.2	Generation of a transparent bills
R3_FR1	To support the long term planning
R3_FR1.1	Provide visual tools to create predictive and explicative models
R3_FR1.2	Provide visuals tools to help in the creation of baselines and what-if scenarios
R3_FR1.3	Perform long term simulations of the waste management system
R3_FR1.4	Allow the optimization of the waste collection for special events
R3_FR1.5	Help in the creation of green procurements

R3_NFR1	Open Source solution
R4_FR1	To foster circular economy opportunities
R4_FR1.1	Provide recommendation to foster circular economy

Requirements for Apps

R5-6-7_FR1	Common functional requirements of the apps
R5-6-7_FR1.1	There are four profiles of users: generator, receptor, public administration, root
R5-6-7_FR1.2	Provide aggregated information to R1_FR4.1
R5-6-7_NFR1.1	The app should be multiplatform
R5_FR1	Coordinate the collection of food for social kitchens to reduce the edible food waste
R5_FR1.2	To characterize the edible food waste (for domestic generators)
R5_FR1.3	Provide suggestion of all the actions that can be done with the food waste
R5_FR1.4	To record the traceability of all the transactions
R5_FR1.5	Analyze the food waste production to give personalized tips for improving the purchase and consumption of food
R6_FR1	To foster local trade, recycling and mutual learning
R6_FR1.1	Provide information about the way to get vouchers
R6_FR1.2	Provide information about where to redeem the vouchers
R6_FR1.3	Provide information about the environmental impact of product and services
R6_FR1.4	Get and send information about the business that have implemented good practices
R6_FR1.5	Provide information about local cooperative actions to prevent the generation of waste
R7_FR1	To foster transparency and citizen participation
R7_FR1.1	Show information about the waste management system
R7_FR1.2	Allow to report incidences from mobile devices (R1_FR3)
R7_FR1.3	Provide information to reduce the footprint
R7_FR1.4	Provide information about the PAYT system implemented
R7_FR1.5	Provide access to the invoices
R7_NFR1.1	Follow the open311 standard

Requirement for educational material and citizen science

R-ICT-SOCIAL	Common NFR of ICT based social actions
R-ICT-SOCIAL_NFR1	Adapted version for each country and education system (except for Eco-design game)
R-ICT-SOCIAL_NFR2	Adapted to the language used and the target groups to be involved
R-ICT-SOCIAL_NFR3	Be enough appealing and easy to use to success within target groups
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR1	To teach on waste management and prevention actions
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR1.1	To teach on waste management and prevention actions
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2	Track players and results
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2.1	Provide a complete log of the use of the tool
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2.2	Register the needed info to calculate the related KPIs
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2.3	Provide final information about the impact of the mistakes of separation at source
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2.4	Detect where the users have had more difficulties
R8_FR1	To teach students in waste management and improving the center management system
R8_FR1.1	To teach students in waste management and improving the center management system
R8_FR1.2	Monitor the effect/impact on the students and the learned concepts/abilities, instruction for teachers evaluation
R8_FR1.3	Propose activities/ideas that later can be implemented and monitored in the center to improve the waste management
R8_FR1.4	Develop mobile games to improve waste management and to promote healthy lifestyle habits
R9_FR1	To teach in the separation at source and related impacts
R9_FR1.1	To teach in the separation at source and related impacts
R10_FR1	To teach in eco-design
R10_FR1.1	To teach in eco-design
R10_FR1.2	Include a selection of key products to be analysed
R11_FR1	To train collection managers and other technicians to optimize the system
R11_FR1.1	To train collection managers and other technicians to optimize the system
R11_FR1.2	Offer different solutions to optimize the system: technical, social, economic, etc.
R12_FR1	Teach about circular economy principles
R12_FR1.1	Teach about circular economy principles
R12_FR1.2	Provide info about the raw materials obtained to be reintroduced in the production chain of other products

R12_FR1.3	Provide info about the specific prevention actions developed for each pilot
R13-14-15_FR1	Facilitate the co-creation of solutions
R13-14-15_FR1.1	Provide a stage editor

Requirement for educational material and citizen science

R17_FR1	To provide information and knowledge to the target groups on the social action in order to change habits and behaviours
R17_FR1.1	Establishment of protocols to assure that the participation is confirmed
R17_FR1.2	Establishment of protocols to monitor the impact of the innovative awareness action
R17_FR1.3	Establishment of subactivities based on innovative awareness methods including the IT solutions
R17_FR1.4	To identify best practices
R17_NFR1	Information and messages adapted to the target groups and effective
R17_NFR2	Acquire/produce adequate and effective communication materials
R17_NFR3	Creation of a work team of educators/trainers (well prepared) and appointment of a coordinator
R17_NFR3.1	Coordination of the action preparation with other departments, entities, etc. that should be involved
R17_FR2	To monitor participation in the different actions
R17_FR2.1	To monitor citizens participating in social campaigns
R17_FR3	To prevent waste generation and to promote recycling among different sectors of the population
R17_FR3.1	To prevent waste generation and to promote recycling among different sectors of the population

Requirements for new treatments

R19_NFR1	Ensuring that the quality of the food waste loaded to the dryer is up to standards (pre-sorted kitchen food waste only).
R19_NFR2	Treatment quantity: up to 150kg/operation cycle
R19_FR1	Monitoring treatment plants (biowaste)
R19_FR1.1	Recording the temperature of the Biowaste Treatment Unit (BTU)
R19_FR1.2	Recording the moisture of the Biowaste Treatment Unit (BTU)
R19_FR1.3	Monitoring of the treatment duration of Biowaste Treatment Unit (BTU)

R19_FR2	Biomass product valorization
R19_FR2.1	Quantity of biomass product loaded to bioreactor at Megabiogas plant in Megara (kg/day)
R19_FR2.2	Monitoring the quantity of biofuel produced in Megabiogas (m3 /day)
R19_FR2.3	Monitoring the cost per collection route when collection truck runs with CNG (biofuel) (€/route)
R19_FR2.4	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of the outputs
R20_FR1	To treat the food waste and nappies
R20_FR1.1	Allow you to temporarily store the disposable nappies, kitchen waste and/or expired food product (EFP)s
R20_FR1.2	Allow you to co-treat disposable nappies, EFP and /or kitchen waste in the Waste Treatment Unit (WTU)
R20_FR1.3	Allow you to compost the WTU sludge
R20_FR2	Monitoring treatment plants (nappies and biowaste)
R20_FR2.1	Monitor and control the temperature of the Waste Treatment Unit (WTU)
R20_FR2.2	Monitor and control the pressure of the Waste Treatment Unit (WTU)
R20_FR2.3	Monitor the volume and composition of produced biogas in the WTU per kg of nappies and EFP fed in the system
R20_FR2.4	Monitor the amount and quality of compost produced per kg of nappies and EFP treated in the WTU

C. USE CASES (THIS APPENDIX CONTAINS A CONFIDENTIAL PART NOT INCLUDED IN THIS DELIVERABLE)

Summary of the Use Cases

		Target Group																	
		Social Groups of Interest					Generators							Managers					
		C	S	SME	R	A	EC	DG	NRG	CG	IG	FWG	NG	WCO	WCC	TPO	FWM	ZWE	WMPB
R1 Operation and management module	R1_FR1																		
	R1_FR1.1				C3			Z1, S1, S2, S3, C1	Z1	Z2, S3	Z3, S3	A2	Z1	S2	S3, C1				S1, S2, S3
	R1_FR1.2				C13			Z1	Z1	Z2	Z3			C1	C1				
	R1_FR1.3				C13							A2		Z4	C6			Z6, Z7	
	R1_FR1.4				C4									Z1, Z2, Z3, Z4, Z5, C2	C2			Z7	
	R1_FR1.5													Z4	Z4				
	R1_FR2																		
	R1_FR2.1				C5									C5, C6, C7	C5, C6, C7				
	R1_FR2.2				C5, C7									C5, C6, C7, C12	C5, C6, C7, C12				
	R1_FR2.3				C7			C10	C10	C10	C10	C10		Z4	C6, C8				
	R1_FR2.4													C7	C7				
	R1_FR2.5				C4			C4	C4	C4	C4	C4		Z4, C4, C8	C4, C8				Z4, C4, C8
	R1_FR2.6				C8									Z4, C3, C6, C8	C3, C6, C8				
	R1_FR2.7				C8									Z4, C3, C6, C8	C3, C6, C8				
	R1_FR2.8				C8									Z4, C8	C8				

R2 Collection module	R1_FR3																	
	R1_FR3.1	A6		C4		C4	C4	C4	C4	C4		Z4, C8	C2, C8					
	R1_FR3.2	A6										Z4, C8	C8					
	R1_FR3.3					S4, S5						Z4, S4, S5, C8	C8				S4, S5	
	R1_FR3.4	A6										Z4, C8	C8					
	R1_FR3.5					A6	A6	A6	A6	A2								
	R1_FR4																	
	R1_FR4.1	Z8		C13								C13	Z9, C13, S10				Z9	
	R1_FR4.2			C13								C13	Z9, C13, S10				Z9	
	R1_FR4.3												Z9				Z9	
	R1_FR4.4	Z8		C13									Z9, C4				Z9	
	R1_FR4.5					C9, C10	C9, C10	C9, C10	C9, 10	C9, C10			Z9				Z9	
	R1_FR5																	
	R1_FR5.1					Z1	Z1	Z2	Z3	A2								
	R1_FR5.2												Z9, S12				Z9, S12	
	R2_FR1																	
	R2_FR1.1			C8								C5, C6, C7	Z10, C5, C6, C7				Z10, C5, C6, C7	
	R2_FR1.2			C8, C12								C5, C6, C7	Z10, S6, S11, C5, C6, C7				S6, S11	
	R2_FR2																	
	R2_FR2.1			C12								C5, C6, C7	C5, C6, C7					

	R2_FR2.2			C12								C12	C12				
	R2_FR3																
	R2_FR3.1					C10	C10	C10	C10	C10		S7, C9, C10	S7, C9, C10				Z11, S7, S8, S9
R3 Planning module	R3_FR1																
	R3_FR1.1			C5													A1
	R3_FR1.2			C5									S10				A1, S10
	R3_FR1.3			C5								C5	C5				A1
	R3_FR1.4			A1, C13									A1				A1
	R3_FR1.5																A16
R4 Circular economy module	R4_FR1																
	R4_FR1.1												A14	A14			A14
	R4_FR1.1.1												A14	A14			
	R4_FR1.1.2																A14
	R4_FR1.1.3												A14	A14			A14
	R4_FR1.2			A14				A14	A14				A14	A14			A14
	R4_FR1.2.1			A14				A14	A14								A14
	R4_FR1.2.2			A14				A14	A14								
R5-6-7 APPs	R5-6-7_FR1																
	R5-6-7_FR1.1	A6, A4				C1,C2,C3	C1,C2,C3	C1,C2,C3	Z3, C1, C2, C3	A2, C1, C2, C3		C5	C5		A3		A7

	R5-6-7_FR1.2																	A7
R5 Food app	R5_FR1																	
	R5_FR1.2									A2							A3	
	R5_FR1.3									A2								
	R5_FR1.5									A2							A3	
	R5_FR1.6									A2							A3	
R6 Local trade app	R6_FR1																	
	R6_FR1.2	A4																
	R6_FR1.3	A4		A5		A5		C9, C10	C10	C10								
	R6_FR1.4	A4		A5		A5		C9, C10	C12	C12								
	R6_FR1.5	A4		A5		A5							C10	C10				A5
	R6_FR1.7	A4		A5		A5												A5
R7 Citizen app	R7_FR1																	
	R7_FR1.1	C3				C2, C3							C10, C13	C10, C13				
	R7_FR1.2	A6																
	R7_FR1.3	A6																
	R7_FR1.4	A6, C3				C3		C10	C10	C10	C10	C10	C10, C13	C10, C13				
	R7_FR1.5	A15, C10				C10		C10	C10	C10	C10	C10	C10, C13	C10, C13				
R 8 to 15 (ICT social actions)	R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR1																	
	R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR1.1	A9	A8, A9			A9		A8						A9	A9	A9		A9
	R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2																	

	R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2.1			A8, A9, C13														
	R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2.2			A8, A9, 13, C13														
	R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2.3			A8, A9, C10	A8, A9											A8, A9	A8, A9	
	R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2.4			A8, A9	A8, A9											A8, A9	A8, A9	
R8 (Innovative teaching units)	R8_FR1																	
	R8_FR1.1		A8	A8	A8													
	R8_FR1.2			A8	A8													
	R8_FR1.3			A8	A8							A8						A8
R9 (Sorting game)	R9_FR1																	
	R9_FR1.1	A9	A9															
R10 (Eco-design game)	R10_FR1																	
	R10_FR1.1		A9	A9														
	R10_FR1.2		A9	A9														
R11 (Planning game)	R11_FR1																	
	R11_FR1.1			A9								A9	A9	A9				A9
	R11_FR1.2			A9								A9	A9	A9				A9
R12 (Virtual city game)	R12_FR1																	
	R12_FR1.1			A9, C13														
	R12_FR1.2	A9		A9								A9	A9	A9				A9
	R12_FR1.3			A9	A9								A9					A9
R13-14	R13-14-15_FR1																	

	R13-14-15_FR1.1				A9	A9							A9				A9
R17 (Innovative awareness actions)	R17_FR1																
	R17_FR1.1				A11C3, C4, C13	A11											
	R17_FR1.2				A11	A11											
	R17_FR1.3		A11														
	R17_FR1.4				A11, C13							A11	A11				A11
	R17_FR2																
	R17_FR2.1				A10							A10	A10				A10
	R17_FR2.2				Z7							Z7	Z7				Z7
	R17_FR3																
	R17_FR3.1	A12															
R19 Pre-dried and shredded bio waste	R19_FR1	H2, H3, H4, H5, H7, H8, H9, H10, H11, H12, H13, H14					H2, H3, H4, H5, H7, H8, H9, H10, H11, H12, H13, H14				H2, H3, H4, H5, H7, H8, H9, H10, H11, H12, H13, H14			H2, H3, H4, H5, H7, H8, H9, H10, H11, H12, H13, H14			H2, H3, H4, H5, H7, H8, H9, H10, H11, H12, H13, H14
	R19_FR2	H2, H3, H4, H5, H7, H8, H9, H10, H11, H12, H13, H14					H2, H3, H4, H5, H7, H8, H9, H10, H11, H12, H13, H14				H2, H3, H4, H5, H7, H8, H9, H10, H11, H12, H13, H14			H2, H3, H4, H5, H7, H8, H9, H10, H11, H12, H13, H14			H2, H3, H4, H5, H7, H8, H9, H10, H11, H12, H13, H14
	R19_FR3	H4, H5, H7, H8, H9, H10,					H4, H5, H7, H8, H9, H10,				H4, H5, H7, H8, H9, H10,			H4, H5, H7, H8, H9, H10,			H4, H5, H7, H8, H9, H10,

		H11, H12, H13, H14						H11, H12, H13, H14						H11, H12, H13, H14				H11, H12, H13, H14
	R19_FR3.1	H4, H5, H7, H8, H9, H10, H11, H12, H13, H14						H4, H5, H7, H8, H9, H10, H11, H12, H13, H14						H4, H5, H7, H8, H9, H10, H11, H12, H13, H14				H4, H5, H7, H8, H9, H10, H11, H12, H13, H14
	R19_FR3.2	H4, H5, H7, H8, H9, H10, H11, H12, H13, H14						H4, H5, H7, H8, H9, H10, H11, H12, H13, H14						H4, H5, H7, H8, H9, H10, H11, H12, H13, H14				H4, H5, H7, H8, H9, H10, H11, H12, H13, H14
	R19_FR3.3	H4, H5, H7, H8, H9, H10, H11, H12, H13, H14						H4, H5, H7, H8, H9, H10, H11, H12, H13, H14						H4, H5, H7, H8, H9, H10, H11, H12, H13, H14				H4, H5, H7, H8, H9, H10, H11, H12, H13, H14
	R19_FR4																	
	R19_FR4.1	H6			H6			H6						H6				H6
	R19_FR4.2	H6			H6			H6						H6				H6
	R19_FR4.3	H6			H6			H6						H6				H6
	R19_FR4.4	H5, H7, H8, H9, H10, H11, H12, H13, H14			H5, H7, H8, H9, H10, H11, H12, H13, H14			H5, H7, H8, H9, H10, H11, H12, H13, H14						H5, H7, H8, H9, H10, H11, H12, H13, H14				H5, H7, H8, H9, H10, H11, H12, H13, H14
	R19_FR4.4.1	H7, H8			H7			H7						H7				H7

	R19_FR4.4.2	H7, H8			H7			H7							H7			H7
	R19_FR4.4.3	H7, H9			H7, H9			H7, H9							H7, H9			H7, H9
	R19_FR4.4.4	H7, H8, H14			H7, H8, H14			H7, H8, H14							H7, H8, H14			H7, H8, H14
	R19_FR4.4.5	H5, H7			H5, H7			H5, H7							H5, H7			H5, H7
	R19_FR4.4.6	H7, H13			H7, H13			H7, H13							H7, H13			H7, H13
	R19_FR4.4.7	H7, H11			H7, H11			H7, H11							H7, H11			H7, H11
	R19_FR4.4.8	H7, H10			H7, H10			H7, H10							H7, H10			H7, H10
	R19_FR4.4.9	H7, H12			H7, H12			H7, H12							H7, H12			H7, H12
R20 Bio fuel and compost production plant	R20_FR1																	
	R20_FR1.1														H17, H18, H19			H17, H19
	R20_FR1.2														H20			
	R20_FR1.3														H21			
	R20_FR2																	
	R20_FR2.1														H20			
	R20_FR2.2														H20			
	R20_FR2.3														H20			
	R20_FR2.4														H21			

APPENDIX D1. SEVESO

Pilot Planning Documentation

Technical Specifications

Seveso, June 2017

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION	4
1.1 WIDE DESCRIPTION OF THE PILOT SITE + MAP.....	4
1.2 COLLECTION SYSTEM CHARACTERISTIC.....	5
1.2.1 COLLECTION POINTS.....	7
1.2.2 COLLECTION TRUCK.....	7
1.3 TREATMENT PLANTS.....	8
1.4 SOFTWARE SOLUTIONS.....	8
2. TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS OF THE EQUIPMENTS	10
2.1 TREATMENT PLANTS.....	10
2.1.1 INCINERATOR.....	10
2.1.1 ANAEROBIC DIGESTION PLANT.....	11
2.2 COLLECTION SYSTEM.....	12
2.2.1 BINS.....	12
2.2.2 BLUE BAGS WITH RFID TAGS FOR RESIDUAL WASTE.....	15
2.2.3 YELLOW BAGS WITH QR CODE FOR LIGHT PACKAGING.....	17
2.2.4 AUTOMATIC BAG DISTRIBUTOR.....	17
2.2.5 COLLECTION VEHICLE IVECO 35Q MV7.....	18
2.2.6 COLLECTION VEHICLE ISUZU M50 R205.....	19
2.2.7 COLLECTION TRUCK 28 MC IVECO MAGIRUS 260E31/E3/75.....	20
2.2.8 GERA SYSTEM DEVELOPMENT (RESOURCES AND ACTIVITIES MANAGEMENT).....	22
2.2.9 USEABLE TECHNOLOGIES FOR DATA RELEVATION IN SYSTEMS WITH CHIPS USED IN THE FIELD OF PRECISION MEASURING.....	22

LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE 1. MAPS OF SEVESO	4
FIGURE 2. COLLECTION POINTS AND CONTAINERS	6
FIGURE 3. COLLECTION AREAS IN SEVESO	6
FIGURE 4. A TYPICAL COLLECTION POINT DOOR TO DOOR	7
FIGURE 5. COLLECTION VEHICLES	8
FIGURE 6. DIAGRAM OF THE DATA FLOW	9
FIGURE 7. INCINERATOR BRIANZA ENERGIA AMBIENTE S.P.A. – DESIO (MB)	10
FIGURE 8. ANAEROBIC DIGESTION PLANT MONTELLO – MONTELLO (BG)	11
FIGURE 9. BIN URBA 10LT	12
FIGURE 10. BIN URBA 40LT	13
FIGURE 11. BIN 120L	14
FIGURE 12. RFID TAGS ON BLUE BAGS FOR RESIDUAL WASTE	15
FIGURE 13. ROLLS OF BLUE BAGS FOR RESIDUAL WASTE	16
FIGURE 14. YELLOW BAGS FOR LIGHT PACKAGING	17
FIGURE 15. AUTOMATIC DISTRIBUTOR AND DATA FLOW	18
FIGURE 16. COLLECTION VEHICLE	19
FIGURE 17. COLLECTION VEHICLE	19
FIGURE 18. COLLECTION VEHICLE	20
FIGURE 19. RFID UHF ANTENNA	21

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE 1. COLLECTION SCHEME - CALENDAR.....5

TABLE 2. COLLECTION SCHEME - CALENDAR.....6

TABLE 3. MAIN TREATMENT PLANTS.....8

TABLE 4. INCINERATOR – MAIN CHARACTERISTICS 11

TABLE 5. ANAEROBIC DIGESTION PLANT – MAIN CHARACTERISTICS 11

TABLE 6. URBA 10 (30L BIN) 12

TABLE 7. URBA 40 (40L BIN) 13

TABLE 8. VEHICLE SPECIFICATIONS..... 19

TABLE 9. VEHICLE SPECIFICATIONS..... 20

TABLE 10. VEHICLE SPECIFICATIONS..... 21

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 WIDE DESCRIPTION OF THE PILOT SITE + MAP

Seveso is a town in the Region of Lombardy, Italy. It's located 21 kilometres north of Milan, has a population of 23,000 inhabitants, and a population density of 3,100/km²

The territory of the is highly urbanised, and the economy of the town has traditionally been based on the furniture industry.

Seveso became sadly famous when, on 10th July 1976, storage vessels at the ICMESA chemical plant broke, releasing several kilograms of dioxin into the atmosphere. The event came later to be known as the Seveso disaster. Nowadays in the main contaminated area there is a park called "Bosco delle Querce" (Oaks Wood).

Since the chemical accident, citizens of Seveso increased their environmental awareness, and this helped in achieving good results especially in separate collection of waste. Seveso reached a very high separate collection rate, 75% in 2016, and started some pioneering activities such as the introduction of the RFID tag on residual waste bags to monitor the individual generation of residual waste.

FIGURE 1. MAPS OF SEVESO

Being one of the 4 Waste4Think pilots. Seveso will perform these activities, with the aim of further increasing separate collection and enhance citizen's sensitization:

- Introduction of Pay As You Throw regulation
- Wide sensitization toward citizens with funny door to door meetings
- Summer eco-events with reusable tableware
- Promotion of reusable nappies
- Contest for virtuous households

1.2 COLLECTION SYSTEM CHARACTERISTIC

The collection system in Seveso is door to door (kerbside) for both citizens and commercial activities. In the following table there is the summary of the waste collection scheme:

TABLE 1. COLLECTION SCHEME - CALENDAR

	Collection system	Frequency
Residual waste	Door to door with transparent blue bags and RFID chip. Bags are individual for each household user.	1 / week
Food waste	Door to door with small brown kitchen caddies (7 l) or 120 l bins	2 / week
Paper and cardboard	Door to door, without container (packed or tied)	1 / week
Light packaging (plastics, metal, tetrapak)	Door to door in yellow transparent bags	1 / week
Other fractions (green waste, bulky, others)	Recycling centre	Open 6 / week

Residual waste

Light packaging

FIGURE 2. COLLECTION POINTS AND CONTAINERS

The city is divided in three areas, with a different calendar for the collection, as shown in the following map. All waste fractions are collected according to the following schedule:

TABLE 2. COLLECTION SCHEME - CALENDAR

Area	Residual waste	Food waste	Paper	Glass	Light packaging
1	Thursday	Monday, Thursday	Thursday	Monday	Monday
2	Friday	Tuesday, Friday	Friday	Tuesday	Tuesday
3	Saturday	Wednesday, Saturday	Saturday	Wednesday	Wednesday

FIGURE 3. COLLECTION AREAS IN SEVESO

1.2.1 COLLECTION POINTS

Collection points are on the kerbside in front of each building. Citizens take care of the delivery (from 10 PM) the evening before of the day of the collection.

FIGURE 4. A TYPICAL COLLECTION POINT DOOR TO DOOR

1.2.2 COLLECTION TRUCK

The collection fleet is based on both light vehicles (satellites) characterized by being single driver (the driver is also collector) with a tank of 7 cubic meters, and large compacting trucks (28 cubic meters) that receive satellites at transfer points. Both are diesel powered. Both have antennas to identify and record the ID user of the RFID tags, recording both during the collection and during the transfer between the satellite and the mother vehicle.

5 cubic meter light vehicle

5 cubic meter light vehicle

FIGURE 5. COLLECTION VEHICLES

1.3 TREATMENT PLANTS

In the following table there are the main treatment plants to which the main waste fractions of Seveso are delivered.

TABLE 3. MAIN TREATMENT PLANTS

Treatment	Description	Geographic coordinates (UTM 32N)	
Incineration	Residual waste. BEA	5050678	514073
Classification plant	Light packaging. CARIS VRD	5045914	503920
Anaerobic digestion	Food waste. MONTELLO	5058267	561561
Classification plant	Paper and Cardboard. LURA MACERI	5055728	503485
Recycling plant	Glass. EUROVETRO	5049478	500619
Classification plant	Bulky waste. RI.ECO	5041295	510578
Regional Composting	Green waste. VERDEAMBIENTE	5059036	500791
Recycling plant	Street sweeping. LA NUOVA TERRA	5058539	508044

1.4 SOFTWARE SOLUTIONS

Software solutions already running include the identification of residual waste bags, transmission of data to an external centralized server, and reporting of the number of bags read to the waste collection company and the municipality.

In the framework of Waste4Think, the invoicing module will be developed by Softline and the integration with the Citizen App is foreseen in order to make citizens aware of their waste generation almost in real time.

In the following diagram a schematic flow chart is represented.

FIGURE 6. DIAGRAM OF THE DATA FLOW

2. TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS OF THE EQUIPMENTS

2.1 TREATMENT PLANTS

2.1.1 INCINERATOR

Treatment	Description	Geographic coordinates (UTM 32N)	
Incineration	Residual waste. BEA	5050678	514073

FIGURE 7. INCINERATOR BRIANZA ENERGIA AMBIENTE S.P.A. – DESIO (MB)

TABLE 4. INCINERATOR – MAIN CHARACTERISTICS

Waste treatment capacity	Total waste received in 2015	Energy produced (MWh/y)	Energy put in the grid (MWh/y)	Distance from Seveso
149.260 MJ/h (113.600 t/y @ 3100 kcal/kg LHV)	72.069,39	34.962	24.573	8 km

2.1.1 ANAEROBIC DIGESTION PLANT

Treatment	Description	Geographic coordinates (UTM 32N)	
Anaerobic digestion	Food waste. MONTELLO	5058267	561561

FIGURE 8. ANAEROBIC DIGESTION PLANT MONTELLO – MONTELLO (BG)**TABLE 5. ANAEROBIC DIGESTION PLANT – MAIN CHARACTERISTICS**

Waste treatment capacity	Total waste received in 2016	Biogas produced (m ³)	Energy produced (MWh/y)	Distance from Seveso
369.000 t/y of which 362.500 t/y food waste	322.000	44.051.343	106.643	73 km

2.2 COLLECTION SYSTEM

2.2.1 BINS

2.2.1.1 FOOD WASTE: URBA 10L BIN

Description: Plastic bin, with main body, lid and handle with the following specifications:

FIGURE 9. BIN URBA 10LT

TABLE 6. URBA 10 (30L BIN)

Type	Width (mm)	Depth (mm)	Height (mm)	Volume (L)	Color
Urba 10	238 with handle	275	300	Ca. 10	Brown

Material: 100% virgin recyclable PP. It is stabilized against the effects of UV light and sudden temperature changes (intense cold and heat), resistant to chemical detergents and biological matter.

2.2.1.2 GLASS: URBA 40L

Description: Plastic bin, with main body, lid and handle with the following specifications:

FIGURE 10. BIN URBA 40LT

TABLE 7. URBA 40 (40L BIN)

Type	Width (mm)	Depth (mm)	Height (mm)	Volume (L)	Color
Urba 40	420 with handle	365	445	Ca. 40	Blue

Material: 100% virgin recyclable PP. It is stabilized against the effects of UV light and sudden temperature changes (intense cold and heat), resistant to chemical detergents and biological matter.

2.2.1.3 FOOD WASTE / GLASS: OPTIONAL BIN 120L FOR LARGE BUILDINGS

Provided by GELSIA Ambiente on request (food waste: brown, glass: green).

FIGURE 11. BIN 120L

2.2.2 BLUE BAGS WITH RFID TAGS FOR RESIDUAL WASTE

FIGURE 12. RFID TAGS ON BLUE BAGS FOR RESIDUAL WASTE

FIGURE 13. ROLLS OF BLUE BAGS FOR RESIDUAL WASTE

Characteristic of the bag:

Low density polyethylene (PE - LD) semi-transparent.

Thickness: not less than 25 micron,

Size: cm 70 x 110

Resistance: at least 15 kg of waste.

Characteristics of the RFID tag:

Passive Trasponder RFID UHF

Operating Frequency 865,6/928,6 MHz (optimized for the frequency 868 MHz)

- Standard EPC Global Class1 Generation 2
- Standard ISO 18000-6C
- EPC 128 bit;
- EPC programmed with ASCII code, unique and generated according to the certified system FIDES CODE (Frequency Identifier Double Encript Security Controlled Operation Dual Encoding).
- Reading sensitivity up to -20db with dipole antenna;
- Writing sensitivity up to -16 db with dipole antenna;
- Storage of at least 50 years in the memory;
- Resistance to thermal variation between- 40 and +70°C

- Operating temperature -25° to + 60° C;

2.2.3 YELLOW BAGS WITH QR CODE FOR LIGHT PACKAGING

Characteristic of the bag:

Low density polyethylene (PE - LD) semi-transparent.

Thickness: not less than 25 micron,

Size: cm 70 x 110

Resistance: at least 15 kg of waste.

FIGURE 14. YELLOW BAGS FOR LIGHT PACKAGING

2.2.4 AUTOMATIC BAG DISTRIBUTOR

SISTEMA INTEGRATO PER LA DISTRIBUZIONE SACCHI

FIGURE 15. AUTOMATIC DISTRIBUTOR AND DATA FLOW

Model: DAINTEcomat 24

Automatic identification of the user by means of the Regional Service Card

In Seveso there are:

- 2 machines for residual waste bags (432 rolls in each machine), 10 bags/ roll
- 2 machines for light packaging bags (216 rolls in each machine), 15 bags / roll

2.2.5 COLLECTION VEHICLE IVECO 35Q MV7

FIGURE 16. COLLECTION VEHICLE

TABLE 8. VEHICLE SPECIFICATIONS

Fuel	Diesel
Engine power	78 kW
CEE class	Euro 4
Engine	2.287 cc
Gear	Mechanic
Axles	2
Volume of the tank	7 m ³
Maximum load	650 kg
External length	6.128 mm
External width	2.000 mm
Antenna to read UHF RFID tags	Reader UHF medium range; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protocol ISO 18000-6C EPC Gen 2; Transmission of data including GPS position at the end of the collection route via GSM / LTE

2.2.6 COLLECTION VEHICLE ISUZU M50 R205

FIGURE 17. COLLECTION VEHICLE

TABLE 9. VEHICLE SPECIFICATIONS

Fuel	Diesel
Engine power	110 kW
CEE class	Euro 4
Engine	2.999 cc
Gear	Mechanic
Axles	2
Maximum load	650 kg
External length	5295 mm
External width	2.120 mm
Antenna to read UHF RFID tags	Reader UHF medium range; • Protocol ISO 18000-6C EPC Gen 2; Transmission of data including GPS position at the end of the collection route via GSM / LTE

2.2.7 COLLECTION TRUCK 28 MC IVECO MAGIRUS 260E31/E3/75

FIGURE 18. COLLECTION VEHICLE

TABLE 10. VEHICLE SPECIFICATIONS

Fuel	Diesel
Engine power	228 kW
CEE class	Euro 3
Engine	7.790 cc
Gear	Mechanic
Axles	3
Volume load	28 m ³
Maximum load	10.650 kg
External length	10 m
External width	2,55 m
Antenna to read UHF RFID tags	Reader UHF medium range; • Protocol ISO 18000-6C EPC Gen 2; Trasmission of data including GPS position at the end of the collection route via GSM / LTE

FIGURE 19. RFID UHF ANTENNA

2.2.8 GERA SYSTEM DEVELOPMENT (RESOURCES AND ACTIVITIES MANAGEMENT)

CONFIDENTIAL

2.2.9 USEABLE TECHNOLOGIES FOR DATA RELEVATION IN SYSTEMS WITH CHIPS USED IN THE FIELD OF PRECISION MEASURING

CONFIDENTIAL

APPENDIX D2. HALANDRI

Pilot Planning Documentation

Technical Specifications

Athens, November 2017

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION.....	6
1.1 WIDE DESCRIPTION OF THE MUNICIPALITY OF HALANDRI.....	6
1.2 COLLECTION SYSTEM CHARACTERISTICS	7
1.2.1 COLLECTION POINTS.....	13
1.2.2 COLLECTION TRUCK.....	13
1.3 TREATMENT PLANTS.....	14
1.4 SOFTWARE SOLUTIONS	16

LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE 1 MUNICIPALITY OF HALANDRI, [HTTPS://EARTH.GOOGLE.COM](https://earth.google.com), [HTTP://WWW.ERANET.GR/GEODATA/XRHSEIS_GHS.PDF](http://www.eranet.gr/geodata/xrhseis_ghs.pdf)6

FIGURE 2 COLLECTION POINTS, CONTAINERS AND SOCIAL WELFARE AT THE MUNICIPALITY OF HALANDRI 12

FIGURE 3 COLLECTION SECTION AREAS IN MUNICIPALITY OF HALANDRI..... 13

FIGURE 4 A TYPICAL COLLECTION SYSTEM AT MUNICIPALITY OF HALANDRI 13

FIGURE 5 A. EMAK ANO LIOSIA, ATTICA, GREECE MSW –MBT UNIT, B. AEROBIC BIO CYLINDER UNIT, C. WASTE RECEPTION AREA, D. BIOGAS PRODUCTION UNIT [HTTP://WWW.EPEM.GR/WASTE-C-CONTROL/DATABASE/HTML/CASE_STUDY-14.HTM](http://www.epem.gr/waste-c-control/database/html/case_study-14.htm) 15

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE 1 POPULATION INFORMATION	7
TABLE 2 MUNICIPAL SOLID WASTE FOR THE MUNICIPALITY OF HALANDRI (RECORDED 2011).....	7
TABLE 3 COLLECTION SYSTEM	8
TABLE 4 COLLECTION SCHEME - CALENDAR.....	12
TABLE 5 TREATMENT UNITS IN COLLABORATION WITH MUNICIPALITY OF HALANDRI	16

ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

MSW	Municipal Solid Waste
ELVs	End-of-Life Vehicles
WEEEs	Waste of Electric and Electronic Equipment
HFW	Household Fermentable Waste

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 WIDE DESCRIPTION OF THE MUNICIPALITY OF HALANDRI

Halandri is a suburb in north-east of Attica basin, around 12 kilometres (7 miles) from the centre; its location corresponds with one of the 10 ancient demes (boroughs) of Athens, known as Phlya (Greek: Φλύα). The municipality has an area of 10.805 km². Halandri was a small village until the rapid expansion of Athens during the 1960s and 1970s. Its built-up area is now continuous with those of the neighbouring suburbs Filothei, Marousi, Vrilissia, Agia Paraskevi, Cholongos, Neo Psychiko and Psychiko (Figure 1). Nevertheless, it has still a high ratio of open green areas per citizen in the Athens agglomeration. Several embassies are based in Halandri. It is one of the largest suburbs in terms of population, with more than 70,000 residents. It holds an independent municipality status since 1944. The population of the Municipality of Halandri recorded at 2011 to be 74.192 residents (Table 1). Halandri has a wide range of business activities, especially in the service sector and the food industry, and it also hosts some multinational companies.

Figure 1 Municipality of Halandri, <https://earth.google.com>,
http://www.eranet.gr/geodata/XRHSEIS_GHS.pdf

Table 1 Population information

Region	Population (citizens)		
	1991	2001	2011
Greece	10.223.392	10.934.097	10.815.197
Region of Attica	3.594.817	3.894.573	3.827.624
Municipality of Halandri	65.287	71.684	74.192

1.2 COLLECTION SYSTEM CHARACTERISTICS

Halandri's waste management system

Waste generation for the Municipality of Halandri is 38.881 tons/year which consists of 43% of Fermentable, 47% of Recyclable, 3% of Recycled and 7% other wastes (Table 2).

Table 2 Municipal Solid Waste for the Municipality of Halandri (recorded 2011)

Population	Total MSW	Qualitative composition of MSW			
		Fermentable	Recyclable	Recycled	Others
74.192	38.881 t	16.719 t	18.274 t	1166 t	2722 t
	100%	43%	47%	3%	7%

MSW collection schemes currently in place in the municipality of Halandri cover the majority of MSW generated within the area. The main streams are co-mingled collection waste (residue) (green bins), a separate collection system of sorted recyclables (blue bins), separate collection of paper/cardboard (yellow bin) and separate collection of glass (blue bell bin). Other specific waste streams separately collected are: used tires, end-of-life vehicles (ELVs), used lubricants, batteries and accumulators, waste of electric and electronic equipment (WEEEs) etc.

The waste management collection system of the Municipality of Halandri operates by using different colour of bins (Figure 2 and 3, Table 3) for both citizens and commercial activities. In the following table there is the summary of the waste collection scheme:

Table 3 Collection system

No	Wastes	Collection system	Frequency
1	Residual (co-mingled) waste (green bin)	Co-mingled kerbside collection (green bins, 1100L capacity)	7 / week
2	Recyclable waste, (blue bin)	Paper, glass, metal and plastic collection (blue bins, 1100L capacity)	3 / week
3	Paper and cardboard waste, (yellow bin)	Separate collection of paper and cardboard (yellow bin, 1100L capacity)	2 / week
4	Glass waste, (blue bell bin)	Separate collection of Glass (blue bell, 1100L capacity)	Contact with Hellenic Recovery Recycling Corporation (HRRC)
5	Household Fermentable Waste (HFW), (brown bin)	Collection of HFW from almost 1000 citizens within Waste4Think project	2 / week
6	End of life tires (ELT)	Collection of tires from tire shops	Contact with Ecoelastica S.A
7	Batteries	Small batteries collection	Contact with Afis S.A
8	Vehicle and industrial batteries	Collection of Vehicle and industrial batteries	Contact with Afis S.A
9	Waste of Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE)	Collection of WEEE in bins of 43 x45cm size.	Contact with Appliances Recycling S.A
10	Pruning	Side road collection point	5 / week
11	End of life vehicles (ELV)	Side road collection point	Contact with OIKANO EPE
12	Cooking oil	Collection tanks located at Super Markets	Contact with REVIVE S.A
13	Motor oil	Collection of motor oil at special collection points	Contact with ENDIALE S.A

Green bin for Residual (mixed) waste, (1100L)

Blue bin for pre-sorting recyclables, (plastic / metal / glass), (1100L)

Yellow bin for paper / cardboard, (1100L)

Blue bell bin for separate collection of Glass, (1100L)

Brown bin for Household Fermentable Waste (HFW), (30L)

Brown bin for Household Fermentable Waste (HFW), (120L)

Pruning

End of life vehicles (ELV)

End of life tires (ELT)

Electric and electronic appliances

Vehicle and industrial batteries

Cooking oil

Motor oil

Batteries collection

Home Composting (280L)

Submerged bins for mixed and recyclable waste at Halandri's city center

Figure 3 Collection section areas in Municipality of Halandri

1.2.1 COLLECTION POINTS

Collection bins at the Municipality of Halandri are located within a distance of no more than 500m each. Main different colours of bins as described above are **green bins** for residual waste, **blue bins** for recyclable waste, **yellow bins** for paper/cardboard and **brown bins** for Household Fermentable waste (HFW) (Figure 6).

Figure 4 a typical Collection System at Municipality of Halandri

1.2.2 COLLECTION TRUCK

The collection fleet at the Municipality of Halandri consist of 22 collection vehicles. Fourteen (14) collection vehicles for residual waste (green bin), five (5) collection vehicles for the recyclable waste (blue

bin), one (1) vehicle for the separate collection of paper/cardboard and finally two (2) new collection vehicles for the collection of HFW, for the brown bin.

Figure 5 some of the collection vehicles

1.3 TREATMENT PLANTS

The main solid waste management authority in the region of Attika is **EDSNA**. EDSNA was set up by a decision of the Ministry of the Interior in accordance with the provision of Article 211 of Law. 3852/2010 Kallikratis on Solid Waste Management Attica Region.

The purpose of the association is temporary storage, editing, uploading, recycling and overall recovery and disposal of waste, the operation of the facilities, the construction processing and recovery units, and to restore existing repositories (ChADA) in the territorial jurisdiction of the Region of Attica.

Under EDSNA's umbrella are 66 municipalities. There is a waste transfer station at **Schistou** area constructed in 1991 and located near Piraeus, processes 900 tonnes of municipal waste daily. Finally a sanitary landfill site at Ano Liosia called **Fyli** is the main disposing area managing of six thousand tonnes of municipal waste a day collected across Attica. It accepts 1.8 million tonnes of municipal waste a year. Fyli is not only the largest sanitary landfill site operated in Greece, but it is also the largest sanitary landfill site in Europe.

Figure 6 Landfill FYLIS

Figure 5 A. EMAK Ano Liosia, Attica, Greece MSW –MBT Unit, B. Aerobic Bio cylinder Unit, C. Waste Reception Area, D. Biogas production unit http://www.epem.gr/waste-control/database/html/case_study-14.htm

Table 5 Treatment units in collaboration with Municipality of Halandri

Treatment units in collaboration with Municipality of Halandri	Description	Geographic coordinates (UTM Zone 34S)	
		UTM Easting	UTM Northing
Landfill- Ano Liosia - FYLIS	Residual waste (Green bin)- FYLIS	732529.26	4217552.61
Facility of Mechanical Recycling and Composting Waste (EMAK)- Ano Liosia - EMAK	Pruning-Biowaste-(prunings) EMAK	737259.06	4217451.94
Biogas of Sanitary Landfill - Biogas Energy Ano Liosia S.A. BEAL SA	Residual Waste - BEAL SA	727318.66	4215742.74
Medical Waste Incineration Plant of A.C.M.A.R. (Association of Communities and Municipalities in the Attica Region)	Medical Waste-Apotefrotiras S.A	737406.49	4218230.15
Hellenic Recovery Recycling Corporation (HERRCO)	Recyclable waste – HERRCO S.A	746295.07	4214020.76
Material Recovery Facility (MRF) in Koropi, Attica	Recyclable waste – WATT S.A	752575.41	4198738.28
Tires waste – Ecoelastica S.A	Tires waste – Ecoelastica S.A	746490.75	4214523.09
Batteries waste, WEEE – Afis S.A	Batteries waste, WEEE – Afis S.A	748920.97	4215310.48
End of life vehicles (ELV) – OIKANO S.A	End of life vehicles (ELV) – OIKANO S.A	742127.98	4219520.81

1.4 SOFTWARE SOLUTIONS

The iLink New Technologies is the informatics company which collaborates with the Municipality of Halandri for introducing in two collection vehicles the GPS and informatics systems, for the 1). Household Fermentable Waste collection within the Waste4Think project and 2). for the separate collection of the paper/cardboard. The company introduces innovative information systems to the Greek market, called **PowerFleet**, the most competitive Fleet Management system in Greece which is translated in 3 languages (Greek, English and German), www.ilink.gr.

Figure 7 PowerFleet, www.ilink.gr.

APPENDIX D3. ZAMUDIO

Pilot Planning Documentation

Technical Specifications

Zamudio, April 2017

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. DESCRIPTION OF THE PILOT	5
1.1 INTRODUCTION	5
1.2 COLLECTION SYSTEM	6
1.3 COLLECTION POINTS CHARACTERISTICS	8
1.4 COLLECTION TRUCK DESCRIPTION	9
2. DESCRIPTION OF SOFTWARE SOLUTIONS	11
3. TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS FOR ZAMUDIO	12
3.1 BINS	12
3.1.1 SOLID URBAN WASTE AND P-C CONTAINERS FOR URBAN ZONE	12
3.1.2 SOLID URBAN WASTE AND P-C CONTAINERS FOR INDUSTRIAL AND ORGANIC CONTAINER	13
3.1.3 GLASS CONTAINER	14
3.1.4 LIGHT-PACKAGING CONTAINER	16
3.1.5 REUSABLES CONTAINER	17
3.1.6 DOMESTIC OIL CONTAINER	18
3.1.1 NEW SUW CONTAINER TYPE	19

LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE 1. ZAMUDIO LOCATION5

FIGURE 2. MANCOMMUNITY ORGANIZATION5

FIGURE 3. MANCOMMUNITY ORGANIZATION8

FIGURE 4. CONTAINER ISLAND IN ZAMUDIO8

FIGURE 5. CONTAINER SYSTEM9

FIGURE 6. TECHNICAL REQUIREMENTS FOR LOCKING AND MONITORING BINS SYSTEM9

FIGURE 7. TECHNOLOGICAL ELEMENTS OF ZAMUDIO PILOT..... 11

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE 1. COLLECTION SYSTEM 7
TABLE 2. TRUCKS USED TO COLLECT EACH FRACTION..... 10

1. DESCRIPTION OF THE PILOT

1.1 INTRODUCTION

FIGURE 1. ZAMUDIO LOCATION

The porch of ZAMUDIO is a municipality in the province of Biscay, Basque Country. It is located in the sub-region of Asúa Valley (Great Bilbao), near Bilbao City. Along with the municipalities of Sondika, Derio, Larrabetzu, Lezama and Loiu, Zamudio is part of the supra-municipal association ‘Txorierri Services’ (Servicios del Txorierri, 1989), which offers municipal services of good quality standards, at the same time that optimises financial resources, materials and personnel costs.

The region has 20.645 inhabitants, belonging 3.281 of them to the municipality of Zamudio. The municipality is close to Bilbao and hosts the Bilbao Airport and the Biscay Science and Technology Park, making it strategic and particularly special for the wellbeing of the region. It is also remarkable the high presence of other technological companies and industrial parks, being 5 of the 13 industrial parks of Biscay located in Zamudio. In reference to its waste management, it is managed by the abovementioned ‘Txorierri Services’ (Servicios del Txorierri), whose work is widening so that no residue is deposited in any inappropriate place for it (see Figure 2).

FIGURE 2. MANCOMMUNITY ORGANIZATION

ZAMUDIO has been developing during the last years an Action Plan, to combine the three main areas of the sustainable development: social, economic and environmental issues. To this end, the implementation of the Local Agenda 21 has been carried out, which will define the development of the municipality of Zamudio for the coming years. Firstly, a municipality Diagnosis was made through citizens' cooperation, as well as some representatives of the industrial net of the town, in order to transmit their needs and particular vision, thanks to some questionnaires to be filled and public meetings in which people could discuss different problems. By this way, it has been possible to detect challenges facing Zamudio to establish, in terms of sustainability, intervention priority objectives for the coming years.

Zamudio belongs to Biscay (Basque Country), which has 112 municipalities, for which the Province Council of Biscay (PCB) is in charge of the Permanent Observatory of Urban Waste. The main aim of the PCB is to develop waste management policies by the analysis of waste related information all along the municipalities. For urban waste collection, the following:

Being one of the 4 Waste4Think pilots. Zamudio will perform these activities, with the aim of further increasing separate collection and enhance citizen's sensitization:

- Full monitoring and decision taking information system
- Citizens' involvement and empowerment
- PAYT system implementation
- Social awareness actions

1.2 COLLECTION SYSTEM

In Zamudio is used bins system as collection system for citizens, and door to door system for industrial activities. On the one hand, citizens will throw their waste in selective fraction bins and USW bins. Selective fraction available are paper and cardboard, glass, light-packaging, domestic oil, reusables, batteries and organic, last one it is open with a key. To get this key, citizens will sign up a registration which is managed by Txorierrri Services. For bulky waste, they will have the chance to throw away in the cleaning point, which is in Derio, given their postal code; or calling Txorierrri mancommunity in order to agree a day to put bulky waste next to the closest containers. For the rest of waste, they should throw into rest-fraction-bin. Selective fraction bins are collected once a week and rest fraction bins twice a week.

On the other hand, each enterprise has their own rest-fraction-bin, which should take to street two days a week in order to be collected by Enviser. If they generate too much paper/cardboard or urban solid waste, they will able to ask Txorierrri mancommunity for a paper-cardboard or USW bin. Restaurants should make the same procedure to get an organic bin. Light-packaging bins are distributed in industrial areas, close from industries which demand it. Those selective fraction bins are collected once a week.

Frequency			
	Urban	Industrial	
ENVISER COLLECTION ENTERPRISE (a private company hired by Txorierrri Services)			
SUW (side-loading truck for urban zone and rear-loading truck for industrial zone)	2 days/week	2 days/week	
Paper-cardboard (side-loading truck for urban zone and rear-loading truck for industrial zone)	3 days/week	1 every 2 weeks	
Organic waste (back-loading truck)	1 day/week		
Batteries	Depend on filling level		
OTHER COLLECTION ENTITIES			
Light-weight packaging (Garbiker, a public company of the Provincial Council of Bizkaia: crane-lift truck)	1 day/week		
Glass (non-profitable organization is responsible of collection and treatment: crane-lift truck)	Depend on filling level		
Domestic oil (a private company hired by Txorierrri Services: rear-loading truck)	1 day/month		
Reusable (non-profitable organization is responsible of collection and treatment: crane-lift truck)	1 day/week		

TABLE 1. COLLECTION SYSTEM

In the next figure you can see the responsible of the collection and treatment of each fraction.

FIGURE 3. MANCOMMUNITY ORGANIZATION

1.3 COLLECTION POINTS CHARACTERISTICS

FIGURE 4. CONTAINER ISLAND IN ZAMUDIO

In the downtown of Zamudio collection points are island bins or isolated bins. Normally, in those neighbourhoods where are in rural areas, citizens have close to their homes the USW fraction bin. Nowadays, those who want to recycle, they should go to the nearest bins island (in urban areas), probably by car. To have better rates of recycling, it is planned to create complete islands (Organic, Light-packaging, Paper-Cardboard, USW and Glass fraction bins), trying to avoid single USW bins.

It will lock all containers, excepting reusable containers, to implement PAYT system in Zamudio. The new collection system is planned to be as you can see below.

FIGURE 5. CONTAINER SYSTEM

FIGURE 6. TECHNICAL REQUIREMENTS FOR LOCKING AND MONITORING BINS SYSTEM

1.4 COLLECTION TRUCK DESCRIPTION

The collection fleet is based on side-loading, rear-loading and crane-lift trucks. Side-loading truck and crane-lift truck needs one worker. The worker who drive the truck, must manage loading system too. Instead, rear-loading truck needs two workers, a driver and an assistant to manage back-load system.

	VOLUME (m3)	LOADING	GPS/BOARDING COMPUTER	POWERED BY
URBAN USW	25	Rear-loading truck	No	Diesel
URBAN P-C	2	Rear-loading truck	No	Diesel
Urban Outskirts	5	Back-loading truck	No	Diesel
INDUSTRIAL USW	24	Back-loading truck	No	Diesel
INDUSTRIAL P-C	24	Back-loading truck	No	Diesel

COMPOST 1	24	Back-loading truck	No	Diesel
COMPOST 2	5	Back-loading truck	No	Diesel
BATTERIES	5	Back-loading truck	No	Diesel
GLASS	40	Crane-lift truck	No	Diesel
BULKY WASTE	25	Open-load	No	Diesel
DOMESTIC OIL	20	Back-loading truck	On-board computer with direct connection to the application. Also, has GPS and smart phone.	Diesel
LIGHT-WEIGHT PACKAGING	15-17-20	Crane-lift truck	Gps and a route program, which allows you to go marking the filling level of each bin of the route and mark incidents.	Diesel
REUSABLE	15-20	Back-loading truck & Rear-loading truck	No	Diesel

TABLE 2. TRUCKS USED TO COLLECT EACH FRACTION

2. DESCRIPTION OF SOFTWARE SOLUTIONS

Zamudio has a web application developed in Angular, which is powered by REST services in C # (Web Api 2) to work with all relevant information, and a mobile application (AdiZamudio) developed with IONIC (Angular + Cordova), which is powered by REST services in C # (Web Api 2) to give news information, events, surveys, messages ... of the mobile application. It is compatible to package solutions in Windows, IOs and Android. Authentication to log in to the web and mobile application is based on OAuth 2.0 per Token. It will use a similar system to show how many bags are you throwing in containers, reaching to know how much you should pay in your next invoice.

FIGURE 7. TECHNOLOGICAL ELEMENTS OF ZAMUDIO PILOT

3. TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS FOR ZAMUDIO

3.1 BINS

3.1.1 SOLID URBAN WASTE AND P-C CONTAINERS FOR URBAN ZONE

CONTENUR

C3200 D
Side loading containers

- 146Kg**
Weight
- 3.200L**
Capacity
- 1.280Kg**
Nominal load
- 1.263mm**
Loading height

FEATURES

The body and lid are injection moulded in solid coloured high-density polyethylene.

Manufactured using environmentally-friendly recyclable materials.

No heavy metals in the pigments.

Ideal for different types of waste collection: paper & cardboard, glass, plastics & packaging.

Customisation of body and lid by thermal transfer or silk screen graphic. Maximum area 400 x 300 mm.

Product Approval Certificate awarded by TÜV Service GmbH in accordance with European Regulation EN 12574.

CE Marking with sound power level shown in accordance with European Directive 2000/14/EC 91

STANDARDS

[Click twice on the picture]

C1100 F
Rear loading containers

1100_L
Capacity

440_{Kg}
Nominal load

200_{mm}
Wheels diameter

FEATURES

The body and lid are injection moulded in solid coloured high-density polyethylene.

Manufactured using environmentally-friendly recyclable materials.

No heavy metals in the pigments.

Ideal for different types of waste collection: paper and cardboard, glass, packaging, organic matter, etc. ...

Available in a wide range of colours..

DIN, AFNOR, OSCHNER or VENTRAL lifting systems.

Customisation of lid with thermal transfer graphic, area: 230 x 45 mm.

Customisation of body with silk screen or thermal transfer graphic, area: 300 x 400 mm.

CE Marking with sound power level indicated in accordance with European Directive 2000/14/EC. 87,1 db.

Product Approval Certificate awarded by TÜV Product Service GmbH in accordance with European Standard EN 840

UN certificate for the transportation of hazardous goods.

STANDARDS

These dimensions are subject to the tolerances given in EN 840-1:2012.

F101282Z / 4-3-13 / Rev 0.0

[Click twice on the picture]

▶ iglú

El contenedor de tipo iglú es uno de los más extendidos en España. Este perfectamente diseñado para la recogida selectiva de residuos. Su durabilidad y resistencia está probada por miles de contenedores repartidos por toda la península. Este fabricado con Gelcoat (recubrimiento exterior), políster (plástico termoestable) y fibra de vidrio (refuerzo natural) consiguiendo de esta forma las mejores resistencias al impacto y a los agentes externos de la naturaleza como son los cambios extremos de temperatura, rayos ultravioleta del sol, viento, agua y ambientes marinos.

697V0506

boca bar

www.hesal.es

vidrio

[Click twice on the picture]

**- CONTENEDOR IGLÚ 4,2 m3 -
DIMENSIONES**

Designed by Juan C. Sampedro	Checked by Juan C. Sampedro	Approved by Andrés Blanco	Date	Date 16/04/2015	
CONTENEDOR VIDRIO_4,2_DIMENSIONES					
MOLDEO Y DISEÑO S.L.				Edition 1	Sheet 1 / 1

▶ duo3500

Es un contenedor concebido especialmente para la Recogida selectiva de residuos urbanos.

Este fabricado con Galcosta (pintura), políster (plástico termoestable) y fibra de vidrio (refuerzo natural) consiguiendo de esta forma las mejores resistencias al impacto y a los agentes externos de la naturaleza como son los cambios extremos de temperatura, rayos ultravioleta del sol, viento y agua.

Este nuevo contenedor de base rectangular está diseñado para poder adaptarse al entorno donde se sitúan contenedores de carga lateral para mantener una armonía con estos.

Manteniendo el sistema de doble gancho en forma de percha lo permiten una gran versatilidad al ser manejado por un solo operario.

La novedad del contenedor es que está compuesto por dos piezas unidas por encajes que garantizan una gran resistencia pero con la ventaja de poder optar a repuestos para el mismo y poder sustituir solo la parte necesaria.

Con el consiguiente ahorro en costes de mantenimiento que esto supone. Sus opciones de personalización, recubrimiento y sistema antivandal lo hacen idóneo para cualquier ayuntamiento, organismo público o empresas privadas.

papel

vidrio

3.1.5 REUSABLES CONTAINER

Capacidad del contenedor	2500 litros
Dimensiones del contenedor	1450 x 1205 x 1825 mm
Dimensión Boca de carga	880 x 300 mm
Altura de la boca desde el suelo	1540 mm
Posición del gancho	Al centro del contenedor
Altura total del contenedor	1825 mm
Peso en vacío	250 KG
Peso máximo admisible del contenedor	700 KG

Contenedor fabricado en chapa galvanizada de 2 mm (Aleación Z275) en caliente, con tratamiento antioxidante. Estructura de chapa realizada mediante plegados para construir una mayor resistencia del conjunto.

Base inferior en chapa galvanizada de 2 mm (Aleación Z275), con marco interior de tubo de 30 x 30 mm

Estructura superior curvada en chapa galvanizada de 2 mm (Aleación Z275), con refuerzos de tubos interiores de 40 x 40 mm

Esquineros exteriores realizados en perfil redondo de 2 mm (Aleación 5083) ensamblados soldadura interna

Unión de estructuras mediante soldadura de hilo y tornillería

El contenedor dispone de un gancho superior, para poder ser desplazado con un camión grúa

Cerradura especial de seguridad para abrir puerta de descarga

El tipo de pintura es poliuretano para exteriores con dos capas de imprimación antioxidante

Ficha técnica de los contenedores instalados en la Mancomunidad del Txorierrri

El contenedor de la firma Sanimobel SA está diseñado específicamente para que el usuario deposite el aceite doméstico usado que previamente ha embotellado en su domicilio, reutilizando envases domésticos tanto de plástico como de vidrio.

Para la introducción de los recipientes de aceite el contenedor dispone de dos buzones o bocas superiores, uno situado en la cara frontal y otro en la cara posterior uno de ellos situado a una altura de 90 cm para fácil acceso de discapacitados. Las bocas de carga son fácilmente accesibles, cómodas de utilizar, y evitan posibles golpes o atrapamientos.

Los buzones están diseñados para permitir la introducción de pequeños bidones o garrafas de aceite doméstico de hasta 10 litros. Las bocas de carga están dotadas de una tapa metálica basculante. Para evitar el ruido que pudiera producir la tapa al cerrar, va equipado con dos gomas en el soporte.

El contenedor está formado por dos elementos: la carcasa exterior y la cuba interior estanca para aceite embotellado, ambas metálicas. El diseño del contenedor es tal que ante la posible rotura de los envases o recipientes depositados por los usuarios, garantiza completamente su estanqueidad, y no permite ni caídas de recipientes fuera de la cuba interior ni que se produzcan derrames de aceite fuera del contenedor por ninguna causa. El contenedor cuenta con marcado CE.

La carcasa exterior del contenedor dispone de cuatro orificios en su base, dos en la parte frontal y dos en la posterior, para su atomillado y fijación al suelo desde el interior, para evitar vuelcos, movimientos o daños por actos vandálicos.

La carcasa exterior del contenedor está fabricada íntegramente en chapa de acero galvanizado de 2 mm. de espesor. La cuba o recipiente interior para la recogida de aceite es también de acero galvanizado, soldada mediante soldadura especial estanca MIG. Todo el resto de elementos metálicos sin excepción, inclusive los remaches, ganchos y tornillería, están tratados convenientemente contra la corrosión mediante galvanizado.

La cuba interior para la recogida de aceite tiene una capacidad nominal de 880 litros, que una vez llena de envases será capaz de soportar la carga. La cuba es completamente estanca y su diseño y colocación dentro del contenedor no permite caídas de recipientes fuera del mismo.

La cuba dispone en su parte superior de un gancho que permite su izado y manipulación mediante grúa.

También por motivos de seguridad, el contenedor está diseñado para que incluso si personas no autorizadas abren la puerta de acceso a la cuba, no se puedan extraer manualmente los envases con aceite que pudiera haber en su interior, al disponer de una barra transversal que lo impide. Esta barra impide también que la

[Click twice on the picture]

CONTENUR

**CONTENEDOR CARGA LATERAL PARA ORGANICA,
DOTADO DE CAJON VOLUMETRICO CON
CERRADURA ELECTRONICA**

NOVIEMBRE 2016

[Click twice on the picture]

APPENDIX D4. CASCAIS

Pilot Planning Documentation

Technical Specifications

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION.....	3
1.1 WIDE DESCRIPTION OF THE PILOT	3
1.2 COLLECTION SYSTEM CHARACTERISTICS	3
1.3 COLLECTION POINTS CHARACTERISTICS + PHOTO.....	4
1.4 COLLECTION TRUCKS DESCRIPTION.....	6
2. DESCRIPTION OF SOFTWARE SOLUTIONS ALREADY RUNNING AND IN WHICH EXTENSIONS SHOULD BE DONE TO INCLUDE THE W4T ECO-SOLUTIONS SUCH AS THE CITIZEN APP OR THE INVOICING MODULE	7

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 WIDE DESCRIPTION OF THE PILOT

The Quinta de São Gonçalo and Lombos Sul are two joint neighborhoods located in Carcavelos parish on the eastern point of Cascais municipality.

The area is urban with medium/high residential density as it is mostly three to six floor building apartments. As it is located near the beach, there is a lot of housing demand and most floor level activities are personal services such as restaurants, bars and others.

Currently, there are 1505 households where 2435 people live. A number that deeply changes as the summer arrives due to tourist demand on house and room offers for vacationers.

1.2 COLLECTION SYSTEM CHARACTERISTICS

The collection system is “collective” as we only collect waste from public bins which vary in capacity and size. Some of them are 800 liters and others are the “eco islands” (underground bins) that vary from 3 cubic meters to 5 cubic meters depending on the waste type. A truck is deployed from our central with a pre-defined route and they collect bins along the route. There are currently eight routes overall, and one in the test area. This is a daily activity for household waste (due to intensive production and odors that might arise from deposit) and with 1 to 4 weekly collections on selective recyclable waste, depending on filing levels and production.

1.3 COLLECTION POINTS CHARACTERISTICS + PHOTO

As seen in the location photo, there are over 88 new bins called (in Portugal) “eco islands” as they are underground containers with larger capacity. They will replace the existing 800 liters surface ones. They are of 5 cubic meters to 3 cubic meters in capacity and we expect to place the filling sensors to contribute for a more efficient assessment of waste production. For collection, they are elevated with a special hydraulic system to help the raising of the inner bin. The system is compatible with the existing one and therefore we can use existing trucks and collection equipment. All citizens will have recycling waste bins closer to their homes.

The main services of the test area bins can be summarized as follows:

- A. Control devices, integrated in the intake receptacles, for the transfer of waste by authorized users;
- B. FOBS to access the devices;
- C. Full preventative and corrective maintenance service;
- D. Full access to web based server and platform, where the devices can be managed and controlled.

Further considerations:

Lock system

Electro-Mechanic Lock and electronic board

Identification (tags)

The key provided to the user is the only mode of authorized access to the access control system. It consists of a RFID transponder “Smart Tag” that is not powered (passive) having the working frequency equal to 13.56 MHz.

Filling sensors

The system is constituted by an autonomous powered sensor using 3.6V long life batteries. The system has an integrated SIM card that provides data transfer between the unit and the server. The system uses infrared and ultrasonic technology that measures various fillings of the container during the day and sends the information to the server at programmed hours. Based on a single information exchange transaction per day, the life span of the battery would be expected to be 4 years

Technical Specifications (see Metro User Guide)

BATTERY TYPE	One 3.6V AA Cell Lithium Thioryl Chloride
BATTERY LIFE	10 years minimum. Assuming one report per day
OPERATING TEMPERATURE	-30°C to +70°C
DIMENSIONS	65mm x 70mm x 30mm
WEIGHT	.33 lbs / .15 kg
ENCLOSURE	IP67 submersible. Polyurethane encapsulated.
STANDARD THREAD MOUNT	Single M6 threaded insert. Ask for bracket details.
COMMUNICATION	SigFox wide area global network. 868 MHz and 902MHz. LoRa wide area networks. 868MHz and 915MHz. No SIM cards. No user accounts required.
ANTENNA	Internal high gain antenna
SHOCKS	200g each Axis (EN 60068-2-27/F4)
IMPACT	1K10 (EN50102/F4)
CE CERTIFICATION	CE 0980 Articles 3.1(a)(b), 3.2 (inside) (EN 60950-1:2006, EN 301 489-1-7, EN 301 511)
FCC COMPLIANCE	Compliant
REPORTING SCHEDULE	Once per day typical. Configurable.

1.4 COLLECTION TRUCKS DESCRIPTION

The trucks weight 26000kg and are Euro VI norm compliant with a diesel engine and a three-axel sizing. They have approximately 15 cubic meters with a compact rate of 2:1. They can elevate bins of 120 liters up to 1 100 liters and an “elevated” arm of the same capacity. Al this is automatic or manual, per preferences. It also provides a cleaning system for bins and collection area with an automatic sprinkler system or a manual hose.

Further considerations:

Communication type

Lock sistem to truck **ISM**

truck to platform **GPRS**

Filling sensor to platform **GPRS**

Protocol

Standard

Communication frequency

Filling sensor – once a day

Lock system - twice a week

2. DESCRIPTION OF SOFTWARE SOLUTIONS ALREADY RUNNING AND IN WHICH EXTENSIONS SHOULD BE DONE TO INCLUDE THE W4T ECO-SOLUTIONS SUCH AS THE CITIZEN APP OR THE INVOICING MODULE

In Cascais, technologic and information systems are implementing allowing the optimization of the waste management collection system. This optimization reduced fuel consumption and the need for maintenance operations. The fact that waste management policies are based on strategies to ensure the preservation of natural and the fact that the cost of waste collection represents the largest cost share in the global waste management system, created the need for greater efficiency and competitiveness that led to the development of a decision-making system based on reliable real-time data collection.

The data from waste collection routes is monitored in real-time to optimize the system. The waste containers were equipped with tags (transponder chips) and filling level sensors, while the vehicles were fitted with onboard computers and GPS tracking. The system also provides conversion of the processed data into performance indicators.

It is designed to provide the business intelligence in order to:

- Maximize the efficiencies of your collection fleet
- Increase asset utilization / performance
- Locate your assets
- Provide traceability and audit process
- KPI : Know profit or loss PRIOR to deployment

Ultrasonic Sensors are positioned above the maximum fill level of the container attached to underside of the cover. The advantage of this is the ease of access to replace batteries and cleaning if required.

The system is constituted by an autonomous powered sensor using 3.6V long life batteries. The system has an integrated SIM card that provides data transfer between the unit and the server. The system uses infrared and ultrasonic technology that measures various fillings of the container during the day and sends the information to the server at programmed hours. Based on a single information exchange transaction per day, the life span of the battery would be expected to be 4 years.

The sensors will be mounted in the bins and will provide the following data:

1. Bin Fill-level;
2. Route Optimization (including the cost of each collection route prior to sending out vehicles);
3. Real time maps and views.

This data will be fed back to the SmartBin management system via cellular network.

The program will provide the following standard features:

1. Remote monitoring of Fill-levels;
2. Real time and historical information to facilitate bin deployment strategies that optimize bin utilization;

3. Business intelligence in the form of community fill level reports to facilitate development of more cost efficient collection patterns.

Further considerations:

Software

MOBA's Mawis 2.0

Routs

Paper, packaging and household are fixed routs

Glass via optimizing routs via filling sensors

Services

Filling sensors communicate once a week

Extra alert if container full

kpi's provided

Paper Kg/Km

Packaging Kg/Km

Glass Kg/Km

Household Kg/Km

Paper collected filling levels

Packaging collected filling levels

Glass collected filling levels

Household collected filling levels.

**E1. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE: LIST OF CARDS WITH THE
COMPONENTS OF WASTE MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS IN
WASTE4THINK**

CARD	DESCRIPTION
<p>The image shows a blue recycling bin with the 'Planetearth' logo and 'Paper Recycling' text. The bin also features the 'ecobin' logo. To the right of the bin is a pile of various paper waste items, including boxes, newspapers, and magazines.</p>	<p>Paper container</p>
<p>The image shows a yellow recycling bin with a red and white striped hazard symbol on the side. To the right of the bin is a pile of plastic packaging waste, including bottles, cans, and containers.</p>	<p>Plastic packaging container</p>
<p>The image shows a green recycling bin with the word 'VIDRIO' (Glass) written vertically on its side. To the right of the bin is a pile of glass waste, including bottles and jars.</p>	<p>Glass container</p>

Remaining waste container

Organic waste container

Composter

Plastic bags

Clean point

Waste truck

Treatment plant

Sensors

Camera

Weighing

<p>The logo for FIWARE, featuring a stylized circular emblem composed of concentric, overlapping bands in shades of blue and white, positioned above the word "FIWARE" in a bold, blue, sans-serif font.</p>	<p>Fiware</p>
<p>An illustration of a server rack and a database cylinder. The server is a grey, vertical tower unit with a handle at the bottom. The database is a blue, three-dimensional cylinder with horizontal lines, representing data storage.</p>	<p>Database</p>
<p>A photograph of a modern control room or observatory. It features a large, curved black desk with several computer monitors displaying various data visualizations, including maps and charts. A black office chair is positioned at the desk. The room has large windows in the background.</p>	<p>Observatory</p>

Dashboard

Mawis / Wintariff / Routing

Invoicing module

	<p>Long term planning</p>
	<p>Food app</p>
	<p>Local trade app</p>

Citizen app

Tablets

Green procurement

Serious games

Learning material

Open data

**E2. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE: LIST OF CARDS WITH THE SENSORS
OF WASTE MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS IN WASTE4THINK**

CARD	DESCRIPTION
	<p>Waste container lock</p>
	<p>Filling sensor</p>
	<p>Volumetric chamber</p>
	<p>RFID tag</p>

	<p>Temperature</p>
	<p>Humidity</p>
	<p>GPS</p>
	<p>Mobile / GPRS</p>

	<p>WiFi</p>
	<p>LORA</p>
	<p>Radio broadcasting</p>
	<p>Camera</p>

Weighing

Mobile / Tablet / PDA

F. APIS (THIS APPENDIX CONTAINS A CONFIDENTIAL PART
NOT INCLUDED IN THIS DELIVERABLE)

List of the APIs

ID	Description	DATA PROVIDERS	USERS API
API_R1_1	Context Broker CRUD		
API_R1_1.1	- Information from waste container sensors	R1-sensor	R1-dashboard, R2-collection, R2-invoicing
API_R1_1.1.1	-- Filling sensors: ID of the container and the filling level	R1-sensor	R1-dashboard, R2-collection
API_R1_1.1.2	-- Waste container access system: ID and timestamp of the waste generator	R1-sensor	R1-dashboard, R2-invoice
API_R1_1.2	- Information from truck sensors	R1-sensor	R1-dashboard, R2-collection
API_R1_1.2.1	-- Weight sensors: ID of the container (respectively, food surplus) and the weight	R1-sensor	R1-dashboard, R2-collection
API_R1_1.2.2	-- High speed camera: ID of the container, estimation of the improper waste	R1-sensor	R1-dashboard
API_R1_1.2.3	-- GPS tracks: Information about the itineraries of the waste trucks	R2	R1-dashboard, R2-collection
API_R1_1.3	- Information from different sensors from the treatment plants	R1-sensor, R19-sensor, R20-sensor	R1-dashboard, R19, R20
API_R1_1.3.1	-- Control parameters: temperature, pH, humidity, etc.	R1-sensor, R19-sensor, R20-sensor	R1-dashboard, R19, R20
API_R1_1.3.2	-- Input materials: biowaste and food waste	R1-sensor, R19-sensor, R20-sensor	R1-dashboard, R19, R20
API_R1_1.3.3	-- Production of the different gases, energy, pellets, etc.	R1-sensor, R19-sensor, R20-sensor	R1-dashboard, R19, R20
API_R1_1.4	- Values calculated by the CEP	R1-CEP, R3	R1-dashboard, R3-long, R4, R5, R19 R20
API_R1_1.4.1	-- KPIs results (real and simulated)	R1-CEP	R1-dashboard, R3-long, R4
API_R1_1.4.2	-- Models forecastings	R1-CEP, R3	R1-dashboard, R3-long, R4, R5, R19 R20
API_R1_1.4.3	-- Invoices	R1-CEP	R2-invoice, R7
API_R1_1.4.4	-- Numerical transforms of the values of the entities (aggregation, anonimization, etc.)	R1-CEP	R1-dashboard, R7
API_R1_1.4.5	-- Alerts	R1-CEP	R1-dashboard, R7
API_R1_1.5	- Information about the transactions of the different apps	R1-sensor	R1-dashboard, R2-invoice, R5, R6, R7
API_R1_1.5.1	-- Food transactions	R5	R1-dashboard, R5
API_R1_1.5.2	-- Coupon transactions	R6	R1-dashboard, R2-invoice, R6, R7
API_R1_1.6	- Incidences from the citizen app	User	R1-dashboard, R2-collection, R7
API_R1_1.7	- Web crawler data.	R1-sensor	R1-dashboard
API_R1_1.8	- Information retrieved from eco-events (weight, surveys, etc.)	R1-sensor, User	R1-dashboard
API_R1_1.9	- Socio-economic information of the pilots	R1-backend	R1-dashboard
API_R1_1.10	- Best practices	User	R1-dashboard, R7
API_R1_1.10.1	-- Best practices (circular economy)	User	R1-dashboard
API_R1_1.10.2	-- Best practices (local trade) by geographical area	User, R6	R7
API_R1_1.11	- Learning analytics information	R8, R9, R10, R11, R12	R1-dashboard
API_R1_1.11.1	-- Use of the different Learning Materials (TBD)	R8	R1-dashboard
API_R1_1.11.2	-- Use of the sorting game	R9	R1-dashboard
API_R1_1.11.3	-- Use of the eco-design game (TBD)	R10	R1-dashboard
API_R1_1.11.4	-- Use of the planning game (TBD)	R11	R1-dashboard

API_R1_1.11.5	-- Use of the virtual city game (TBD)	R12	R1-dashboard
API_R1_2	Persistence CRUD (all historic)		
API_R1_2.1	- Information from the waste container sensors	R1-context broker	R1-dashboard, R2-invoicing, R2-collection, R3-long
API_R1_2.1.1	-- Filling sensors: ID of the container and the filling level	R1-context broker	R1-dashboard, R2-collection, R3-long
API_R1_2.1.2	-- Waste container access system: ID and timestamp of the waste generator	R1-context broker	R1-dashboard, R2-invoicing, R2-collection, R3-long
API_R1_2.2	- Information from truck sensors	R1-context broker	R1-dashboard, R2-invoicing, R3-long
API_R1_2.2.1	-- Weight sensors: ID of the container (respectively, food surplus) and the weight	R1-context broker	R1-dashboard, R2-invoicing
API_R1_2.2.2	-- High speed camera: ID of the container, estimation of the improper waste	R1-context broker	R1-dashboard
API_R1_2.2.3	-- GPS tracks: Information about the itineraries of the waste trucks	R1-context broker	R1-dashboard, R3-long
API_R1_2.3	- Information from different sensors from the treatment plants	R1-context broker	R1-dashboard, R3-long, R4, R19, R20
API_R1_2.3.1	-- Control parameters: temperature, pH, humidity, etc.	R1-context broker	R1-dashboard, R3-long, R4, R19, R20
API_R1_2.3.2	-- Input materials: biowaste and food waste	R1-context broker	R1-dashboard, R3-long, R4, R19, R20
API_R1_2.3.3	-- Production of the different gases, energy, pellets, etc.	R1-context broker	R1-dashboard, R3-long, R4, R19, R20
API_R1_2.4	- Values calculated by the CEP	R1-context broker	R2-invoicing, R2-collection, R3-long, R3-green, R3-zero, R5, R7, R8, R9, R11, R12
API_R1_2.4.1	-- KPIs results (real and simulated)	R1-context broker	R3-long, R3-green, R3-zero, R8, R9, R11, R12
API_R1_2.4.2	-- Models forecastings	R1-context broker	R2-collection, R3-long, R5
API_R1_2.4.3	-- Invoices	R1-context broker	R2-invoicing, R7
API_R1_2.4.4	-- Numerical transforms of the values of the entities (aggregation, anonimization, etc.)	R1-context broker	R1-dashboard
API_R1_2.4.5	-- Alerts	R1-context broker	R1-dashboard, R7
API_R1_2.5	- Information about the transactions of the different apps	R1-context broker	R1-dashboard, R3-long, R5, R6, R7
API_R1_2.5.1	-- Food transactions	R1-context broker	R1-dashboard, R3-long, R5
API_R1_2.5.2	-- Coupon transaction	R1-context broker	R1-dashboard, R2-invoicing, R6, R7
API_R1_2.6	- Incidences from the citizen app	R1-context broker	R1-dashboard, R7
API_R1_2.7	- Web crawler data	R1-context broker	R1-dashboard
API_R1_2.8	- Information retrieved from eco-events (weight, surveys, etc.)	R1-context broker	R1-dashboard, R3-zero, R3-long
API_R1_2.9	- Socio-economic information of the pilots	R1-context broker	R1-dashboard, R3-long, R11
API_R1_2.10	- Best practices	R1-context broker	R1-dashboard, R4, R6, R7, R11
API_R1_2.10.1	-- Best practices (circular economy)	R1-context broker	R1-dashboard, R4, R11
API_R1_2.10.2	-- Best practices (local trade) by geographical area	R1-context broker	R1-dashboard, R6, R7
API_R1_2.11	- Learning analytics information	R1-context broker	R1-dashboard
API_R1_2.11.1	-- Use of the different Learning Materials (TBD)	R1-context broker	R1-dashboard
API_R1_2.11.2	-- Use of the sorting game	R1-context broker	R1-dashboard
API_R1_2.11.3	-- Use of the eco-design game (TBD)	R1-context broker	R1-dashboard
API_R1_2.11.4	-- Use of the planning game (TBD)	R1-context broker	R1-dashboard

API_R1_2.11.5	-- Use of the virtual city game (TBD)	R1-context broker	R1-dashboard
API_R1_2.12	- Sorting type: elements in the sorting type and sorting type of a waste	R1-context broker	R1-dashboard, R3-long, R4, R7, R9
API_R1_3	CEP rules CRUD		
API_R1_3.1	Create rules for KPIs	User	R1-CEP
API_R1_3.2	Create rules for Alerts	User	R1-CEP
API_R1_3.3	Create rules for Models	User	R1-CEP
API_R1_3.3.1	Create rules for forecasting entities values	User	R1-CEP
API_R1_3.3.2	Create rules for describe models of KPI	User	R1-CEP
API_R1_3.3.3	Create rules for forecasting food waste generation	User	R1-CEP
API_R1_3.3.4	Create rules for forecasting traffic condtions	User	R1-CEP
API_R1_3.4	Create rules for Tariffs	User	R1-CEP
API_R1_3.5	Create rules for numerical transforms of the values of the entities (aggregation, anonymization, etc.)	User	R1-CEP
API_R1_4	Admin Back-end CRUD		
API_R1_4.1	Users and roles	User	R1-backend
API_R1_4.2	Dashboard created by users	User	R1-dashboard
API_R1_4.3	What-if scenarios created by users	User	R3-long, R4
API_R2_1	Optimization of What-if scenarios		
API_R2_1.1	Routes optimizarion	User, R1-persistence	R2-collection
API_R2_1.2	Waste containers optimization (R3)	User, R1-persistence	R3-long
API_R2_1.3	Treatment plants optimization (R3)	User, R1-persistence	R3-long
API_R2_1.4	Waste collections optimization (R3)	User, R1-persistence	R3-long
API_R3_1	Simulation of What-if scenarios		
API_R3_1.1	Routes simulation	User, R1-persistence	R3-long
API_R3_1.2	Waste containers simulation	User, R1-persistence	R3-long
API_R3_1.3	Treatment plants simulation	User, R1-persistence	R3-long
API_R3_1.4	Waste collections simulation	User, R1-persistence	R3-long
API_R3_1.5	Green Procurement simulation	User, R1-persistence	R3-green
API_R3_1.6	Zero Waste Events and Ecosystems simulation	User, R1-persistence	R3-zero
API_R3_1.7	Circular Economy Best Practices simulation (R4)	User, R1-persistence	R3-long, R4
API_R9-R12_1	Stage editor		
API_R9-R12_1.1	Sorting types and probabilities	User	R9
API_R9-R12_1.2	LCA results for the products	User	R10, R13
API_R9-R12_1.3	What-if scenario	User	R11, R14
API_R9-R12_1.4	Best practices and objectives	R1, user	R12, R15

G. PILOTS DEPLOYMENT SCHEDULE

IOT

	2016												2017												2018												2019											
	Use case analysis						Preparatory Actions						Deployment & Integration						Preliminary Test						Full Test																							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	M1						M2						M3						M4						M5																							
	ref						star						ref						stat						ref						stat																	
DEVELOPMENT STATUS																																																
S1							B						RC						RC						1																							
S2							B						RC						RC						1																							
S3							1						1						1						1																							
S4							B						RC						RC						1																							
S5							B						1						1						1																							
S6							1						RC						RC						1																							
S7							B						RC						RC						1																							
S8							B						RC						RC						1																							
S9							B						RC						RC						1																							
S10							B						RC						RC						1																							
S11							B						RC						RC						1																							
S12							B						RC						RC						1																							
S13							B						RC						RC						1																							
IMPLEMENTATION STATUS																																																
Seveso Pilot																																																
S1							T						P						P																													
S3							T						P						P																													
Cascais Pilot																																																
S1							D						I						T																													
S2							D						I						T																													
S4							D						I						T																													
S5							D						P						P																													
S6							P						P						P																													
Zamudio Pilot																																																
S1							T						I						T																													
S2							D						I						T																													
S4							D						I						T																													
S5							D						I						T																													
S6							D						I						T																													
S7							Ø						I						T																													
S8							D						I						T																													
S9							D						I						T																													
S12							Ø						I						T																													
S13							Ø						I						T																													
Halandri Pilot																																																
S4							D						I						T																													
S6							D						I						T																													
S9							D						I						T																													
S10							€						I						T																													
S11							€						I						T																													

STATUS description

Integration of Sensors

- Ø The sensor have not been selected yet or the purchase have not started.
- € A tender, or similar procedure, have been sheduled to acquire the sensors.
- D Sensor have been installed but no integration with the rest of the components have started.
- I Sensors are being integrated with the rest of solutions at the pilot site.
- T Sensors have been deployed and have been integrated. Tests are being carried out in real conditions.
- P Sensors have been deployed and work as expected.

Development

- Ø The device has been designed but it was not started its assembly
- α Not all functionalities are implemented or some of them are in a "Wizard of Oz" type of implementation (the function exists but behaves trivially). Only partial test could be made.
- B All functionalities are implemented but some of them do not behave as expected. Obvious bugs are been found. The system is been tested in lab conditions.
- RC All functionalities are implemented and behaves as expected. Obvious bugs have been ironed out. The system is been tested in real conditions.
- 1 All functionalities are working as expected. The system have been tested in real conditions.

OPERATION AND PLANNING TOOLS

2016											2017											2018											2019																																						
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12																								
Use case analysis						M1	Preparatory Actions											M2	Deployment & Integration						M3	Preliminary Test					M4	Full Test						M5																																	
1						2	3						4	5						6	7						8	9					10	11						12																															
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DEVELOPMENT STATUS		2016											2017											2018											2019										
R1_FR1	To monitor the waste generation																																												
R1_FR1.1	Allow to identify the users to the collection system																																												
R1_FR1.1.1	Allow to identify the users by an ID card (NFC)																																												
R1_FR1.1.2	Allow to identify the user by an iBag (RFID) (D2D system)																																												
R1_FR1.1.3	Allow to identify the bin by a RFID tag																																												
R1_FR1.2	Monitor the delivery of waste (control access)																																												
R1_FR1.2.1	Control the access to the containers with a black list mechanism																																												
R1_FR1.2.2	Control the access to the containers with a white list mechanism																																												
R1_FR1.2.3	Locks must be reprogrammables																																												
R1_FR1.3	Allow to characterize the waste deposited																																												
R1_FR1.3.1	Identify the type of waste deposited (information of manual characterizations)																																												
R1_FR1.3.2	Provide help in the identification of the improper waste when emptying the bin/bag																																												
R1_FR1.3.3	Get the amount of waste deposited																																												
R1_FR1.3.4	Get the time when the waste is generated (deposited or surplus)																																												
R1_FR1.3.5	Get the localization where the waste is deposited																																												
R1_FR1.3.6	Get the number of iBags delivered to users																																												
R1_FR1.3.7	Monitoring the waste deposited in Eco-events																																												
R1_FR1.4	Get information about the state of the deposit point and composting plants																																												
R1_FR1.4.1	Allows the monitorization of the filling level (Bins)																																												
R1_FR1.4.2	Allows the monitorization of the temperature (Composting)																																												
R1_FR1.4.3	Allows the monitorization of the moisture (Composting)																																												
R1_FR1.5	Provide a fallback solution to publish information in the context broker																																												
R1_FR2	Get information of a collection route																																												
R1_FR2.1	Get the total fuel consumption of a collection route																																												
R1_FR2.2	Estimate the total environmental impact of a collection route																																												
R1_FR2.3	Get the GPS Trace of a collection route																																												
R1_FR2.4	Get the FMS information from the CAN BUS																																												
R1_FR2.5	Get the total weight of waste collected																																												
R1_FR2.6	Get the places where the bin have been collected																																												
R1_FR2.7	Get the time when the bin have been collected																																												
R1_FR2.8	Allow to emit a certification of the work done during the shift																																												
R1_FR3	Allow to report issues																																												
R1_FR3.1	Allow to report the overfill of a container																																												
R1_FR3.2	Allow to report vandalizing of a container																																												
R1_FR3.3	Allow to report incorrect use of a container or bag																																												
R1_FR3.3.1	Allows to report the presence of improper waste																																												
R1_FR3.3.2	Allows to detect if a container is not inventoried																																												
R1_FR3.3.3	Allow to report a missing container																																												
R1_FR3.4	Allow to take evidences (photos or videos) of the incidences																																												
R1_FR3.5	Allow to request of specific collections (bulky waste)																																												
R1_FR4	To display the state of the waste collection system																																												
R1_FR4.1	Allow to show the state of the waste collection system																																												
R1_FR4.1.1	Allow to show the [past, current, planned] state of the system																																												
R1_FR4.2	Detect anomalies in the waste generation patterns																																												
R1_FR4.3	Allows to personalize the monitoring system																																												
R1_FR4.3.1	Allows to filter the information provided by time, type and geographical distribution																																												
R1_FR4.3.2	Allows to select and configure the KPIs to show																																												
R1_FR4.3.3	Allows to define alerts																																												
R1_FR4.4	Allows to create automatic reports in PDF, Excel and CSV																																												
R1_FR4.5	The system must be able to crawl the web to get incidences																																												
R1_FR4.5.1	Crawl social networks like Twitter and Facebook																																												
R1_FR4.5.2	Crawl blogs and webpages																																												
R1_FR5	Provide a system to persist the information																																												
R1_FR5.1	Provide a communication channel to the persistence solution																																												
R1_FR5.2	Provide a communication channel to CKAN storage systems																																												
R1_FR5.3	Data Transmission to the Server (for MOBA components)																																												
R1_FR5.3.1	Secured data transmission for PAYT																																												
R1_FR5.3.2	Data transmission for real time reporting																																												
R2_FR1	To manage the waste collection service																																												
R2_FR1.1	To create the routes to follow every vehicle of the fleet																																												
R2_FR1.1.1	Depending of the fill level of the bins																																												
R2_FR1.1.2	Depending on the incidences declared																																												
R2_FR1.1.3	Depending on the vehicle and driver aviability																																												

STATUS description

Deployment

- I Sensors are being integrated with the rest of solutions at the pilot site.
- T Sensors have been deployed and have been integrated. Tests are being carried out in real conditions.
- P Sensors have been deployed and work as expected.

Development

- ∅ The device has been designed but it was not started its assembly
- α Not all functionalities are implemented or some of them are in a "Wizard of Oz" type of implementation (the function exists but behaves trivially). Only partial test could be made.
- β All functionalities are implemented but some of them do not behave as expected. Obvious bugs are been found. The system is been tested in lab conditions.
- RC All functionalities are implemented and behaves as expected. Obvious bugs have been ironed out. The system is been tested in real conditions.
- 1 All functionalities are working as expected. The system have been tested in real conditions.

	2016											2017											2018											2019											#		
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11			
	Use case analysis					M1	Preparatory Actions					M2	Deployment & Integration					M3	Preliminary Test					M4	Full Test					M5																	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42					
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R1_FR1.5																																															
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R1_FR2.3																																															
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R3_FR1.3.6																																															
R3_FR1.4																																															
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R4_FR1.1																																															

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		Use case analysis					Preparatory Actions					Deployment & Integration					Preliminary Test					Full Test																					
		M1					M2					M3					M4					M5																					
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R4_FR1.1	Provide recommendation to foster circular economy																																										
R4_FR1.1.1	Allow to create baseline and what-if scenarios																																										
R4_FR1.1.2	Evaluate the impact that several best practices have to foster circular economy																																										
R4_FR1.1.3	Search for viable circular economy best practices																																										
Halandri Pilot																																											
R1_FR1	To monitor the waste generation																																										
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R1_FR5	Provide a system to persist the information																																										
R1_FR5.1	Provide a communication channel to the persistence solution																																										
R1_FR5.2	Provide a communication channel to CKAN storage systems																																										
R3_FR1	To support the long term planning																																										
R3_FR1.1	Provide visual tools to create predictive and explicative models																																										
R3_FR1.2	Provide visuals tools to help in the creation of baselines and what-if scenarios																																										
R3_FR1.2.1	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the projected population and their spatial distribution																																										
R3_FR1.2.2	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the waste type and quantity																																										
R3_FR1.2.3	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the introduction of new treatment plants																																										
R3_FR1.2.4	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the introduction of new collection systems																																										
R3_FR1.2.5	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the mean for waste collection (electric truck, etc.)																																										
R3_FR1.2.6	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the localization of the collection spots																																										
R3_FR1.2.7	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the prevention campaigns																																										
R3_FR1.2.8	Allow to introduce and / or modify the economic instruments (tariff, PAYT, etc.)																																										
R3_FR1.3	Perform long term simulations of the waste management system																																										
R3_FR1.3.1	Simulate the combination of collection system plus treatment plans																																										
R3_FR1.3.2	Simulate the localization and size of the collection points and treatment plans																																										
R3_FR1.3.3	Design and simulate combinations of prevention campaigns																																										
R3_FR1.3.4	Take into consideration multiple criteria (economical, environmental and social impacts)																																										
R3_FR1.3.5	Simulate different transport means for waste collection																																										
R3_FR1.3.6	Simulate the effect of different combination of economic instruments																																										
R3_FR1.4	Allow the optimization of the waste collection for special events																																										

		2016					2017					2018					2019																					
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	#	
		Use case analysis					Preparatory Actions					Deployment & Integration					Preliminary Test					Full Test																
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	
												ref stat					ref stat					ref stat					ref stat											
R3_FR1.5	Help in the creation of green procurements																I					T					P											
R3_FR1.5.1	To identify criteria for the tendering																I					T					P											
R3_FR1.5.2	To evaluate the applicants of the tender																I					T					P											
R4_FR1	To foster circular economy opportunities																																					
R4_FR1.1	Provide recommendation to foster circular economy																I					T					P											
R4_FR1.1.1	Allow to create baseline and what-if scenarios																I					T					P											
R4_FR1.1.2	Evaluate the impact that several best practices have to foster circular economy																I					T					P											
R4_FR1.1.3	Search for viable circular economy best practices																I					T					P											

APPS

Requirement ID	Description	2018-34	2019-40
R7_FR1.1.1	Show the public information about the state of the waste management system (R1_FR4.1)	I	P
R7_FR1.1.2	Localization of the nearest collection point	I	P
R7_FR1.1.3	Localization of the clean points	I	P
R7_FR1.2	Allow to report incidences from mobile devices (R1_FR3)	I	P
R7_FR1.3	Provide information to reduce the footprint	I	P
R7_FR1.3.1	Provide information to reduce the amount of waste generated	I	P
R7_FR1.3.2	Provide information about the correct way of sorting waste	I	P
R7_FR1.5	Provide access to the invoices	I	P
R7_FR1.5.2	Provide a gamification experiences to improve the awareness of the citizens	I	P

EDUCATIONAL MATERIALS

SOCIAL ACTIONS

2016												2017												2018												2019											
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Use case analysis				Preparatory Actions								Deployment & Integration								Preliminary Test				Full Test																							
M1				M2								M3								M4				M5																							
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
ref stat												ref stat												ref stat												ref stat											

DEVELOPMENT STATUS		2017												2018												2019																																			
R17_FR1	To provide information and knowledge to the target groups on the social action in order to change habits and behaviours													a												β												RC												1											
R17_FR1.1	Establishment of protocols to assure that the participation is confirmed													a												β												RC												1											
R17_FR1.2	Establishment of protocols to monitor the impact of the innovative awareness action													RC												1												1												1											
R17_FR1.2.1	Establishment of specific protocols to collect the information needed to calculate the corresponding KPIs or other own indicators													RC												1												1												1											
R17_FR1.2.2	Establishment of other monitoring actions to detect the impact of the action and the acquisition of knowledge or habits change (surveys)													RC												1												1												1											
R17_FR1.3	Establishment of subactivities based on innovative awareness methods including the IT solutions													a												β												RC												1											
R17_FR1.4	To identify best practices													RC												1												1												1											
R17_FR2	To monitor participation in the different actions													a												β												RC												1											
R17_FR2.1	To monitor citizens participating in social campaigns													a												β												RC												1											
R17_FR3	To prevent waste generation and to promote recycling among different sectors of the population													a												β												RC												1											
R17_FR3.1	To prevent waste generation and to promote recycling among different sectors of the population													a												β												RC												1											

- DEPLOYMENT**
- I Sensors are being integrated with the rest of solutions at the pilot site.
 - T Sensors have been deployed and have been integrated. Tests are being carried out in real conditions.
 - P Sensors have been deployed and work as expected.

- Development**
- 0 The device has been designed but it was not started its assembly
 - a Not all functionalities are implemented or some of them are in a "Wizard of Oz" type of implementation (the function exists but behaves trivially). Only partial test could be made.
 - B All functionalities are implemented but some of them do not behave as expected. Obvious bugs are been found. The system is been tested in lab conditions.
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IMPLEMENTATION STATUS		2017												2018												2019											
Seveso Pilot																																					
R17_FR1	To provide information and knowledge to the target groups on the social action in order to change habits and behaviours	T												P												P											
R17_FR1.1	Establishment of protocols to assure that the participation is confirmed	T												P												P											
R17_FR1.2	Establishment of protocols to monitor the impact of the innovative awareness action	T												P												P											
R17_FR1.2.1	Establishment of specific protocols to collect the information needed to calculate the corresponding KPIs or other own indicators	T												P												P											
R17_FR1.2.2	Establishment of other monitoring actions to detect the impact of the action and the acquisition of knowledge or habits change (surveys)	T												P												P											
R17_FR1.3	Establishment of subactivities based on innovative awareness methods including the IT solutions	P												P												P											
R17_FR1.4	To identify best practices	P												P												P											
R17_FR2	To monitor participation in the different actions	T												P												P											
R17_FR2.1	To monitor citizens participating in social campaigns	T												P												P											
R17_FR3	To prevent waste generation and to promote recycling among different sectors of the population	T												P												P											
R17_FR3.1	To prevent waste generation and to promote recycling among different sectors of the population	T												P												P											
Cascals Pilot																																					
R17_FR1	To provide information and knowledge to the target groups on the social action in order to change habits and behaviours	I												T												P											
R17_FR1.1	Establishment of protocols to assure that the participation is confirmed	I												T												P											
R17_FR1.2	Establishment of protocols to monitor the impact of the innovative awareness action	I												T												P											
R17_FR1.2.1	Establishment of specific protocols to collect the information needed to calculate the corresponding KPIs or other own indicators	I												T												P											
R17_FR1.2.2	Establishment of other monitoring actions to detect the impact of the action and the acquisition of knowledge or habits change (surveys)	I												T												P											
R17_FR1.3	Establishment of subactivities based on innovative awareness methods including the IT solutions	I												T												P											
R17_FR1.4	To identify best practices	P												P												P											
R17_FR2	To monitor participation in the different actions	I												T												P											
R17_FR2.1	To monitor citizens participating in social campaigns	I												T												P											
R17_FR3	To prevent waste generation and to promote recycling among different sectors of the population	I												T												P											
R17_FR3.1	To prevent waste generation and to promote recycling among different sectors of the population	I												T												P											
Zamudio Pilot																																					
R17_FR1	To provide information and knowledge to the target groups on the social action in order to change habits and behaviours	I												T												P											
R17_FR1.1	Establishment of protocols to assure that the participation is confirmed	I												T												P											
R17_FR1.2	Establishment of protocols to monitor the impact of the innovative awareness action	I												T												P											
R17_FR1.2.1	Establishment of specific protocols to collect the information needed to calculate the corresponding KPIs or other own indicators	I												T												P											
R17_FR1.2.2	Establishment of other monitoring actions to detect the impact of the action and the acquisition of knowledge or habits change (surveys)	I												T												P											
R17_FR1.3	Establishment of subactivities based on innovative awareness methods including the IT solutions	I												T												P											
R17_FR1.4	To identify best practices	P												P												P											
R17_FR2	To monitor participation in the different actions	I												T												P											
R17_FR2.1	To monitor citizens participating in social campaigns	I												T												P											
R17_FR3	To prevent waste generation and to promote recycling among different sectors of the population	I												T												P											
R17_FR3.1	To prevent waste generation and to promote recycling among different sectors of the population	I												T												P											
Halandri Pilot																																					
R17_FR1	To provide information and knowledge to the target groups on the social action in order to change habits and behaviours	I												T												P											
R17_FR1.1	Establishment of protocols to assure that the participation is confirmed	I												T												P											
R17_FR1.2	Establishment of protocols to monitor the impact of the innovative awareness action	I												T												P											
R17_FR1.2.1	Establishment of specific protocols to collect the information needed to calculate the corresponding KPIs or other own indicators	I												T												P											
R17_FR1.2.2	Establishment of other monitoring actions to detect the impact of the action and the acquisition of knowledge or habits change (surveys)	I												T												P											
R17_FR1.3	Establishment of subactivities based on innovative awareness methods including the IT solutions	I												T												P											
R17_FR1.4	To identify best practices	P												P												P											
R17_FR2	To monitor participation in the different actions	I												T												P											
R17_FR2.1	To monitor citizens participating in social campaigns	I												T												P											
R17_FR3	To prevent waste generation and to promote recycling among different sectors of the population	I												T												P											
R17_FR3.1	To prevent waste generation and to promote recycling among different sectors of the population	I												T												P											

TREATMENT PLANTS

2016												2017												2018												2019																							
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12												
Use case analysis						M1						Preparatory Actions						M2						Deployment & Integration						M3						Preliminary Test						M4						Full Test						M5					
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12												
ref stat												ref stat												ref stat												ref stat																							

DEVELOPMENT STATUS		ref stat	ref stat	ref stat	ref stat
R19_FR1	Monitoring treatment plants (biowaste)	a	β	RC	1
R19_FR1.1	Recording the temperature of the Biowaste Treatment Unit (BTU)	a	β	RC	1
R19_FR1.2	Recording the moisture of the Biowaste Treatment Unit (BTU)	a	β	RC	1
R19_FR1.3	Monitoring of the treatment duration of Biowaste Treatment Unit (BTU)	a	β	RC	1
R19_FR2	Biomass product valorization	a	β	RC	1
R19_FR2.1	Quantity of biomass product loaded to bioreactor at NTUA (kg/day)	a	β	RC	1
R19_FR2.2	Monitoring the quantity of biofuel produced (m3 /day)	a	β	RC	1
R19_FR2.3	Monitoring the cost per collection route when collection truck runs with CNG (biofuel) (€/route)	a	β	RC	1
R19_FR2.4	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of the outputs	a	β	RC	1
R19_FR2.4.1	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of HYTHANE produced per kg biomass product	a	β	RC	1
R19_FR2.4.2	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of METHANE produced per kg biomass product	a	β	RC	1
R19_FR2.4.3	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of ETHANOL produced per kg biomass product	a	β	RC	1
R19_FR2.4.4	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of COMPOST produced per kg biomass product	a	β	RC	1
R19_FR2.4.5	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of PELLETS produced per kg biomass product	a	β	RC	1
R19_FR2.4.6	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of ALTERNATIVE FUEL FOR CEMENT INDUSTRY produced per kg biomass product	a	β	RC	1
R19_FR2.4.7	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of BIOSORBENT produced per kg biomass product	a	β	RC	1
R19_FR2.4.8	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of ELECTRICITY produced per kg biomass product through MFC technology	a	β	RC	1
R19_FR2.4.9	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of ANIMAL FEED produced per kg biomass product	a	β	RC	1
R20_FR1	To treat the food waste and nappies	a	β	RC	1
R20_FR1.1	Allow you to temporarily store the disposable nappies, kitchen waste and/or expired food product (EFP)s	a	β	RC	1
R20_FR1.2	Allow you to co-treat disposable nappies, EFP and /or kitchen waste in the Waste Treatment Unit (WTU)	a	β	RC	1
R20_FR1.3	Allow you to compost the WTU sludge	a	β	RC	1
R20_FR2	Monitoring treatment plants (nappies and biowaste)	a	β	RC	1
R20_FR2.1	Monitor and control the temperature of the Waste Treatment Unit (WTU)	a	β	RC	1
R20_FR2.2	Monitor and control the pressure of the Waste Treatment Unit (WTU)	a	β	RC	1
R20_FR2.3	Monitor the volume and composition of produced biogas in the WTU per kg of nappies and EFP fed in the system	a	β	RC	1
R20_FR2.4	Monitor the amount and quality of compost produced per kg of nappies and EFP treated in the WTU	a	β	RC	1

IMPLEMENTATION STATUS					
Seveso Pilot					
Cascais Pilot					
Zamudio Pilot					
R19_FR1	Monitoring treatment plants (biowaste)				
R19_FR1.1	Recording the temperature of the Biowaste Treatment Unit (BTU)				
R19_FR1.2	Recording the moisture of the Biowaste Treatment Unit (BTU)				
R19_FR1.3	Monitoring of the treatment duration of Biowaste Treatment Unit (BTU)				
R19_FR2	Biomass product valorization				
R19_FR2.1	Quantity of biomass product loaded to bioreactor at biogas plant (kg/day)				
R19_FR2.2	Monitoring the quantity of biofuel produced in biogas (m3 /day)				
R19_FR2.3	Monitoring the cost per collection route when collection truck runs with CNG (biofuel) (€/route)				
R19_FR2.4	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of the outputs				
R19_FR2.4.1	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of HYTHANE produced per kg biomass product				
R19_FR2.4.2	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of METHANE produced per kg biomass product				
R19_FR2.4.3	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of ETHANOL produced per kg biomass product				
R19_FR2.4.4	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of COMPOST produced per kg biomass product				
R19_FR2.4.5	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of PELLETS produced per kg biomass product				
R19_FR2.4.6	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of ALTERNATIVE FUEL FOR CEMENT INDUSTRY produced per kg biomass product				
R19_FR2.4.7	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of BIOSORBENT produced per kg biomass product				
R19_FR2.4.8	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of ELECTRICITY produced per kg biomass product through MFC technology				
R19_FR2.4.9	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of ANIMAL FEED produced per kg biomass product				
R20_FR1	To treat the food waste and nappies				
R20_FR1.1	Allow you to temporarily store the disposable nappies, kitchen waste and/or expired food product (EFP)s				
R20_FR1.2	Allow you to co-treat disposable nappies, EFP and /or kitchen waste in the Waste Treatment Unit (WTU)				
R20_FR1.3	Allow you to compost the WTU sludge				
R20_FR2	Monitoring treatment plants (nappies and biowaste)				
R20_FR2.1	Monitor and control the temperature of the Waste Treatment Unit (WTU)				
R20_FR2.2	Monitor and control the pressure of the Waste Treatment Unit (WTU)				
R20_FR2.3	Monitor the volume and composition of produced biogas in the WTU per kg of nappies and EFP fed in the system				
R20_FR2.4	Monitor the amount and quality of compost produced per kg of nappies and EFP treated in the WTU				

- DEPLOYMENT**
- I** Sensors are being integrated with the rest of solutions at the pilot site.
 - T** Sensors have been deployed and have been integrated. Tests are being carried out in real conditions.
 - P** Sensors have been deployed and work as expected.
- Development**
- 0** The device has been designed but it was not started its assembly
 - α** Not all functionalities are implemented or some of them are in a "Wizard of Oz" type of implementation (the function exists but behaves trivially). Only partial test could be made.
 - β** All functionalities are implemented but some of them do not behave as expected. Obvious bugs are been found. The system is been tested in lab conditions.
 - RC** All functionalities are implemented and behaves as expected. Obvious bugs have been ironed out. The system is been tested in real conditions.
 - 1** All functionalities are working as expected. The system have been tested in real conditions.

H. COMMENTS FROM EXTERNAL REVIEWERS

COMMENTS FROM EXTERNAL REVIEWERS

External Reviewer #1

DATE 22/11/2017

Issue	Score		Comments
	Yes	No	
Is the format of the document correct?	YES	3	Move the table captions on the bottom of the table
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	YES	5	
Does the index of the document collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	YES	5	
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	YES	5	
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	YES	5	
Does the content have sufficient technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	YES	5	
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?	YES	3	The list of figures and the list of tables are missing
Are the indexes correct?	YES	5	
Is the written English correct?	YES	5	
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?	NO	2	the glossary section is missing
Glossary present in the document?	NO	2	the glossary section is missing

DARIO PELLEGRINO

ENG

External Reviewer #2

23/11/2017

Issue	Score		Comments
	Yes	No	
Is the format of the document correct?		3	
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?		4	
Does the index of the document collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?		4	
Is the content of the document clear and well described?		4	
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?		4	
Does the content have sufficient technical description to make clear the research and development performed?		4	
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?		3	
Are the indexes correct?		2	No figure & Tables index
Is the written English correct?		3	
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?		4	
Glossary present in the document?		4	

Jon Arambarri

Virtualware

External Reviewer #3

DATE 23.11.2017

Issue	Yes	No	Score (1=low to 5=high)	Comments
Is the format of the document correct?	x		4	
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	x		5	
Does the index of the document collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	x		5	
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	x		5	
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	x		5	
Does the content have sufficient technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	x		5	
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?	x		4	list of figure added in Appendix D1_CON-revSOFTline and in D1.1_Plots Documentation_2.0-revSOFTline
Are the indexes correct?	x		5	
Is the written English correct?	x		5	
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?	x		5	
Glossary present in the document?	X		5	Glossary added in AppendixD1_CONrevSof tline

Name G. Drosi; J. Avakian

Partner SOFTLINE